

Division of Education

School of Education and Social Sciences

THE IMPACT OF HOLDING FAITH, PARTICULARLY THE CHRISTIAN THEOLOGIES
OF HOPE AND SUFFERING, WHEN DIAGNOSED WITH DEMENTIA: AN IPA STUDY

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Abstract

Dementia is a growing phenomenon in the 21st Century as the population ages. A diagnosis of dementia is associated with fear, anxiety, and depression, as well as significant changes for the family members and friends of those with the diagnosis. The holding of spiritual beliefs can be a resilience factor in stressful life situations. There is, however, little research exploring the impact of holding Christian beliefs on one's response to receiving a diagnosis of dementia. Therefore, the aim of this study was to explore the lived experiences of people who hold their Christian faith closely and have been diagnosed with dementia, aiming to better understand how holding faith impacts one on the dementia journey and with an aim of helping faith-based workers, social workers, families and wider society better support, empower, and love those with a dementia diagnosis.

This study adopted Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) as a qualitative research method in exploring the lived experiences of the impact of faith on the dementia journey.

Data from 8 participants was collected using semi-structured interviews, including submission of personal written statements from 1 participant. The interviews were analysed through an in-depth, interpretative lens.

The interviews conducted resulted in multiple findings. Of 8 participants, 7 clearly expressed that faith is a form of emotional and psychological support as they experience dementia, and an 8th implicitly discussed the importance of faith. Most participants expressed an understanding of God as a loving presence through their dementia journey, and vehemently not blaming God for their diagnosis of dementia. They also spoke of the need to be seen and approached by others, to have humour embedded into their lives and to have the Biblical stories understood as a source of emotional support. All participants acknowledged their dependence both on God and others as their dementia journey continues. Reclaiming dependence as a positive value emerged as a central theme and is discussed as a

recommendation for social work practice, social work education, and those engaged in faith-based work with individuals diagnosed with dementia.

It is clear from this study that faith has an over-all positive impact on the dementia journey, and that there are ways we in professional and church positions can understand and use the faith in an individual's life to help support them.

While this study was limited to exploring participants who hold the Christian faith, it is acknowledged that broader work needs to be done with people with lived experience of the onset of dementia from various religious and secular traditions.

Keywords: dementia, faith, embodiment, kenosis, stories, innocence, dependence.

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Dedication

I dedicate this Doctorate to my mom and dad and my mother and father-in-law.

My husband and I have been blessed to have parents who always put their children and grandchildren first and have been role models for us with our own children. Their steadfast support has made all our accomplishments possible, and I love them all.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Statement of the issue

Dementia is a growing issue in society and one that is being increasingly studied (World Health Organisation [WHO], 2021). Receiving a diagnosis of dementia can lead to anxiety, depression, and general mental distress (Alzheimer's Society, 2023). People respond to such stressors in different ways, but holding a religious faith closely can be a coping factor and can mitigate the negative response to such a diagnosis (Cook, 2016). Given the ageing population, as well as the increasing secularisation of society, it has been noted that social workers do not know how to adequately support those in society who hold a strong faith (Furman et al., 2004). Additionally, those who work actively in the faith community (such as ministers, priests, or Christian social workers) need to understand how those they support experience the world around them. The existing literature discusses the impact of faith on medical conditions and recovery, but little specifically discusses dementia and there is limited research on how holding a faith impacts an individual's experience and response to this diagnosis (Cook, 2016). This study will focus on those who hold a Christian faith and have received a diagnosis of dementia using qualitative techniques to delve into their lived experiences and perceptions of how their faith impacts them in light of their diagnosis.

1.2. Aim

The aim of this research is to explore the lived experience of those with a dementia diagnosis who hold a Christian faith closely and examine how this faith impacts their journey. I will then use that knowledge to recommend ways to enhance social work practice and education. Exploring the lived experience of those with dementia allows an exploration of how social workers, social work educators, and faith-based workers can better support individuals, taking into consideration the ways that faith impacts well-being. Once the impact of holding

faith is explored, this thesis provides recommendations of how the social work profession and those in faith-based positions can develop their own work by embedding their practice in faith-based approaches. This Professional Doctorate seeks to fill gaps in knowledge and contribute to the conversation about faith, dementia, and good social work practice, and how we can use this learning to better support those with dementia.

1.3 Objectives

The objectives of this study include:

1. Exploring the life, feelings, and perceptions of 8 people who have been diagnosed with dementia and self-identify as holding a strong Christian faith
2. Identifying the key-ways faith is understood by my participants, and how faith has impacted their life journey
3. Exploring the role of faith (or lack thereof) in social work education and the social work profession as a whole
4. Exploring how those in faith-based positions can further use the faith of individuals to support them in the dementia journey

1.4 Research questions

This study seeks to determine how holding the Christian faith impacts an individual's experience of a dementia diagnosis. More specifically, it asks what the impact is of holding Christian faith (particularly the theologies of hope and suffering) on the dementia journey? Research questions were devised before interviews, and then refined during analysis, as is consistent with the IPA process. This overarching question can be broken down into the following research questions:

1. How does holding a Christian faith affect an individual's view of their dementia diagnosis?

2. How does receiving a dementia diagnosis affect how one views or approaches their faith or God?
3. How does one's view of suffering, rooted in the Christian faith, affect their view of their diagnosis?
4. How does hope (associated with the Christian faith) affect one's view or approach to their dementia diagnosis?
5. In what ways does the Christian faith provide support or comfort to someone who has received a dementia diagnosis?
6. How can social workers and faith-based professionals improve the care and support provided to service users who hold the Christian faith and have a dementia diagnosis?
7. How can social work education improve the curriculum to better prepare social workers to work with clients who hold the Christian faith and have a dementia diagnosis?

1.5 Background/context of the study issues

1.5.1 Scottish context

While this study has relevance for many countries in the western world, special focus is given to Scotland for several reasons. The majority of my participants are Scottish. Scottish society is increasingly secular, with all the complexity that entails for those who still hold closely to faith (The News Letter, 2022). Additionally, my professional context is largely Scottish as I have taught and worked in Scotland for 20 years. My findings are hopefully relevant to many secular western countries, with the acknowledgement that they all have nuances within their culture. For example, the United States has more faith-based educational institutions which might mean some of my recommendations regarding change in the social work curriculum might be easier to address. Ultimately, I hope to take my findings and embed them in the social work curriculum in the university where I teach.

1.5.2 Policy background

The Scottish government has given more attention in recent years to the growing issue of dementia in our society. In 2019 at the EngAGE/Ageing Festival at Glasgow Caledonian University, the Minister of Ageing, Christina McKelvie, asserted a goal of making Scotland the “most ageing friendly country in the world” (McKelvie, 2019). Throughout the conference the increasing number of citizens being diagnosed with dementia was acknowledged and a call for public, private and third sector organizations to educate themselves as to how to support all impacted including caregivers. My colleagues and I noted that “faith” was seldom discussed by those at this conference and there is a wider debate about how and if broader society understands the role of faith in supporting those with dementia.

The Scottish Government (2017) published its third “National Dementia Strategy 2017-2020” in 2017. This strategy stresses the importance of improving the quality of dementia services; more specifically better care/treatment and more timely diagnosis. The previously published second strategy titled “National Dementia Strategy 2013-2016” was centered on enhancing post-diagnostic support and integrated person-centered support whereas the third strategy strengthens the focus on how to support individuals post-diagnosis in a flexible way at all stages of diagnosis and care provision (Scottish Government, 2017). It also calls for more data and research about actual techniques to support those with dementia (Scottish Government, 2017).

An IPA study that explores the post-diagnostic experience is congruent with the person-centred focus of the Scottish strategy. An IPA methodology focuses fully on the individual and employs an idiographic theoretical backdrop. Idiographic approaches are focused on a particular person in a particular context, which will be discussed in more detail in Chapter 3 (Pietkiewicz and Smith, 2012). The “particular person and particular context” approach of my

research methodology coincides with the current government and social work agenda of person-centred care.

There is some evidence that the Scottish government is beginning to appreciate the role of faith groups in enhancing the lives of all older people and those with dementia. Faith in Older People is a Scottish Charity which seeks to “enable a better understanding of the importance of the spiritual dimension to the well-being of older people” (The Diocese of Edinburgh, 2018, para. 3). This organization has convened multiple government roundtables regarding the development of Scotland’s dementia policy and new loneliness and isolation strategy which is titled, “A Connected Scotland” (Scottish Government, 2018). The Older Peoples’ Ministry team of the Salvation Army, which I represented, responded to the Scottish Government policy of “A Connected Scotland”, asking for a stronger acknowledgement of the role of the Churches in addressing loneliness among the older population and those diagnosed with dementia. These contributions have been increasingly welcomed by the Scottish Government and, as a contributor myself at the government round tables, I am cautiously optimistic that the role of faith will be respected as part of the comprehensive response to these issues. This thesis seeks to contribute to the overall discussion.

The Scottish Government is calling for a greater focus on the experience of dementia, expressed by people impacted by dementia (Scottish Government, 2013; 2017). It is crucial to understand and embrace patients’ perceptions of and feelings about their bodily experience and the meaning to which they attribute them, according to health psychologists (Leventhal, Nerenz, and Steele, 1984). There is evidence that maintaining religious and spiritual practices has a positive impact when people suffer from health conditions (Kaufman et al., 2007), yet minimal attention is given to the topic of dementia from a theological perspective (Cook, 2016). Given the Scottish Government’s call for a more personalized approach, it’s growing acknowledgement of the importance of faith groups, and calls for more research from subject

experts (Cook, 2016; Kaufman, et al, 2007), the time is appropriate for creative studies on the links between dementia/spirituality/theology and the individual.

1.6 Motivation in undertaking the study

This research is important because, as is shown in various sections of this thesis, the role of faith on the lives of service users is given scant attention by social workers in Scotland and other western countries (Cousineau, 2018). This lack of attention to matters of faith is in sharp contradiction to the importance of faith shown to me by older people in my professional roles. In my roles as a social worker in a Catholic Nursing home, as a faith-based dementia specialist building Dementia Programmes for the Salvation Army, and as a community care social worker in both Washington DC and Hamilton Scotland, older people have often spoken to me about the importance of their faith.

This juxtaposition between my experiences and the lack of faith-based learning material in the programmes I have taught in is concerning. This study will be beneficial to social work and faith-based professionals because it contributes to the discussion around the importance of matters of faith, and shows professionals how conversations around faith, as experienced by those they work with, can embed their work. This study offers ways of understanding faith from the older person's perspective and this understanding can help those in social work education design relevant curriculums. The dearth of material in western universities regarding the role of faith in many who live in our society is extremely concerning, and this study hopes to shed light on why we need to do better.

1.6.1 Professional Doctorate: Context of the study

To better understand the nature of this study, it is important to understand the academic context within which it was pursued. A Professional Doctorate is not the same as a Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.). Both are advanced degrees involving the development of theory and

knowledge, but the PhD is more theory based, while the Professional Doctorate is concerned with clear recommendations for the development of practice.

Professional Doctorates are intended to be practical, with a focus on applying knowledge that will have an impact on professional practice or policy (University of Portsmouth, 2022; Open University, 2023). Similar to a PhD, the Professional Doctorate supports original research, but the aim is to find novel approaches to integrating professional and academic knowledge so that there is a contribution to theory and general knowledge within the field.

When considering the professional knowledge base to which I am contributing, it is important to consider the diverse nature of my professional life, and to what exactly I am trying to contribute. I have been a qualified social worker for 30 years. In the course of my social work career I have worked in the legal system (I have a joint social work/law degree) advocating for older people with housing and health related legal issues; managed a team of nursing home social workers; performed community care assessments both in America and Scotland; became a Dementia Care Specialist; ran dementia carer support groups; and taught at UWS for 12 years as part of the social work team, with a focus on community care, dementia, and risk. I helped develop faith-based dementia programmes for the Salvation Army for 3 years, and now lecture for the Strathclyde University social work team. While my career has crossed professional practice, teaching, and faith-based work, it has always involved issues of ageing and dementia. I am committed to contributing to the knowledge base of all who work with those with dementia, but particularly social workers, social work educators and those in direct faith-based positions.

1.7 Contribution/significance

The role of faith in the dementia journey needs to be studied to a far greater extent, as there is a dearth of research on this topic (Cook, 2016). How the role of faith in an individual's life impacts their well-being is crucial knowledge for the social work and faith-based professions.

My project fills a gap in the research by focusing on the lived experience of 8 individuals who are navigating their dementia journey while holding a strong faith.

Sheridan and Hemert (1999) note that many students have received little training in religion in their social work graduate programmes. Oxhandler and Pargament (2014) agree that many social workers have not received education on religion and spirituality integration in social work practice. Given the emphasis of the social work profession on understanding the “whole person” it is essential that research takes place that focuses on those parts of the “whole person” too often ignored.

Key to my research is a belief that the rhetoric about “social death” of those with dementia needs to be challenged – and that we must hear from those with dementia themselves in order to challenge this belief. Xavier Symons states “There are few books and only a handful of scholarly articles directly addressing what dementia means for a soul’s relations with God. This paucity of theological and pastoral guidance may give the mistaken impression that dementia is a form of spiritual and social death” (Symons, 2021, p. 1). It is imperative that those in professions that seek to help people through difficult stages in their life – for the purposes of my study the focus will be on social workers and those in faith-based positions – start to challenge their own way of thinking of what it means to be a person with a worthwhile life.

This thesis contributes to the conversation about the role of faith in ageing and gives social work educators much to think about in the future while developing their curriculums - a neglected topic in most social work curriculums. It also encourages those already engaged in faith-based work to form a greater understanding of what it means to be on the dementia journey and hold a faith closely. It challenges social workers to overcome their distrust of the topic of faith and to see faith as part of our humanity. Finally, it argues that faith needs to be approached in academia and by researchers in a positive and encouraging way.

1.8 Limitations of the study

Limitations exist within the study based on methodology, sample size, and scope. First, this study is qualitative and more specifically uses IPA philosophy and methodology. Given this is the case, it is not intended that all findings be generalizable for all people. IPA is idiographic, looking very closely at the experience of the individual (Smith, Flowers, and Larkin, 2013). Due to the nature of qualitative research, the sample size is small which further reduces the generalizability of the findings. While these findings cannot be generalized, the experiences of individuals are highlighted allowing deeper insight into how faith can impact one's experience of having dementia and generalization is not expected in an IPA study. These insights provide guidance for recommendations for professional practice which is the focus of the Professional Doctorate.

This study is also limited in that it only includes those who profess and practice the Christian faith and because the participants are all Caucasian. While many other faiths exist, Christianity is the most predominant religion globally (31%) and provides a good starting point for exploring the impact of faith on one's experience of a dementia diagnosis (Pew Research Center, 2023). The cultural/ethnic limitation of this study may in part be due to the geographic location in which the study was conducted but is also affected by self-selection to participate. Future research with other faiths, races and ethnic backgrounds would be beneficial. It should be noted that IPA is an idiographic methodology, so limitations of this kind are appropriate.

1.9 Structure of the thesis

Chapter 1 provides an introduction to this study by identifying the statement of the issue. It looks at the aims, objectives, research questions, background, motivation, and limitations of the study.

Chapter 2 offers a literature review and exploration of theoretical frameworks regarding dementia, faith, embodiment, and other key concepts that are relevant to this study. The first part of chapter 2 reviews literature and theories explored before data collection began. After data collection began, new theories emerged. Consistent with IPA, these theories were explored more thoroughly in chapter 5 as part of the discussion of findings.

Chapter 3 offers a full exploration of the IPA methodology, critiquing it and showing how I have used it throughout my study. This chapter explores theoretical concepts and literature related to methodology that were not explored in Chapter 2.

Chapter 4 presents the study findings. Extracts from participant interviews are explored and themes are identified. Themes include Individual and Cross-Participant themes. In addition, GEMs are explored that emerged from my interviews (GEMs are explained in chapter 3). It is important to note that some long participant statements are offered which is in line with the idiographic nature of social work and the selected methodology. (Smith, Flowers, and Larkin, 2013). Chapter 4 also looks at themes in relation to Ricoeur's model of "empathy/suspicion".

Chapter 5 offers a full analysis and discussion of my findings. In chapter 5, theoretical material that was not addressed in full in Chapter 2 are included in a more comprehensive way. This is in line with IPA as an inductive approach which allows theory to emerge throughout the research process.

Chapter 6 offers recommendations for social workers, faith-based professionals, and social work education based on the findings. This chapter sums up the findings with a discussion of the phenomenology of love which concludes this thesis.

1.9.1 IPA: Use of first person

Note is given to my choice to use the first person "I" throughout this dissertation. This decision was made on the basis of the double hermeneutic that underpins IPA research. The double hermeneutic speaks to the voice of the participant, but also the role of the researcher

in “trying to make sense of the participant trying to make sense of their personal and social world,” (Smith, 2004, p.40). Therefore, nothing said in this dissertation can be separated from the “I” of the researcher – myself. In line with IPA, I have used reflective boxes at the end of some chapters to show my own emotional/psychological/growth process as I have undertaken my research journey.

1.9.2 Inductive approach

In accordance with IPA, it is important to go into interviews without pre-determining the type of theories that would eventually inform findings. IPA is inductive as opposed to deductive (Chatfield, 2022). Therefore, the first part of the literature review in Chapter 2 includes theories that were explored before the commencement of interviews but were then found to be especially relevant, after exploring the emerging themes. As themes emerged through the research process, additional relevant literature also emerged. This literature is introduced in Chapter 2 and given far more exploration in Chapter 5.

1.9.3 Reflective boxes

Consistent with the reflective nature of IPA research, a “reflective box” will appear in some chapters to provide journaling notes of the research process. Doing so is believed to establish quality in IPA research. The reflective box provides transparency and aids in the learning, reflective, interpretation, and bracketing processes of the researcher (Vicary, Young and Hicks, 2016). It is argued that this process allows quality to be dynamic, rather than static (Vicary, et al.). In my reflective boxes I will reflect on my growing understanding of IPA and my incorporation of IPA into every part of the research process – including in the very beginning. At the end of this chapter, a reflection is provided (Reflection Box 1), offering a discussion of embodiment theories. At the end of chapter 2, Reflective Box 2 will discuss the use of the literature review. Finally, Reflective Box 3 will discuss reflective and reflexive thought at the end of chapter 3.

Reflective Box 1: Embodiment

Very early on in my reading and thinking about faith and dementia I encountered embodiment theories. This was quite challenging for me, as I never really considered, focused on, or appreciated the idea of us being “bodies in the world” – it was something I took for granted. Although I spent years in direct social work practice and many of those years working with people whose bodies were impacted by ageing, it became apparent to me early on that I often glossed over “ageing bodies” as having any spiritual significance. It made me uncomfortable that I’ve always held negative connotations of the ageing body - and very likely still do.

Interestingly, I am in the life stage where myself and my peers are experiencing results of ageing. Before conducting this research I do not think I would have actively considered the role of our changing bodies in our psychology and spirituality as explicitly as I do now.

While there is a great deal of feminist literature on the female body, it is not literature that I have explored.

Actively thinking about the “body” in time and space has been an uncomfortable experience at times – and this discomfort is something I have needed to be aware of in all of my interviews. I have challenged myself on looking at the body – even the ageing body – as a “source of opportunity” and this has likely influenced my interviews. I have remained aware of what my participants can do with their bodies, the opportunities their bodies give them for connection with others, as well as the opportunity ageing bodies give younger bodies in terms of service and love. Positive psychology theories come to mind, and a recognition that as a society, we seldom see ageing as positive – only as inevitable.

Chapter 2

Conceptual Frameworks and Literature – A Scoping Review

2.1 Introduction

This chapter is divided into two sections. The first explores relevant material that incorporates the theory and conceptual frameworks explored at the outset of the study. It begins with an introduction to dementia and reviews the growing issue of dementia in our society as well as the policy context. A review of research is presented that explores lived experiences for individuals with dementia, as well as the research on the impact of faith on medical problems in general, and dementia in particular. Areas such as embodiment and personhood are explored as they relate to the dementia process and our understanding of “who” the person with dementia is.

The second section provides an introduction to literature about theories and conceptual frameworks that emerged during the data collection and IPA analysis process. These theories will be further explored in chapter 5. Because IPA is an inductive approach that prioritizes participant voice and impact above all else, I have made the decision to present new conceptual frameworks as they emerged for me through interviews and analysis. The role of the literature review in IPA research is contentious, and I have included a reflective box at the end of this chapter, looking more at the complexities.

Although this chapter includes both substantive and conceptual literature, it must be noted that this is not intended as a systematic review of the literature, but rather a scoping review.

A scoping review is often used to clarify concepts or identify characteristics related to a concept and answer questions that are exploratory in nature (Munn et al, 2008; Mak and Thomas, 2022; Sharma and Goyal, 2023). Grant and Booth (2009) refer to it as a “preliminary assessment” (p.95). My IPA study is exploratory in nature, looking at the lived experience of individuals with dementia and digging deep into their feelings, thoughts, and

ways of experiencing the world. My literature review offers the reader an overview of some of the literature related to concepts such as embodiment, personhood, and spirituality and dementia, without intending to exhaust the literature or offer a systematic analysis. Mak and Thomas (2022) state that scoping reviews can be useful for providing a map to the reader and my literature review can be seen as a map giving a glimpse of the key concepts.

2.2. Section 1: Initial Literature Review

2.2.1 Holding a Christian Faith

For the purposes of this study, holding a Christian faith is defined as someone who considers themselves a believing Christian, is engaged with their faith and expresses that their faith plays a prominent role in their life. The Christian faith is grounded in the events of the birth and life of Jesus, as well as in events following His death. The Christian faith is defined, in its simplest sense, as one who believes in God, and that God is reflected in the trinity - the Father, Son (Jesus) and Holy Spirit. For the purposes of discussing scripture in the Christian Bible, the translation called the New International Version will be used throughout.

The UK Data Service (2023) discusses two broad categories of Christian faith - Trinitarian and Non-Trinitarian. My study explores the lives of those who hold a Trinitarian faith, defining God as three in one - the Father, the Son, and the Holy Spirit. The Non-Trinitarian faiths include Christian Scientists, Latter Day Saints and Jehovah's Witnesses, which are not included in this study. While I am confident people who belong to these faiths have a great deal of their own insights and experiences to offer, I decided to limit my study. This project is not large enough to include traditions that differ to the extent that Trinitarian and Non-Trinitarian faiths differ. Trinitarian Churches are separated into two main categories; Protestant and Catholic, both which are within the scope of this study. Trinitarian Christians (Catholic and Protestant) in the UK can be broken down into 10 groups including Anglicans, Baptists, Roman Catholic, Orthodox, Methodists, Pentecostal, United Reformed,

Independent, New Churches (House Churches), and “others” (such as the Salvation Army and Quakers). There are at least 247 different Trinitarian Christian denominations in the UK that fit within those 10 broad categories (UK Data Services).

This study must be understood in relation to the complexities of holding a Christian faith in a largely secular western society. Both Scotland and the United States (the 2 countries where my participants came from) have declining religious populations (Voas, 2006; Voas and Chaves, 2018). From 1999 to 2013, the percentage of Scots who do not identify with any religion increased from 40% to 54% (Scottish Government Social Research, 2015). While America is a more religious country, it is far less religious than it used to be. The percentage of people in the United States describing themselves as atheist, agnostic, or “nothing in particular” has increased to 26% in 2023 (from 17% in 2009) (Pew Research, 2023). While 26 percent might not seem startling, it should be acknowledged that many who define themselves as religious do so simply because they nominally identify with the faith they were raised in, and the number of non-believers might very well be higher than 26 percent (Pew Research, 2023).

My participants ranged in age between 74 and 96, and all are experiencing living their older years in countries with declining religious attitudes. This increases the relevance of this study, as there might come a time (and in some circles this time has already come) when holding a Christian faith will mean one is a minority. Throughout this study, I address the fact that social work is a largely secular profession with limited understanding of how to respect and positively use faith and religion in their toolbox of approaches and interventions.

2.2.2 Dementia

Dementia is a progressive condition that, for many, robs them of their memories, cognitive ability, and ability to do tasks of daily living. The term dementia is a blanket term for neurological conditions that get progressively worse over time including Alzheimer’s

Disease, frontal lobe dementia, lewy body dementia, vascular dementia, and others (National Dementia UK, 2023). It is important to note that dementia can impact a person at any age but is more prevalent in people over the age of 65. The number of individuals in the UK with dementia is significant and growing. As of 2022, there were over 900,000 people diagnosed with dementia in the UK (Alzheimer's Society, 2022a). Alzheimer's Research UK estimates nearly 2.2 million individuals in the UK will be experiencing dementia by 2051 (Lewis et al., 2014). For the purposes of this dissertation no distinction will be made between the types and dementia will be defined as:

Dementia is a syndrome that can be caused by a number of diseases which over time destroy nerve cells and damage the brain, typically leading to deterioration in cognitive function (i.e. the ability to process thought) beyond what might be expected from the usual consequences of biological ageing. While consciousness is not affected, the impairment in cognitive function is commonly accompanied, and occasionally preceded, by changes in mood, emotional control, behaviour, or motivation (World Health Organisation, 2023, p. 1).

The unalterable and progressive nature of the diagnosis often has a detrimental psychological impact on the individual (Cook, 2016). Anxiety and depression often occur for those with dementia and for their families or caregivers (Krok, Zarzycka, & Telka, 2021). It is imperative that we, as a society, find compassionate and realistic ways to combat depression and anxiety related to having dementia or caring for those who have it. Because of the growing nature of this issue, there is a need for further understanding of the role of spirituality and faith on the dementia journey with a focus on lived experience.

The Alzheimer's Society discusses the psychological and emotional impact of dementia and the significant impact it can have on an individual's life. It can require quite a bit of adjustment when such a diagnosis is received and often brings about a variety of emotions including fear, anger, and embarrassment (Alzheimer's Society, 2022b). Furthermore, some emotional and behavioral changes can be a result of or influenced by the disease itself

including agitation, aberrant motor behaviour, anxiety, elation, irritability, depression, apathy, disinhibition, delusions, hallucinations, and sleep or appetite changes (Cerejeira, Lagarto and Mukaetova-Ladinska, 2012). As many as 20 to 32 percent of people with a dementia diagnosis experience clinical depression and between 38 and 72 percent experience anxiety (Badrakalimuthu and Tarbuck, 2012; Shub and Kunik, 2009). The cognitive difficulties associated with dementia can appear worse when combined with anxiety and depression (Badrakalimuthu and Tarbuck, 2012). The assessment of depression and anxiety disorders in people with dementia is challenging, because of the overlap in symptoms across diagnoses, such as decreased energy, fading memory, and poor concentration (Seignourel et al., 2008; Aldridge, 2015). The challenges associated with a diagnosis of dementia expand significantly beyond the direct symptoms of dementia.

2.2.3 Spirituality and Illness

There is a growing body of research looking at the impact of faith when one is diagnosed with an illness. Although there is a dearth of information regarding faith and dementia, the body of literature regarding other illnesses is helpful to demonstrate the possible impact of faith on the dementia process (Cook, 2016). Recent quantitative studies show a generally positive impact of faith on how one copes with illness (Mueller, et al. 2001; Miller and Thoresen, 2003; Kharitonov, 2012; Unterrainer, Lewis & Fink, 2014). While this dissertation is not seeking correlations such as these studies indicate, it is helpful to the discussion to know that there can be a positive correlation between holding a particular faith and general well-being through illness. My research seeks to explore individual experiences in an in-depth way to include both positive and negative experiences – however, it is important to note that current quantitative research shows holding faith can help with “positive coping” – knowing this can impact how we make use of faith when “being with” those with dementia (Unterrainer, 2014).

According to Koenig, King and Carson (2012), religion, medicine, and healthcare have always been highly interrelated across all population groups. Human beings are ‘meaning-making beings’, and therefore any significant event in their lives, particularly one that impacts their body and mind, will be examined for meaning. The studies highlighted by Koenig, King and Carson (2012) show a generally strong correlation between the positive impact of faith and well-being when one is ill. Of 326 quantitative peer-reviewed studies, 256 (79%) found religion/spirituality and well-being to be significantly associated in a positive way only. Only 3 studies reported an inverse relationship. At least 40 studies examined relationships with religion/spirituality and “hope”- of those, 72.5% reported only significant positive relationships with “hope”. An additional 32 studied the relationship between religion/spirituality and “optimism” and 81.3% reported positive relationships. Researchers at the Mayo Clinic concluded that religious involvement and spirituality are connected with better outcomes (Mueller, Plevak and Rumans, 2001). Those outcomes include greater longevity, coping skills, and health-related quality of life (even during terminal illness). Religious beliefs and spirituality engender positive emotions such as hope and contentment, while also reducing negative emotions such as hostility. This results in a reduction in anxiety, depression, and suicide among patients (Mueller, Plevak and Rumans, 2001). As will be shown in the results section of this dissertation, hope and optimism have been displayed as values held by the research participants and have been attributed to their faith.

2.2.4 The Intersection between Religion/Spirituality and Dementia

There is growing interest in the role of religion and faith in supporting those with dementia. Giannouli and Giannouli (2020) conducted a literature review that explored the possibility of using religious and spiritual beliefs in a clinical setting to support a patient with dementia. These findings are from the perspective of the diagnosed patient, the caregiver, family

members, and various health professionals. Giannouli and Giannouli examined only quantitative studies, using methods consistent with quantitative research. For this reason, their research is useful for a starting discussion of “participant voice” but only begins to capture that voice. The majority of the papers reviewed by Giannouli and Giannouli (50 out of 51) identified a positive influence of religiousness and spirituality, giving further justification for this current study.

According to Bell and Troxel (2001) religion and spirituality may offer people meaning as they deal with the life-altering diagnosis of dementia. Alzheimer’s Disease (a type of dementia) is considered a chronic illness and can cause the individual to feel disrupted and disorganized. These feelings can result in spiritual distress (Narayanasamy, 1996). Harris and Durkin (2002) note that spirituality may provide comfort and emotional support for those who have received this diagnosis. Teleological explanations (i.e. a belief in a higher-power) can help the patient to feel a sense of hope or comfort allowing them to believe that ‘all is not lost’ and that a higher power remains in control and is able to improve their current situation (Lombrozo, Telemen and Zaitchik, 2007). For some patients, their spiritual needs can be met with faith rituals and symbols which can bring about long-term memories through those communication channels (e.g. music, poetry, symbols) (Richards, 1990). Especially in the early stages of Alzheimer’s Disease, the opportunity to participate in religious events is found to be linked to self-reports of a better quality of life, while believing in God is claimed to be a significant coping resource (Katsuno, 2003). The findings of these studies show a clear relationship to the types of statements made by my participants while exploring their lived experience of their dementia.

2.2.5 Conceptual Literature - Dementia, Embodiment, and Personhood/Selfhood

Following a review of the relevant substantive literature, it is important to consider the conceptual literature particularly in the areas of dementia, embodiment, and

personhood/selfhood (used interchangeably). Personhood is a contested notion within the literature, and one that plays a vital role in our understanding of how we “see” a person who has been diagnosed with dementia (Kitwood and Bredin, 1992) and what their status is as a person, deserving of respect. Because our collective understanding of what it means to be a person impacts how we respect and love those with dementia, and how we understand their faith, a discussion of personhood is relevant to this study. There is evidence that the current understanding of personhood in western society is too focused on cognitive ability (Katz, 2023), and ignores other ways of understanding what it means to be a person. This is detrimental to the well-being of those with dementia as it does not take account notions such as long held faith, embodied faith, and relational understandings of what it means to be a person and a child of God. This must be challenged. In the following sections I offer a detailed discussion of Embodiment and Christian Embodiment, arguing that an understanding of these concepts is essential for our work with those with dementia, in general, and particularly with those who hold a Christian faith.

The participants I interviewed have held faith as an intimate part of their lives and understand dementia as impacting them in an intimate fashion. Their sense of self is greatly impacted by both their faith and their dementia diagnosis, and they show an understanding of themselves as persons of infinite worth, despite cognitive decline. The issue of “being seen” emerged very strongly in my findings, and clearly the positive and meaningful role of faith in the lives of my participants was often discussed in a “bodily” way – therefore these interlinking concepts are important to consider.

Loosely, personhood can be defined as that which makes one a ‘person’ and therefore that which makes them worthy of the respect to which our culture collectively believes a person is entitled. While simple on its face, the definition of personhood is varied and contested among sources. Frederick White argues that what it means to be a person can be constructed from

both an existential and a relational viewpoint. An existential construct sees personhood as a “state of being inherent and essential to the human species” (White, 2013, p.75), whereas a relational construct sees “personhood as a conditional state of value defined by society” (White, 2013, p.75). Whether we are a person, worthy of respect, simply because we are born biologically human – or whether we are a person, worthy of respect, due to society’s mores and values – is not a settled question. Tied up in these discussions is the role of cognition and the question of whether a person is worthy of respect “as” a person only because they have cognitive functioning or if our very bodies can give us the status of being a person. These questions have great bearing in how we approach those with dementia, who might see their own personhood as embedded in their status as a child of God.

The concept of embodiment, as discussed by Merleau-Ponty (1945), has become key to this overall discussion. Merleau-Ponty defined embodiment as the notion that it is impossible to separate the “I” (the person) from the body of the “I”. May-Hobbs (2023) notes, according to Merleau-Ponty, it is impossible to understand oneself as a person as apart from one’s body. Merleau-Ponty argued that any philosophical analysis must start with the fact that we exist in a physical world, and experience it with our physical bodies, and any philosophy that discounts this does not consider what it means to be human in any meaningful sense.

Much of the literature surrounding dementia, and what it means to be a person, has over focused on the cognitive losses inherent in the dementia process (Martin, Kontos, and Ward, 2013), and the belief that cognitive decline impacts one’s personhood. Merleau-Ponty's work states that cognition and perception are always embodied. This view can be taken a step further to encourage practitioners to reclaim the concept of embodiment and challenge this focus on cognition – an approach important for our understanding of those with dementia. As extant research encourages us to move from a “cognitive loss” approach to a “bodily opportunity approach” in the context of dementia, the definition of embodiment is

inconsistent and often not comprehensive in the literature. Scholars express different viewpoints about what it means to embrace an embodied version of selfhood in the context of dementia (Coaten & Newman-Bluestein, 2013). Due to the mixed definitions, Coaten and Newman-Bluestein attempted to provide a clear definition of embodiment within the context of dementia. They state:

Embodiment is a concept pertaining to lived-body and phenomenal experience that is crucial to better understand what it subjectively means to be human. It can be described as a continuum, requiring at least part of human awareness to be grounded in the internal subjective sensations of lived-body experience. The extent to which one is grounded in the lived-body experience affects one's perceptions, and understandings of the world (Coaten and Newman-Bluestein, 2013, p. 677).

While this definition is complex, it can be broken down to better understand the implications of holding an understanding of the concept of embodiment in our work with those diagnosed with dementia. It is helpful to dig deep into this definition and explore the various elements. The definition asks us to be aware that our understanding of our lived-bodies is part of what it means to be human. We might not always feel ourselves grounded in the lived-body experience, and our human awareness might also be partly grounded in other areas – such as our rationality, our dreams, our emotions – but keeping at least part of our understanding of being human fixed in our lived-body opens doors for us to understand our lives, and help others, in new ways.

For the Christian, the answer of what it means to be a “person” is tied up with the belief in the Imago Dei – that we are made in God's image, and that our bodies are therefore part of our sacredness and part of our very value – connecting notions of personhood and embodiment strongly to faith (Genesis 1:27). This is clearly important when looking to support and love those on the dementia journey and helps argue further why cognitive based understandings of personhood are deficient. Although dementia is a disease of the mind, it

tends to coincide with ageing, and impacts how one experiences one's body – for the Christian, while a body declines, it also retains the image of God imprinted on it. Because this entire project has been pursued through a phenomenological lens, the concept of embodiment, and how one experiences one's body, for one who holds faith, takes on special importance. Merleau-Ponty's phenomenology and work on embodiment from a Christian viewpoint has impacted this work greatly – both at the outset and particularly while transcribing the videos and delving deep into the data. This is discussed in greater detail in the Chapter on Methodology.

According to Martin, Kontos and Ward (2013), embodiment is an emerging field within dementia studies, “in which the body and embodied practices are placed at the centre of explorations of how dementia is represented, experienced, and understood. Through attention to embodiment we have begun to consider the body as a source of *opportunity* in relations with and between people with dementia,” (Martin, Kontos, and Ward, 2013, p.283). To consider the body as a source of opportunity expands the possible ways in which we can work and interact with those who have been diagnosed with dementia.

The participants I interviewed are in the later stages of their lives, with enhanced views of the significance of their own body (see emerging themes, Chapter 4). The faith of the participants clearly include some concept of their physical body as one which will be resurrected in perfection at a given time in history (Moltmann, 2002). The contradictory concepts (bodily decline and bodily resurrection) are ones they hold together in tension, but clearly the word “opportunity” is inherent in one's belief that one will be resurrected. Participants also expressed a strong notion of the need to be seen, further showing why an embodied view remains important. Certainly, the idea of embodiment as a source of opportunity emerged in more than one interview, as participants expressed the importance of touch, of being noticed, and of physical connection to religious objects, bodily ritual, and the Church.

An embodied understanding of personhood also can be argued to impact the over-all “quality of life” of those with dementia. Murna Downs, in her 2013 study about embodiment focuses on applying the concept of embodiment to enhance the quality of life of those with dementia. Quality of life can generally be described as the extent to which a person is healthy, comfortable, and able to participate in or enjoy life events (Jenkinson, 2023) and while Downs does not define Quality of Life in her own work, she seems to assume a shared understanding that “living well” is inherent in the definition.

Quality of life is used as a measure in many medical and social service settings, despite a non-precise and varying definition (Higginson and Carr, 2001). Downs links the concept of quality of life to the discussions of personhood and argues “an embodied approach to understanding selfhood provides a direct challenge to the dominant discourse, as described by Katz (2013) and Kontos and Martin (2013), that with impaired cognition there is a corresponding loss of selfhood” (2013, p.368). Downs offers an inspiring suggestion that – for example – when we see a person with dementia “wandering” we can interpret it as them expressing their need to explore - and this can be a source of celebration. We can understand their wandering body as important to who they are, and we can see their personhood in an embodied fashion. This example can be taken further, looking at prayer practices as an embodied way someone celebrates who they are, as a cherished child of God.

As this discussion has argued, selfhood in the literature about dementia has long been associated with our cognitive status, but this is increasingly being deconstructed (Katz, 2013). Descartes and Locke were famous philosophers who each asserted a form “dualism” and the dominant place of the “mind” over the “body” in who we are (Carman, 2012). This dualistic approach may partially be responsible for the focus on cognition in our society. Ranking of the mind over the body has a strong tradition in the philosophy and psychology movements of the 20th century, but, there have been increasing calls to unite the body and mind and give

well-deserved attention to our bodies in the narratives and discussions about personhood (Carman, 2012). This impacts how we understand those with dementia and even how we understand the role of faith in enhancing their lives – and this can be very important when we consider the role of the care giver.

How, as a society, we view “personhood” and “selfhood” influences how caregivers view those for whom they care. The concept of embodiment is, importantly, beginning to challenge the view of dementia as a “social death”. Social death is the dissolution of social relationships that occurs as the individual diagnosed with dementia progressively loses their faculties and begins to withdraw from social activities and relationships (Spicker, 2000). Many caregivers have internalized this view, some seeing their loved one as in essence “dead” - but this view ignores the role of the body and can be detrimental to those they care for (Sweeting and Gilhooly, 1997). If a caregiver or family member starts to over-focus on the notion of “death” due to changing relationships, the cared for person with dementia can increasingly be made to feel invisible, compounding their sadness.

Downs (2013) asserts it is important to “critically examine the myriad ways in which selfhood is manifest in the body” (p. 368), to avoid over focusing on loss and death. A 1997 study interviewed 100 caregiving relatives of those impacted by dementia (Sweeting and Gilhooly, 1997). In more than 30 percent of respondents, evidence existed of beliefs and behaviours indicating some level of social death occurred before the patient’s biological death (Sweeting and Gilhooly, 1997). For many caregivers and family members, the loss of memory, speech, cognition and personality can be as devastating as a physical death, if not more. While there is no denying that a person changes radically during the dementia process – and that the caregiver is radically impacted, a topic which needs attention itself - the equating of those changes to physical death is problematic, and an enhanced understanding of embodiment and personhood is needed to challenge this. The thoughts, feelings and ways of

being of those interviewed in my study will hopefully contribute to an enhanced understanding, challenging us all to “see” others as living, human persons, even when in the end stages of their dementia.

While not disputing the existing research and expressed feelings in earlier studies of the “double death” of dementia, (Blandin, 2016; Blandin and Peppin, 2017), reclaiming the body and this concept of opportunity needs further exploration. There is a link between sociological embodiment theories and the experience of my participants. My participants seem to hold an embodied view of life and faith due to their long-entrenched belief in the hope and suffering of the Embodied Jesus. They see His death on the Cross and even his suffering as an opportunity. Further research to explore the declining body as still being a source of future opportunity would help support the arguments in this research study.

An embodied view of personhood requires moving beyond traditional, rational approaches. Newman and Bluestein argue we need to be creative and use our imagination to step into another’s bodily space and inter-subjective space. (Newman-Bluestein, 2013). Naomi Feil has shown how mimicking the bodily movements of those with dementia can actually calm them. (Feil, 2015). Feil proposes that the many bodily movements of those with dementia are trying to express a feeling or idea that cannot be expressed verbally and by moving along with them, they feel understood, and are comforted (Feil, 2015). I have had the privilege of watching Naomi Feil enact her theories using the medium of drama, bringing her theories to life. These theories help us understand why holding an embodied understanding of the human person can enhance our work with those with dementia. As we participate in the bodily movement of others, we also experience enhanced empathy.

Empathy is key to fully embracing an embodied view of the world. Kinesthetic empathy can be defined as “the capacity to participate in somebody’s movement, or their sensory experience of movement” (Niezink and Train, 2020, p. 1; Fischman, 2015). The idea of

kinesthetic empathy highlights the role of physical prayer practices in the lives of those of the Christian faith, particularly those sections of the faith that use the body to pray regularly and pray with others. Michele Le Gribble-Dates (2022) discusses “a theology of embodied prayer”, indicating Bible stories such as Solomon spreading his hands towards Heaven, Miriam and David dancing in prayer, and noting how movement has brought him closer to God in his own life. He explored how those who work with individuals diagnosed with dementia may be able to further help them by making greater use of embodied prayer in supporting them if this was something that individual had done throughout their lifetime prior to the diagnosis. Naomi Feil would likely concur with Le Gribble-Dates and argue we can (when appropriate) pray along with the person we are working with, to help use the body as way of expressing self-hood.

The discussion of embodiment leads us to a fuller appreciation of how we define “personhood” and helps us critique the deficient theories of personhood which pervade our culture. The next section moves the conversation forward with a discussion of Christian Embodiment.

2.2.6 Christian Embodiment

The literature about embodiment in the Christian faith is diverse and vast – similar to the topic of dementia, it is hard to narrow down in terms of the literature review. Key concepts have emerged, however, that are important to this research. As in the secular literature, the debates within the Christian world also center on cognition, rationality and science vs other ways of seeing the world. In the Christian world, the concept of “personhood” and whether embodiment is critical to what it means to be a person of faith are equally relevant as the debates concerning dementia and memory loss. Indeed, throughout history, the relevance of embodiment within the faith has vacillated, depending on the dominating paradigms of the era. Kourie and Ruthenberg (2008) point out that although Christianity is an “embodied

religion”, there have been time periods and religious leaders who have been less focused on embodiment. According to Kourie and Ruthenberg, “while it might seem commonplace to defend a Christian spirituality’s embodied, incarnational reality it is clear that spirituality has not always been so understood, even constituting a pejorative connotation at times - as something essentially detached, disembodied, and inferentially dualistic” (Kourie and Ruthenberg, 2008, p. 303). This dualistic understanding discounts the role of Church, symbols, and rituals in the Christians sense of self.

Mark Wynn posits the “symbol theory of embodied religion”, offering a full discussion on why it is important to understand the links between our bodies, our symbols, and our faith. In discussing Wynn’s work, Barth remarks on the importance of sacrament and ritual in an individual’s sense of self. He contrasts this with what he calls the “scientific worldview which has the coercive tendency to see rituals and sacraments as deficient forms of engagement with the world...According to scientisms naturalist epistemology, rituals and sacraments originate in a pre-scientific stage of civilisation, superseded by modern empiricism” (Barth, 2013, p.94).

Barth reviewed Wynn’s work and discussed the fear that “religious values wind up as isolated phenomena in a scientific ontology” (Barth, 2013, p. 95). Both men note the problem with viewing rituals and symbols only through a scientific lens instead of through the lens of meaning, history and culture, and they discuss the dangers of an embodied view becoming lost or made to seem irrelevant. Their discussion confirms embodiment as a contested topic within theology just as it is in dementia.

Julian Hughes is a key writer in the field of Christian Embodiment. Hughes coined the phrase “Situated Embodied Agent” as a model of personhood and like others, he explores two views of personhood. The first he calls the “Locke-Parfit” view which regards persons only in relation to their psychological state and the brain connections that largely inform

psychological states, and second is the Situated Embodied view which regards the person as embedded in a history and culture (Hughes, 2001; Parfit, 1971; Locke, 1999).

Hughes critiques Locke's view that without consciousness there is no person and that a person is only an "intelligent, thinking being". He also critiques Parfit's view that personal identity is connected to "psychological continuity" and involves "psychological connectedness". Although Locke and Parfit wrote in different social contexts and different centuries, continuity exists in the thought between these two philosophers (Parfit, 1971; Locke, 1999). Hughes tracks the negative outcomes these views can have on those with conditions that make their minds decline.

Hughes contrasts the Locke/Parfit thinking with his notion of "situated embodiment" – that we are all entrenched in our histories, cultures, families, and bodies, and this is what makes us a "person". This idea coincides within the Christian worldview of the historical, embodied Christ.

One of the key issues in the work of Downs (2013) is the notion that having a sense of embodiment leads workers, family members and friends to better empathetically support those with dementia, and it can be argued that when we see a body as embedded in history, we can better recognize the uniqueness of that person's life and, for Christians, plan in God's Providence. According to Downs (p.369), "when we adopt an embodied perspective on selfhood, it means we recognize that each person we care for is an individual with unique perspectives, wishes and desires that are experienced and communicated through the body, even when verbal communication is impaired." Like Naomi Feil, Downs sees bodily movements as expressing feelings and thoughts that are difficult (or impossible) to express verbally. Those in various stages of dementia, who hold their faith closely, might express their understanding of their faith through their bodily movements, and this could easily be missed if one limits ones understanding of personhood to a cognitive understanding.

As in the current literature regarding dementia, the literature on Christian Embodiment points to the dualism that has dominated Western philosophy (and to some extent theology) for a few hundred years and indicates a need to reclaim the Christian understanding of embodiment. Kourie and Ruthenberg (2008) argue that within the Catholic faith, Vatican II re-established the role of the body within history, rituals and culture, which is similar to the views of Anna Corwin (2012). In “Changing God, Changing Bodies, The Impact of New Prayer Practices” (2012) Anna Corwin examines institutional change in the Catholic Church that she believes altered and enhanced the lives of religious sisters or nuns in the United States after Vatican II. She states that in her article she “combines a phenomenological model of embodiment with narrative analysis to show how institutional linguistic prayer practices transform elderly nuns’ embodied experience as they pray” (Corwin, 2012, p.1). Corwin explains that the changes implemented as part of Vatican II allowed for individual creativity in prayer and encouraged nuns to understand their bodies as a gift from God, and supported them in engaging in more creative and individual (or if chosen, communal) embodied prayer practices, leading to improved well-being.

Among various findings, Corwin (2012) shows how changing embodied prayer practices following Vatican II influenced nuns’ understanding and experiences of their own physical pain and illness – and that the new emphasis on embodiment has had an overall positive effect on their experience of pain and discomfort. Corwin notes that research has been conducted related to the effect of prayer on physical pain (Dedeli and Kaptan, 2013; Koenig, 1999; 2003), but not enough has been completed to show how communicative practices, such as prayer, can impact psychological well-being. In Corwin’s work, she attempts to make transparent how the nuns’ embodied practices of prayer positively impacted their psychological experience of pain and helped them in handling their feelings of pain. Corwin

notes that Christians pray to connect to the God, to strengthen community relationships, to better understand themselves, or to achieve a sense of cleansing in their body and soul.

Corwin's (2012) study has been an inspiration in my work because she has demonstrated, through the narratives she explores, how embodiment, illness, and faith are linked and their influence upon each other and upon our emotional and psychological well-being. Corwin's view of the impact of prayer has shown to be valuable in the discussions I had with participants and will be explored in my findings.

There are various researchers who have focused on the connection between faith, dementia, and embodiment in the late 20th and early 21st centuries. Csordas (1994) argues that individuals can experience religion and divinity through sensory experiences such as light, sound, taste, temperature, pressure, and smell. Luhrmann, Nusbaum, and Thisted (2010) look at how individuals learn to use and understand sensory experiences as communication with the divine. Peter Kevern (2015) has written about the connections between personhood, dementia, and faith and argues that "if spirituality is fundamental to personhood it must be as integral to the life of the person with dementia as to any other person," (p.765). Abramowitz (1992) posits that deep prayer habits are still relevant for people with dementia and suggests this may be due to the development of habit and emotional connections that people retain below the level of conscious awareness. Rituals, as part of our bodily movements, are embedded in what it means to be human. Those who are in caring, ministry, family, and friendship roles need to understand how those who are newly diagnosed understand the role of ritual (Engelhardt, 2012). It is encouraging to find researchers interested in exploring how we understand the person with dementia, and how our understanding of faith, rituals, and the role of the body helps us to truly help others.

Some define personhood through the relationship with God while others base in on retained stories and memories of the individual. David Keck (1996) has argued that the person with

dementia retains their personhood because their personhood is dependent on who they are with God and an individual's integrity and spiritual status are grounded because God always remembers every individual (Keck, 1996). Alternatively, Goldsmith (2011) argues that despite cognitive decline, personhood is retained through collective memories and the narratives of others. The individual holds their own stories and memories, but others also hold stories and memories for and of them. Although these writers do not use the phrase "embodiment" I note their understanding of personhood look very much like Hughes' (2001, p.86) "situated-embodied-agent" which discusses the collective memories of those around us as part of what it means to be "embodied in space." This notion of our bodies existing in time, history, and culture and in the stories of our lives is evident in all of their writing.

2.2.7 Initial Literature Review Conclusion

The above literature review and discussion of conceptual frameworks that have informed this study help to put the study into context of current research. Chapter 2 explores the theoretical literature and concepts that helped me to understand the context of my participants' lives and also to robustly analyse my participant interviews. While IPA is an inductive approach that encourages allowing data to emerge without being overly influenced by prior reading – it must be acknowledged that even within IPA we are not a "blank slate" and we come into our research with theoretical backdrops that seem particularly relevant to the lives of those interviewed in this study.

2.3 Section 2: Inductive Literature Review

IPA is an inductive approach where literature emerges as relevant throughout the study (Smith, Flowers, Larkin, 2021). Some IPA researchers believe a literature review should not even be attempted before the interviews and analysis are complete, as an IPA researcher should go in as blank slate. While I have avoided this approach, and allowed research to inform my work throughout, I have also been especially conscious of allowing theoretical

concepts to become important during the analysis process. The following begins a discussion of theoretical concepts that are discussed further in my analyses and recommendations. These concepts became important through the process of my interviews and analyses and are therefore explored far more fully in further chapters.

2.3.1 Kenosis

Kenosis, in the Christian literature refers to Christ's Incarnation and also His 'giving up' on the Cross (Hinshaw, 2023, p.18). It is also now used to explore the entire "giving up" involved in the life of a Christian, and the life of a human being. The dementia process is one that involves a 'giving up' of cognition, memory, and ability. In the process of my analysis, it became obvious that letting go of control was an important theme in the lives of all my participants. This emerged as an area for deep exploration in how 'giving up' needs to be embraced by the social work profession and those involved in faith-based work.

2.3.2 Empowerment

Empowerment theory in social work can be defined as the importance of "using intervention methods to guide people toward a sense of control" (VCU, 2023, para. 4) It is considered an entrenched and key social work value (Adams, 2003). It emerged as a theoretical concept to be explored and deconstructed. Key to this thesis will be my final argument that the social work field needs to reconsider its focus on empowerment.

2.3.3 Abandonment Theology

Abandonment theology is associated with Karl Rahner (Rahner, 1978). "Rahner sees abandonment as not only the meaning, but also the essence of a human being's nature," (Rosok, 2017, p.57). Abandonment theology emerged as important as I analysed my participant statements, seeing the themes involving releasing control and abandoning oneself to the natural process of dementia.

2.4 Conclusion

Chapter 2 has included a literature review, looking at spirituality and dementia, and an exploration of conceptual frameworks relevant to this thesis. Subjects such as embodiment and personhood have been explored in depth in relation to the Christian faith. At the end of the chapter, conceptual frameworks that emerged as my analysis took place were introduced with the intent of exploring them in depth in future chapters.

Reflective Box 2: Literature Review

The role of the literature review in IPA is contentious. Researchers debate if one should conduct a literature review, what type of literature review to use, and how it is used to guide the research. My literature review was more of a scoping review than a systematic review. I think it is important to discuss the complexity of the literature review within the IPA methodology.

IPA is a methodology that focuses on emerging themes and letting the individual's experience shine forth (Smith, Flowers, and Larkin, 2022). Some argue that a full literature review should be conducted before interviews, while others disagree. However, it is not considered inappropriate in all cases to conduct a literature review before interviews are conducted, and many researchers take a more nuanced view, exploring literature at the outset. According to Smith, Flowers and Larkin (2022), research and interview questions in IPA are not usually driven by theory, but if doing a literature review it should "help you identify a gap which your research question can then address, and it should also help you learn something about your participants. This kind of literature review might be quite short and may be more evaluative than most. Your aim is to introduce readers to the field. It can help you be explicit about what particular aspect you are interested in" (Smith, Flowers, and Larkin, 2022, p.37)

Brocki and Wearden (2006) in "A Critical Evaluation of the Use of Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) in Health Psychology" discuss the alternative types of literature reviews done in IPA research. They give examples of how different researchers have approached their literature reviews. They discuss Robson (2002) who used completely unstructured interviews and purposely made no detailed literature review of the research topic until after analysis was completed. They then mention Turner and Coyle who based their questionnaire on findings from similar fields of research and current literature. They clearly explain there is not "one" right way, and "there is no reason why

either approach is incompatible with IPA” (Brocki and Wearden, 2006, p.91). Whether one conducts a literature review before data analysis or not, the important thing in IPA is the acknowledgement of how this has impacted the researcher in their interpretation, and how the researcher has let the idiographic emerging nature of the themes shine through.

When I started my Professional Doctorate and made the decision to focus on faith and the experience of dementia, I started reading and came upon theories of embodiment. These theories resonated with me and offered me a whole new way of looking at the individual with dementia. I knew at that point that embodiment and theories of personhood would help guide my research and help me think about my participants. The decision was made to approach my literature as an exploration of personhood and embodiment, with attention given to some of the basic literature related to spirituality and illness. My literature review was intended to show how I would “view” my participants and shape my analysis. It was important, however, to maintain a very clear balance between using these theories to guide my analysis and not automatically “reading them into” the emerging themes. I took a balanced, nuanced approach in my analysis, using my overview and basic introduction to embodiment and personhood to guide me, while still letting the participant voice emerge and speak for itself.

I made a deliberate choice to do a literature review and then I needed to shape what that review would look like. Grant and Booth (2009) have written an article on various types of reviews, and this is helpful in explaining how I thought about my own literature review. They discuss an approach simply called an “overview”. They describe it as “typically narrative” (p.94), and say that “analysis may be chronological, conceptual, or thematic” (p.94). They also discuss the scoping review saying that such reviews might provide a “preliminary assessment” and “cannot usually be regarded as a final output in their own right, particularly because limitations in their rigour and limitations in their duration mean that they hold potential for bias”. In thinking about how I decided to approach my literature review, Grant and Booth’s discussion of overviews and scoping reviews resonate with my approach. I looked at the themes of personhood and embodiment, offering a narrative approach, without claiming an exhaustive review of the literature. I used my literature review to offer my reader a glimpse into the theories that embedded my thinking throughout the process. This feels consistent with IPA as a methodology – acknowledging that I came to my interviews with pre-explored theories, while not insisting those theories

drive my analysis. In turn, new literature (such as abandonment theory and kenosis) emerged during my analysis, which are explored in more detail in my findings and discussion. This made for a rich project consistent with IPA.

Chapter 3

Research Methodology and Methods

3.1 Introduction

This study uses a type of qualitative methodology called Interpretive Phenomenological Analysis to explore the lives and experiences of the study participants. This methodology permeates the entire research process and will be discussed extensively below.

Participants for this IPA study were chosen based on having a diagnosis of dementia and stating they follow and practice the Christian faith. Four participants were interviewed in person, 3 were interviewed by Zoom, and one gave written responses to questions. Four out of 8 participants were interviewed a second time, offering an opportunity to review their testimony and add to it, and a 5th (the one who gave written answers initially) wrote more to enhance his answers.

The following sections explore both methodology and methods. While I have attempted to discuss the philosophical basis of my chosen methodology first, there are places where it shows my work more coherently to combine discussions – therefore, there will be places in the methodology section that mention my methods as well, and vice versa. The theoretical concepts embedding IPA (phenomenology, hermeneutics, and idiography) are given a great deal of attention, as these backdrops drove my analysis and interpretations, and are considered key concepts to explore when working with IPA.

3.2 Research approach

A qualitative research method was chosen because it was the most effective way to explore the lived experiences of individuals and reach the “why” and “how” of faith impacting their experience and reaction to a dementia diagnosis. The goal was to delve deeper into their experiences rather than generalizability, therefore qualitative methodology was appropriate for this study. More specifically, Interpretive Phenomenological Analysis was chosen in order

to prioritize the importance of the individual experience. This fits squarely into my social work ethics and the particular social work value of holding “unconditional positive regard” for every individual (Rogers, 1957).

3.3 Methodology: Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis

3.3.1 Adoption of IPA

Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) is a qualitative research approach that explores how people make sense of their major life experiences, digging deeper into the individual experience than the collective (Smith, Flowers, and Larkin, 2002). Being diagnosed with dementia qualifies as a major life experience (Alzheimer’s Scotland, 2023). IPA argues that people are “reflective” creatures who will reflect on the meaning of life (Smith, Flowers, and Larkin, 2022). The goal of this research is to capture and explore the pre and post reflective insights and reflections of those interviewed, to hear the individual voice, and to help build a holistic understanding of their dementia journey and the impact of their faith on this journey.

Kierkegaard (2014) believed that people are always in the process of ‘becoming’. As we “become” we are impacted and changed by the expected and unexpected events and experiences around us. Some of these experiences – such as experiencing a severe illness – are beyond our control, and yet, we have no choice but to “live” the experience. The participants who took part in the study are all “living” their experience of dementia in current time.

IPA was adopted for this study because it posits an understanding of the world and human nature that resonates with me: humans reflect, interpret and make sense of their lives, and researchers will always bring something of their own underlying values and experience to the process (Jeong and Othman, 2016). As a qualified social worker, I have always felt drawn to the “systems theory” of human relationships – every part of the system impacts every other

part, and nothing exists in isolation (Hanson, 1995). “Systems Theory” also resonates with a Heideggerian view of phenomenology. It understands human behaviour as the “intersection of the influences” - multiple interrelated systems influencing each other (Schirmer and Michailakis, 2019). Heideggerian IPA acknowledges that the relationship between researcher and participant is one of the systems that influence both the interview and the ultimate interpretation of the interview (see 3.3.5). A “systems theory” approach has helped me remain conscious of the impact of my relationship with the participant, and how the relationship has a bearing on the interview and my analysis of the transcripts.

3.3.2 IPA and Phenomenology

To understand IPA, it is necessary to have some grounding in phenomenology as a philosophy. Phenomenology is considered one of the three theoretical underpinnings of IPA and gives IPA its philosophical foundations. Although there are elements of what might be seen as phenomenology as early as Kierkegaard (2014), modern phenomenology is attributed to the philosophy of Husserl in the early/mid-20th century (Brooks, 2015). “The founding principle of phenomenological inquiry is that experience should be examined in a way that it occurs, and in its own terms” (Smith and Shinebourne, 2012, p.12).

Joanna Brooks (2015), a psychologist, in *Learning from the Lifeworld* described Husserl as concerned with developing phenomenology as a rigorous alternative to methods traditionally used by the natural sciences because the existing methods were not appropriate for the examination of human experience. Rather than an objective reality, Husserl felt only one’s subjective experience was ‘knowable’. Husserl argued that we can really only know and understand concepts grounded in concrete experience (Husserl, 1983; 2001). Heidegger (1988), a pupil of Husserl, focused on understanding experiences within their context. Brooks (2015) described him as being “interested in exploring what it means to live in and among a world that is experienced by each individual in their own way,” (p.1). Heidegger saw our

relation to the world as being contextual-- always both interpretive and relational (Heidegger, 1988). The whole and individual elements must be understood within reference to one another—a concept known as the hermeneutic circle (Bontekoe, 1995).

Heidegger (1988), in his version of phenomenology, stressed the role of “letting something be seen” and described phenomena as “that which shows itself”. According to Van Manen (2014), Heidegger sought to expose “what is hidden” and what truly is the “meaning and ground” of the phenomenon (in this project the phenomenon being the impact of faith on the dementia journey). Arriving at “meaning and ground” requires far more than analytic thought – it can require feeling, imagination, and reflection – which will be seen in my use of the GEM analysis as well as Ricoeur's two-tiered interpretation approach with the data from my participants (see GEM and Ricoeur sections below). According to Van Manen, the very method we use to interpret impacts the meaning we find in statements. Van Manen argues: there is an acknowledgement that enquiries into the phenomenality of human experience and truths require the full measure and complexity of the language of prose and the poetic, the cognitive and the pathic... [we] need to explore the relation between meaning and method – where method does not merely mean procedural, technical, repeatable features of enquiry. Phenomenological method is always a matter of attempts, bids, and hopeful risks. Within a phenomenological context method is never *just* an engine that will unerringly produce insightful outcomes (p. 29).

Van Manen's understanding of meaning as it relates to the phenomenological process has driven this whole project. My “phenomenological” way of seeing the world encouraged me to be mindful of thought patterns, decisions, and initial steps, even before meeting my participants. I have had the “lived experience” of the IPA methodology, living “phenomenologically” even beyond the research project (see Reflective Box 2).

3.3.3 *Hermeneutics*

Hermeneutics is the second theoretical underpinning of IPA. Hermeneutics is concerned with the interpretation of the text and was originally used as a term to explain how Biblical texts were interpreted (Smith and Shinebourne, 2012). The word Hermeneutics is derived from the Greek verb, *hermeneuein*, to interpret, and the noun *hermeneia*, “interpretation” and its aim is to make “meaning intelligible” (Grondin 1994, p.4). In IPA research, hermeneutics focuses on how we interpret the answers given by our participants and asks “is it ever possible to uncover the intentions or original meanings of an author?” (Smith and Shinebourne, 2012, p.22). This question will be discussed more below in the section looking at critiques of IPA and also in the section on analysis. The hermeneutical circle is a “back and forth movement” in which we are reflecting on our understanding of the text, while we try to locate the intentions and original meanings of the author.

While hermeneutics is one of the philosophical underpinnings of IPA, it is intricately related to and informs analysis, which warrants attention in this section. I have chosen to use hermeneutical models presented by Ricoeur and Smith to analyse my interviews, but with the backdrop of Schleiermacher and Gadamer informing my work (Schleiermacher, 1978; Gadamer, 2013). Specifically, I will be using the “both/and approach” of Ricoeur to dig deep into the meaning of a participant’s statements, as well as Smith’s GEM model. These are addressed in greater detail below in the section on analysis while Schleiermacher and Gadamer will be briefly discussed here, in relation to hermeneutics.

Schleiermacher discussed the need to read a text the way we would approach dialogue in a conversation (Rutt, 2006). The thoughts expressed in text help us to see “moments of life breaking forth” (Rutt, 2006, p.2). Schleiermacher was concerned with two aspects of interpretation: grammatical and psychological (Schleiermacher, 1978). Grammatical analysis looks at the words used and general language. Psychological understanding involves exploring the mind of the author and is at the heart of phenomenological analysis (Rutt,

2006). Both are considered key to strong analysis, and part of the backdrop of a hermeneutical approach to IPA. (Stiver, 1996). In his analysis of the hermeneutic cycle related to the work of Schleiermacher, Dan Stiver (1996, p.89) states that “we cannot understand the meaning of the whole text apart from understanding the meaning of the individual sentences, and even words, in the text. On the other hand, we cannot properly understand the individual parts apart from some grasp of the whole” (1996: p. 89).

Schleiermacher developed the controversial notion of finding the “authorial intent” (Schleiermacher, 1978). The authorial intent argues that we, as researchers, can understand the author better than the author understands himself – we can find out what he is expressing, by how he expresses it, and interpret it for him. He believes this can be done through becoming one with the creative mind of the original author, something we attempt to do as phenomenological researchers. Gadamer (2013) did not agree with this, however, and instead of speaking of “authorial intent”, examined the hermeneutical process as if it is a game of interpretation, going back and forth in analysis. I would argue, however, that there is not necessarily a conflict between the two positions – it is possible that the “circle game”, the going back and forth, can eventually lead to Schleiermacher’s authorial intent.

Whatever the truth of these two views, I have attempted in my analysis to go back to the “circle game”, listening and re-listening to video interviews, reading transcripts, and considering participant statements against statements they have said elsewhere in the interview, trying to imagine and construct a “whole” of their meaning.

Phenomenological hermeneutics has been explored by Eatough and Smith (2017), explaining the core ideas of Schleiermacher, Dilthey, Gadamer, and Ricœur and outlining the nuances in their approaches, ultimately arguing that IPA can incorporate all of their approaches. While it is beyond the scope of this thesis to fully explore all 4 thinkers, it is important to acknowledge I have used a mixture of Schleiermacher (1998), Dilthey (1996), Gadamer

(1977) and Ricoeur (1981) in my interpretations as will be shown below. While all 4 of these thinkers have overlapping ideas, they also have individual emphases, but these emphases are not contradictory and often work together well. For example, Heidegger and Gadamer agree that to live a life is to interpret (Eatough and Smith, 2017) – so every action, nuance, word spoken is interpreting the world around you. This approach will be especially shown in my analysis of Brother James, and his use of language to shape his own thinking.

3.3.4 Idiography/Sample Size

Idiography is the 3rd theoretical underpinning of IPA. According to Smith and Shinebourne (2012), idiography has had a major influence on IPA and is focused on the “particular”.

Unlike many theoretical underpinnings that focus on groups, idiography looks at the depth of the individual experience. It requires the analysis to be “thorough and systematic” (Smith and Shinebourne, 2012).

In 1943, Alport noted the field of psychology was experiencing a decline in the use of the idiographic perspective, a reduced interest in the individual case, and a lack of attention to experience. Alport felt the field’s tendency to “categorize” was resulting in the loss of the individual. IPA started as a method in the psychological sciences, with one of the goals being to bring back the individual voice.

Eatough and Smith (2017) posit that one way to remain committed to the idiographic perspective is by using single-person case studies. Beyond single case studies, however, IPA researchers commonly use “small and situated case studies”. This allows not only a thorough, holistic and focused study of the individual in his/her life world – it also allows the researcher to find commonality around very individual experiences. This process of presenting the diversity of human experience while also finding common shared experiences can encourage creative thinking and lead to insight into both (Eatough and Smith, 2017).

Hefferon and Gil-Rodriguez (2011) of the The British Psychological Society have argued that students are too concerned with including large numbers in their sample at the risk of compromising thorough analysis, and I have been conscious of this critique. They argue that supervisors might influence students to have too many participants, and that students need to be able to justify their sample size based on the principles of IPA. According to Hefferman and Rodriguez “less is more with IPA. Fewer participants examined at a greater depth is always preferable to a broader, shallow, and simply descriptive analysis of many individuals, as commonly seen in thematic analysis, grounded theory, or poor IPA” (2011, p. 756).

Acknowledging these perspectives and following my idiographic emphasis, I have put a great deal of thought into my sample size. Obviously, sampling is a method (not part of the philosophical backdrop) but given how closely related it is to idiography, it warrants mentioning in this section. In recruiting my sample I have considered the quality of the interviews needed, the depth of analysis, and the complexities of recruiting participants. Smith, Jarman and Osborn (1999) argue for a sample size of roughly 3 to 6 participants at a Masters level and slightly more for a Doctorate. I have interviewed 8 individuals, which fits well within the usual recommendations for an IPA study.

3.3.5 Merleau-Ponty and IPA

Merleau-Ponty (1962) was a phenomenologist who had an “embodied” understanding of the person in relation to the world. Smith and Shinebourne explain the importance of Merleau-Ponty’s work, stating:

While we can observe and experience empathy for another, ultimately we can never share entirely the other's experience, because their experience belongs to their own embodied position in the world. The intentional quality and meaning of the “mineness” and “absoluteness” of an experience are always personal to the body-subject. The lived experience of being a body in the world can never be entirely captured or absorbed, but equally, must not be ignored or overlooked (2012, p.19).

Merleau-Ponty (1962) is concerned with the “embodied” nature of human existence. This clearly sits closely with my interest in the Christian theologies that take an embodied understanding of human existence and belief, and my curiosity about the impact of holding an embodied worldview (Corwin, 2012). The diagnosis of dementia is an “embodied” experience - our minds, physical body, human relationships, and ability to interact in the wider world is drastically and progressively impacted. Van Manen (2014, p.128) interpreted Merleau-Ponty in this way:

“We know the world bodily and through our embodied actions. And in some sense, this is a pre-knowing knowing: we know our world first of all through our embodied being rather than immediately in a disembodied intellectual manner.”

Merleau-Ponty offers some very interesting perspectives on thought, language, and body. According to Van Manen (2014, p.129) he “criticizes the naïve view that speaking means putting thought into words”. On the contrary, he argues that , thought and feeling are actually IN the word. Just as we cannot separate mind from body, we also cannot separate word, and thought and feeling. . “To speak is not to put a word under each thought” (Merleau-Ponty, 1964, p.43). This is an fascinating perspective that seems to imply that the very words chosen by an individual helps to create and express the meaning. During my hermeneutical analyses I have explored how I can analyse the very words used as part of the meaningful lived experience, and I have pondered how the words reflect meaning and possibly create meaning. Merleau-Ponty's idea of “wonder” is also one that I have held onto throughout this project. Merleau-Ponty is often translated as having said, “Wonder is the unwilling willingness to meet what is utterly strange in what is most familiar” (Van Manen, 2014, p.223). “When we are struck with wonder we seem to have evaporated momentarily our present preoccupation. The mind is cleared of garbage, so to speak. We are struck by the strangeness of this thing, this phenomenon,” (Van Manen, 2014, p.223). As discussed in my results below the sense of

“wonder” is evident in the lived experience of all of my participants. Certainly “the strangeness” of their diagnosis is felt, and for some, there is an acknowledgement of the “strangeness” of knowing they are going to partake in, through their dementia, what Christian’s might call “Christ’s cross and resurrection”.

Merleau- Ponty’s (1962) embodied view of human beings enhances and pushes Heidegger’s idea of “being in the world” (referred to as “DASEIN”) – we are not just a “being in the world”, we are a specific “body in the world”. Our “bodies in the world” are intricately linked to the ‘Rich tapestry of life’,” (Eatough and Smith, 2017, p.4). I have found that this concept of being a “body” remains very important through the statements of my participants, and their experience cannot be understood without attending to the fact that they are truly “bodies in the world”.

3.3.6 Bracketing

While bracketing might be considered more of a method than part of methodology, most IPA literature discusses it as both. Phenomenology explores what the experience of being human is “like” and tries to find the “core” quality of the experience (Smith and Shinebourne, 2012), asking us to put aside what might obscure the core quality. The Husserlian understanding of phenomenology involves “bracketing” which means to step aside, to not take the world for granted, to try and see the world “as it is”. As researchers, it is necessary that we attempt to bracket our own preconceived notions and prejudices about the world when we are exploring a participant’s “lived experience” and allow the experience to “show itself as it is”. Bracketing our own prejudices as the researcher (at least to an extent) is key to the process. None of these concepts are universally understood in the same way and Brooks stated, “the extent to which the bracketing of presuppositions is possible, and the appropriate balance between description and interpretation in phenomenologically informed work, continue to provoke considerable debate to this day” (Brooks, 2015, para.3).

Bracketing is an essential part of any phenomenological enquiry, though it is a contested notion in various branches of phenomenology (Smith, 2012). The Heideggerian branch of phenomenology acknowledges preconceived notions will always exist, and total bracketing is not possible. As phenomenological researchers we understand it is inevitable that preconceived notions will influence us, but we also work to move beyond our preconceptions through being transparent in our work. “Heidegger maintains that a person should always be seen as a ‘person in context’ and all activities being a relational engagement with the world” (Heidegger, 1988; Smith and Shinebourne, 2012). We, as researchers, are part of that context. Part of the phenomenological project is understanding the preconceived biases we bring into our research and staying conscious of them throughout the process. Acknowledgement of our biases makes for a more honest and ethical project. In approaching this project, I have attempted to remain conscious of all my biases. I have my own experience of working with people diagnosed with dementia and my own understanding of the Christian concepts of hope and suffering. While I do not believe anyone can completely bracket their preconceived ideas, I do believe by staying aware of them I have worked with them in a transparent way, and this has helped maintain an ethical approach to my project.

3.3.7 Limitations of IPA

IPA is a contested research methodology, making it important to justify its use and show why it is an effective choice for this study. According to Tuffour (2017), IPA has two primary aims – to look at and understand in detail how someone makes sense of life experience and to provide a detailed account and interpretation of the account so that the experience can be understood. This is accomplished by using subjective judgement and making it visible how one’s preconceptions shape the knowledge produced. During the research, this is done through personal reflexivity and self-evaluation.

There have been many debates about the appropriate way to “do” phenomenology – with two broad categories of phenomenology research identified - descriptive and hermeneutic (Rapport, 2005). I have used a hermeneutic approach throughout the research process, constantly using the “hermeneutic circle” as I have negotiated the complex processes of designing my project and carrying it out . Tuffour (2017) outlines the most common critiques of IPA, including hermeneutic IPA, focusing on the most prominent difficulties. These critiques look at the conceptual and practical limitations of IPA. I have considered all of these limitations and addressed the considerations.

According to Tuffour, the major difficulties cited by those who critique IPA involve: arguing that IPA, like many phenomenological studies, gives unsatisfactory recognition to the integral role of language; arguing that IPA does not capture the experiences, meanings and expressions of participants, but instead captures the researcher’s own opinion of it; questioning whether participants have the necessary communication skills to truly say what they mean; questioning if IPA is suitable only for the most eloquent individuals, and thus discriminatory; arguing that the “why” is left out in the over-all analysis when a researcher describes “what is”.

All of these critiques are helpful in encouraging the researcher to fully scrutinize their own methods and can ensure a more robust project. The critique surrounding language asserts that IPA researchers do not make sufficient use of the role of language – but Tuffour (2017) contests this critique by pointing out that most IPA researchers consider history, discourse, metaphors and the use of language quite closely. Certainly, if we are looking for meaning in the accounts, the participants’ use of language will be part of seeking meaning. An example of this in my own research would be the use of repetition. At least one participant repeated multiple times that he became anxious when his wife would say “you worry me” and that she has learned not to use that expression with him. The very phrase “you worry me” causing

anxiety can be analysed hermeneutically, focusing on the word “worry” and the resulting word of “anxiety” while looking at the role of repetition in stating it. IPA is a creative method which allows for the use of language in analysis.

The next critique – whether participants and researchers actually have the requisite communication skills to express experience – has a bearing on my research. I conducted interviews with people whose cognitive and vocal skills have been and continue to be altered. One might ask about a person with dementia (and any person) “are they expressing what they mean to express?” This also leads to arguments that IPA leads to elitism – only interviewing those able to express themselves in a clear and coherent way.

This is a very important critique to consider. Tuffour (2017) decided to counter this critique by pointing out the elitism of the critics themselves – are they suggesting some people not be allowed to express themselves simply because they might not express the “exact” experience? If so, it could result in nobody ever trying to express meaning at all, which is clearly not how we live. We all use language with a basic assumption that at least “sometimes” we are expressing what we intend. Additionally, part of our job as IPA researchers is to use the hermeneutic method to help find the meaning that might not be obvious – thus we believe language can help lead us to meaning even if it is not clear at the outset.

I have considered the issue of elitism within my own project, focusing on those who are competent to give consent, a willingness to participate, and an ability to express themselves. There are many people in the later stages of dementia who are left out of studies where interviews are employed. I can envision, however, using other approaches beyond “talking” to allow people with dementia to express their ways of being, their wishes, and their needs in a research study. I think particularly of the research of Naomi Feil (1992) who argued that bodily movement and repetition in those with advanced dementia express needs in a way we

can interpret. This resonates with the work of Merleau-Ponty and would be an interesting future research study.

A further critique – that IPA seeks to understand the experience without exploring the “why” of the experience – is combated easily by Tuffour (2017) by showing that most IPA projects use hermeneutics, ideography, context, history and culture to explore the phenomenon, which contributes to an understanding of the “why” even if this is not the primary purpose of the research. The criticism that the “why” is left out seems to discount the various historical movements within phenomenology and IPA and posits a very Husserl-ian understanding of the research at the expense of the other varied and rich approaches offered. My own use of Heidegger and Merleau-Ponty, while not focusing exclusively on the “why” of “the impact of faith on dementia” - at times explores theories that can help us begin to understand the “why”.

All of the criticisms related to the IPA approach can be addressed, at least in part, by being clear about interpretation approaches, particularly hermeneutics. Conducting IPA research forces one to be very clear about the process invoked and to combat any claims of vagueness in the methodology. The hermeneutic circle will always involve a consideration of the wider contexts of a participant's life. According to Eatough and Smith (2017, p.3) “IPA aims to grasp the texture and qualities of an experience as it is lived by experiencing subjects.” It is acknowledged that texture and quality are affected by and have an on effect the wider context of a participant's life – thus Heidegger's phrase “being in the world” resonates with IPA's understanding of people and the worlds they inhabit as socially and historically contingent and contextually bounded.

In the methods section below, when exploring “analysis” I will now look more closely at the double hermeneutic, the concept of “GEMs”, the use of Ricoeur's work, and how these have guided me in my own process of interpretation.

3.4 Methods

The rest of this chapter looks more closely at the methods I used for data collection, coding and analysis. As stated above, in IPA Methodology and Methods are closely related and sometimes discussions need to entail both. This is appropriate in a study which seeks to integrate IPA philosophy throughout.

3.4.1 Study participants: Selection procedure and demographics

Finding a sample came with various complexities. The criteria set out when beginning were stringent – a participant needed to be diagnosed with dementia within the past 3 months, competent to give consent, and a strong belief and understanding of the basic Christian doctrines of the cross and resurrection. A sample of no more than 4 to 8 participants was chosen due to preference for small samples in IPA research and my interest in understanding the lived experience of individuals. The specificity of the criteria and unusualness of the topic likely contributed to recruiting challenges which can be common with IPA (Smith and Shinebourne 2012).

During the recruitment process, I was advised by multiple sources that the 3-month criteria were too strict and excluded participants who might be more willing and able to participate and also offer valuable contributions. Sarah Thorpe (2020), Dementia Coordinator for the Anglican Diocese for Lichfield, said “some people might be far more able and willing to speak six months after diagnosis – the first three months might not be the best time, as they are still adjusting.” I was given this feedback from a number of people who work with those with dementia. This criterion was eliminated based on the feedback given. The change was submitted to the ethics committee and it was approved.

The participants were found through various sources: conversation with the Salvation Army Officers (ministers) and requesting appropriate referrals; consulting with local Catholic Churches; advertising through Faith in Older People, an advocacy group for older people who

hold a strong faith; and joining the Scottish Dementia Research Consortium, which holds a data base of those who have been diagnosed with dementia and signed up to participate in appropriate research studies. The Research Consortium had its own ethics procedure and training that I attended before being allowed to engage with potential participants.

The 8 study participants ranged in age from 74 to 96, with 5 being male and 3 being female. All participants were Caucasian. Each had their dementia diagnosis for over a year. The participants I recruited were from various denominations - 4 Roman Catholics, 1 Salvation Army, 1 Church of Scotland, 1 United Church of Christ and 1 Methodist. All were practicing Christians from childhood and maintained a strong faith into their older age. None came from what might be called a charismatic background, or evangelical background. As expected, given the range of denominations, their particular expressions of faith differed, with the Catholics expressing more about bodily forms of worship, and those in Protestant denominations more focus on Bible stories. While there are significant differences between various denominations, and very interesting ramifications to those differences - a full discussion is beyond the scope of this thesis.

3.4.2 Data collection tools and process

The study used semi-structured interviews to collect data. Semi-structured interviews, are described as "... a conversation with a purpose" (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009, p.57). Cohen, Manion, and Morrison (2018, p.535) state that "the in-depth interview is conducted to explore issues, personal biographies, what is meaningful to, and valued by participants, what they know, and what they have experienced." This is congruent with the values of IPA research and with the goal to understand the lived experience of those diagnosed with dementia. The same questions used in interviews were used for the participant who decided to write his answers.

Each interview began with an interview schedule including 9 questions (see Appendix 2). The questions covered topics such as the participants' feelings about being diagnosed with dementia, the participants' understanding of hope and suffering, and the role of their faith communities in helping them on the dementia journey. While the appropriate number of questions asked and the development of quality questions in IPA research is debatable (Hefferon and Gil-Rodriguez, 2011), I aimed to ask enough questions to encourage in-depth discussion, but to also not so many that participants would feel overwhelmed.

Although I made use of an interview schedule, I was also prepared to be flexible in the use of questions. Interviews are fluid, and agendas must remain loose to allow for the addition of topics or to follow where one answer might lead (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009). All questions were open-ended giving the participant room to tell their story and share their perceptions. Smith, et al stresses the importance of questions that do not make too many assumptions about the participants' experiences or concerns. Assumptions regarding my participants were certainly a danger with this type of project. I was aware of the possibility of going into the interviews assuming both the level of distress after diagnosis, and the impact of the theologies of hope, suffering, and embodiment. I remained aware throughout of my own views and preconceived notions and tried to "bracket" these (to an extent) and avoid leading questions (see reflective box below for more on my preconceived notions).

I spent time devising the research questions and also had the interview questions reviewed by the Dementia Consortium, for appropriateness, with the goal of ensuring user participation in the research. Interestingly, the feedback received was contradictory – one reviewer felt the questions were too simple and said not to underestimate the ability of those with dementia to understand longer questions. Another participant said to simplify the phrasing of the questions and to remember that when interviewing those diagnosed with dementia, simplicity is better. Time was spent phrasing the questions in a way that attempted to both respect the

intelligence of those being interviewed but also respect the needs of those who would feel more empowered with short, clear questions (see Appendix 2).

According to Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2018, p.518), the interview is a “social encounter – a speech act” and the interviewer must be at pains to conduct the interview “carefully, sensitively, and with delicacy”. Although there have been many parts of the research project that have intimidated me, I have felt generally confident about conducting interviews. As a qualified social worker of more than 25 years, I have a great deal of experience interviewing vulnerable individuals. Most of my career has been with older adults, many of whom have been diagnosed with dementia. Empathetic, sensitive communication is key to conducting both ethical and effective interviews, and I have remained aware that I must be reflexive throughout the process. Significantly, while most of my participants were communicative, they often veered off the questions, leading us down paths that contributed to the interviews in unexpected ways. I sometimes varied the phrasing of my questions based on participant understanding and expression of interest in particular topics.

Guiding my understanding of IPA methods is the IPA Email Forum (2019), run from Glasgow Caledonian University. Advice from the IPA forum has been crucial in building my understanding of the complexity of methods and ethics within research and has supplemented my academic reading. Advice read within the forum included following specific guidelines/frameworks for analysis; detail each stage in the analytic process (if possible, provide an audit trail for the reader); owning one’s perspective; checking understanding with the participant; consider one’s own potential influence and balance of power on participants (reflexivity); and ensure coherence across research question, philosophical perspective and analysis approach. This advice has been invaluable as a quick reminder as to the many areas I have needed to consider, throughout the research process.

3.4.3 Research process

The past few years have been challenging regarding research but have also opened new avenues and opportunities. Because of COVID and the population being interviewed, it was unclear if interviews with older adults with vulnerabilities would be feasible. The choice was made to expand the options for interviews to include Zoom or “in person”. Including Zoom interviews ended up being an opportunity for various reasons: it allowed interviews with people from various parts of the world; it allowed visual recording, so that interviews could be watched or listened to again; Zoom offered a transcription service – therefore I could both transcribe the interviews myself, and also have the Zoom transcriptions, and be able to compare and contrast.

Four of the interviews took place on Zoom; three of the interviews were done in person; and one interview was done by writing. This was requested by the research participant who said that he “has plenty I want to say” and can “express myself so much better in writing”. In line with being flexible to empower people with dementia, I accepted this form of interview and indeed received very detailed written responses to questions. This is a qualitative survey type model and accepted within IPA (Deakin University, 2023).

Once data was collected, it was necessary to transcribe the interviews and analyse the data. Per the methodology chosen, an iterative and inductive cycle was used when analysing the transcripts. Themes were not identified before the data analysis, but rather emerged through the data analysis process. Themes were not identified through a linear process, but rather through a reflective, circular process of reading, listening, reflective writing, and re-reviewing.

3.4.4 Data arrangement and analysis: Transcription

I went through multiple stages of transcribing. Because IPA is an approach that asks the researcher to “dive deep”, I knew it was important that I transcribed on my own, and not use software to transcribe for me. After transcribing my first Zoom interview, I discovered that

the Zoom function did an automatic transcription as well. It was very helpful to look through my own transcribing and compare it to the Zoom version. What I noted quickly was that I was able to isolate certain words that were stressed, or spoken quietly, which the Zoom transcribing did not do. Comparing my own transcript to the Zoom transcript became part of the process for me as it allowed me to consider “why” I noted certain words, nuances of voice, and facial expressions – it allowed me to refine my thinking. I re-watched the recordings multiple times, after my initial transcription. I was able to stop and pause, and replay certain sections, letting the tones of voice, the words chosen, and even the sentence structure and repetitions “sink in”. This allowed me to uncover the GEMs (see section 3.4.6 for explanation of use of GEMS), as well as use the two-tiered Ricoeur approach of empathy and suspicion.

My approach for those interviews that did not take place on Zoom was different. One participant asked me to turn off my recording device – he wanted to be interviewed and wanted me to write down his words “verbatim” he said. He said that electronic devices distracted him, but my writing while he spoke would not distract him. I therefore left the interview with pages of notes and I tried during the interview to make sure I was noting the especially meaningful things that he said. After the interview, I went back over his responses and asked him to confirm I had written his responses correctly. When I was done with the interview, within the hour, I typed up his responses, and therefore had the original handwritten version and the typed version. On my second interview with this gentleman, we went through the same process.

3.4.5 Analytical Procedures

I created a document with six columns for each transcript. The transcript was copied into the first column of the table, on the left-hand side of the page (see Appendix 7). Column two was used to incorporate my notes, reflections and ruminations straight after the interview, as well

as themes as they started to emerge for me. In the third column, I noted strong individual emergent themes – those themes that were explicit (such as “I have never been angry at God”, and those themes that were implicit – “I laughed and laughed, and that was Church”.) Strong Themes emerged as I read transcript notes, replayed Zoom interviews, and compared sections of a participant's interview to other sections of the same interview.

A number of individual themes were chosen for discussion in Chapter 4. I was then able to go back through all of my third columns, on each participant grid, to start comparing for cross-participant themes. Column 4 notes those themes that emerged strongly in at least 6 of 8 participants. These cross-participant themes are discussed extensively in Chapter 4. Column 5 was used to explore GEMs. In this column, I not only state the GEM but offer a small explanation as to why it occurs as a GEM for me. GEMs are explored in the discussion section of Chapter 4. Finally, column 6 looks at themes that are explored under Ricoeur’s “empathy/suspicion” framework with a discussion section as well in Chapter 4.

There is not one prescriptive method of analysis for IPA. Smith and Shinebourne (2012, p.79) give a comprehensive account of the types of activities included in analysis:

Typically, analysis has been described as an iterative and inductive cycle which proceeds by drawing upon the following strategies: the close, line-by-line analysis of the experiential claims, concerns, and understandings of each participant; the identification of the emergent patterns; the development of the dialogue between the researchers, coded data, and their psychological data, about what it might mean for participants to have these concerns, in this context leading to the development of a more interpretative account.

Cohen, Manion, and Morrison (2018) would agree with Smith and Shinebourne (2012), noting that the researcher must read, reflect, re-read and interpret – multiple times. Before data can be analysed, however, it must be put into a format. Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2018) note that transcription can provide important detail and be important for in-depth analysis. I explored various transcription techniques before starting this project.

Ricoeur's work is very helpful in understanding the concept of the double hermeneutic. According to Smith (2004), using the IPA methodology requires navigating between different layers of interpretation while simultaneously engaging deeply with the way the participants expressed their personal experience. Ricoeur posits a hermeneutics of empathy and a hermeneutics of suspicion, showing one way to envision the double hermeneutic (Ricoeur, 1970). I have used this model of the double hermeneutic in my interpretations and part of section 4 looks at particular examples of how I have used empathy/suspicion in analysing certain participant statements.

Kearney (1994, p.101) describes Ricoeur's view of interpretation as "the work of thought which exists in deciphering the hidden meaning in the apparent meaning, in unfolding the levels of meaning implied in the literal meaning,". Ricoeur is described as using a double approach—a combination of being empathetic to the participant's experience while also being critical and probing for meaning in ways the participant may not be able or willing to do. As Kearney (1994, p.94) says "it is not sufficient simply to describe meaning as it *appears*; we are also obliged to interpret it as it *conceals itself*." For Ricoeur, we remain "sympathetic" to how it appears, and also "suspicious" that there are other layers not appearing on the surface. This suspicion is not one that ever discounts the visible – but actually builds on it. In trying to visualize this, I thought of a patient going to the emergency room with a sore wrist, and finding out her wrist is broken. The sore wrist is not any less true than the broken bone – the discovery of the broken bone simply enhances the patient's understanding of "what is".

Chapter 4 includes a section on Ricoeur and the double hermeneutic, showing how I have used Ricoeur's work to my interpretation of some of my participant's statements. At various times, contradictory statements emerged or statements that when read in line with the rest of the interview, invoked a sense of "suspicion".

3.4.6 Cross Participant Themes, Individual Themes, and GEMs

Analysis began by identifying individual themes as the transcripts were reviewed, videos watched, body language was considered. Cross participant themes are those which emerged as individual themes in 6 or more participants. Reflections were noted post-interview and used as part of the analysis process. I considered the strength with which certain points were emphasized, how often a participant repeated certain ideas, tone, and the body language that accompanied certain statements.

GEMs are a relatively new concept in IPA research proposed by Jonathan Smith (2011). It is a valuable interpretive tool for IPA. The purpose of a GEM is to illuminate and enrich the researcher's interpretations and understanding. Ashworth (2008, p.4-5) described a GEM in this way, "Typically the GEM is a singular remark which jumps out at the researcher or a small extract from an entire interview that the researcher is drawn to and has a hunch might be key to understanding a person's grasp of their world." The concept of the GEM emerged for me as an exploratory way to consider the words of my participants. Jonathan Smith (2011, p.6) states that:

Reflecting on my own experience of doing IPA, I am aware of the pivotal role played by single utterances and small passages to the analysis of a research corpus. In many studies, I have found a single extract to have a significance completely disproportionate to its size. And this is what I mean by a GEM. It may be that the passage takes focal concern on first reading and engages considerable analytic effort at that stage. Or it may be that a passage intrigues or mystifies but pulls me back a number of times during the analysis process. Either way these short utterances and passages prove extremely fertile to the research, offer strong insight to the experience for this individual and often for the group of participants as a whole.

Smith (2011) proposes 3 types of GEMs: shining, suggestive, and secret. A GEM that shines literally shines with meaning; the meaning is clear. He gives the example of a woman who discusses her son's circumcision and says "everyone was watching my son cut to pieces". Her

feelings about this “shine through” in that statement. This was the case with a few of my participants - certain phrases or expressions that simply “shone”. Suggestive GEMs imply some feeling behind it but are not as clear and require more digging to identify. Secret GEMs are even less obvious as the participant may be unaware of the feeling behind their words/statement. I note that not every individual theme and GEM that emerged is addressed later in the study. Due to space limitation and the need to focus on cross participant themes, the decision was made to choose those individual themes and GEMs that occur as most relevant for discussion.

Throughout the whole process, I remained conscious of Ricoeur’s empathy/suspicion model, as well as diving deep for GEMs (Smith, 2011). Having models to use was incredibly helpful in staying focused, but I had to remain conscious of not “forcing” GEMs – I remained aware of letting them come naturally, through rumination on words, sentences, statements, and body language. I worked with my data throughout the whole project, and when writing up my findings, I remained reflective throughout the process.

Following this chapter, Chapters 4 and 5 will entail more detailed discussion on all cross-participant themes and selected individual themes and GEMs, developing a more robust theoretical backdrop, and Chapter 6 will follow with recommendations for practice.

As is consistent with IPA, themes were developed during the analysis process rather than before data collection began. For this reason, all discussion of specific themes is reserved until chapter 4 where findings will be discussed.

3.5 Philosophical assumptions

This study is underpinned by an interpretivist research philosophy. Both realism and social constructionism are evident in an IPA framework. IPA posits the belief that there is a real experience “to capture” and that we help to construct the meaning by interpreting it.

3.6 Transferability and reliability

Due to the qualitative nature of this study, it is not generalizable to the wider population. We must assume that participants were giving a true and accurate representation of their faith, feelings, challenges, and experiences. The intent of the study was to explore the lived experience of real, individual human beings, valuing them as individuals, regardless of generalizability. It must be noted, however, that we can still learn from the participants, using what we learn to inform how we approach other individuals – thus our learning is transferable, while not generalizable.

3.7 Ethical considerations

3.7.1 Ethics approval and permissions

Ethical approval was obtained from the University Ethics Committee. Because of the nature of my study, a great deal was asked in terms of ensuring the protection of the participants. Time was spent reading about ethical behaviour while conducting research with those with dementia and reflecting on the ways conducting this research was similar to, yet different from, social work assessments I have done in the past. I devised an assessment to use and a protocol to follow if during the course of the interviews I discerned a participant was becoming upset or unwell. I researched organizations I could refer participants to if necessary and I devised two information sheets, one comprehensive and one simplified. I worked with my supervisors and the University Ethics Committee to ensure I was engaging in an empowering and ethical research project. I completed the Dementia Consortium Training on Research Ethics in order to ensure I understood their standards, before recruiting participants through the Consortium.

3.7.2 Informed Consent

Informed Consent for those with dementia is a contested issue. The National Health Service of Scotland (2012) defines capacity as, “the ability to use and understand information to make a decision,” (p. 7) and capacity is the basis for informed consent. The Alzheimer’s

Society encourages all researchers to always start with the assumption that a person is competent (Alzheimer's Society, 2023). This is in-line with the law and the goal of empowering those with dementia. I have considered the *Adults with Incapacity (Scotland) Act* (2000) throughout my research to guide me in terms of principles of empowerment and a rights-based approach.

For my study, capacity to consent was demonstrated if potential participants were able to understand the participant information sheet, retain the information for long enough to make their decision and then communicate their wish to take part in the study. When recruiting through the Dementia Research Consortium initial contact and discussions about capacity were had with family members. This was in line with the wishes of those diagnosed with dementia who had requested that researchers contact their family first.

Because half of my interviews were done by Zoom, the consent process was somewhat altered. Each participant was given my information sheet and consent form by email. I sent the enhanced and the simplified information sheet (see Appendix 1). Participants and their family members were given time to look through the material, type their names in the signature spot, and send them back to me. At the start of each Zoom interview participants were reminded of the reason for my study, and informed that they could withdraw at any time. We reviewed their rights as participants and my role in helping keep them safe. At various intervals within the interview, for both those on Zoom and those "in person" I checked in with how they were feeling.

3.7.3 Participant Well-being

From the outset of this project, I have been aware of the potential harm that could come to my participants. There is a great deal of literature, however, on the benefits that can come from allowing and encouraging those with dementia to speak for themselves and to help society shape the services and approaches of the future (Boyle, 2014). I thought a great deal

about “positive risk taking” and the importance of “service user participation” in all that we, as social workers, do professionally, including research (Mapes, 2017; Stevenson & Taylor, 2017).

All of my participants were told at the start of the interview that some of my questions were sensitive and personal. I devised a participant safety assessment tool and protocol which I used as a guide to help me continually assess well-being. This tool, titled Adult Support and Protection Protocol, was approved by the ethics committee (see Appendix 3). There was one particular situation where I used my protocol specifically – a participant started to cry when telling me about losing her son at a very young age. I used my therapeutic communication skills in the moment – asking if she needed to stop the interview, validating her feelings, and giving her time to relax. She stated clearly that she wanted to continue with the interview and said that she often became emotional when speaking of her son. I followed my protocol by explaining to the nurses in the care home, with the participant’s permission, that she had been upset, and they confirmed that she often became emotional when speaking of her son, and that she preferred to speak about him, even while becoming emotional. I contacted the care home in the days after the interview to confirm that she was well.

3.7.4 Confidentiality and Anonymity

All participants were informed that their personal information would be kept confidential throughout the research process, with only myself and my research team having access to data. Names have been changed throughout this thesis to further protect their personal information. Those who chose to participate through the Dementia Research Consortium were aware that the Consortium itself would have access to certain information for their database. All participants were told that the only exception to confidentiality would be if I assessed there was a danger to their well-being, in line with the Adult Support and Protection Act, or a danger to another vulnerable individual or child. The participants all expressed

verbally to me that they understood about confidentiality and those who chose to have a family member with them in the interview expressed that they were comfortable speaking and sharing what they were saying with their family members.

3.8 Limitations

The limitations regarding the methodology mainly involve self-selection bias and lack of diversity among participants. I do not believe the use of Zoom or accepting written responses negatively impacted this study, however it is possible someone may have selected not to participate based on the need to use technology. COVID may have influenced people's willingness to participate in person, but this challenge was mitigated through the use of video conferencing software or electronic mail. It cannot be known what may have influenced potential participants to decide to be a part of the study or not, though it is worth noting that two of my participants had signed up with the Dementia Research Consortium to try and actively become involved with a research study.

The majority of those with a dementia diagnosis are over the age of 75 and Caucasian, despite Blacks and Hispanics being at higher risk (Alzheimer's Impact Movement, 2020), which may explain the demographics of participants in this study. Women are diagnosed with higher rates of Alzheimer's than men, but this is because women tend to live longer and age is the largest determining factor (Alzheimer's Society, 2023) therefore the distribution of gender among participants is not heavily unbalanced.

3.9 Conclusion

IPA is a methodology particularly suited to capturing, understanding, respecting, and even cherishing the individual participant voice. This chapter, while lengthy, has been designed to show the complexities of the methodology as well as its strengths and weaknesses.

Additionally, because I have used a phenomenological approach throughout the whole process of this study, including writing it up, it has been important to address the

phenomenological underpinnings of IPA. Phenomenology has been my guiding lens and driven all aspects of this study.

Reflective Box 3: The IPA Method/Reflective and Reflexive Thought

The attraction of IPA for me has been very much related to its reflective stance. I am a reflector by nature and social work training. The IPA literature encourages the researcher to be “in” the IPA process through every stage of the research. IPA does not “start” when writing the research proposal, but rather at the foundation of thinking about the project. There has been much for me to reflect on, to bracket, to consider and reconsider from the very beginning of the programme.

My own journey to the doctorate programme has been at the forefront of my mind, as I began a doctorate (PhD) years ago and for various reasons had to withdraw. The very nature of the professional doctorate has suited my talents and personality more than the traditional PhD. Having a community of practice and engaging in classroom learning has motivated me.

I have had to be aware that I have at times wanted to rush through parts of the process. The nature of the research process has slowed me down. I became frustrated at my inability to quickly get ethical approval, because I have worked with those impacted by dementia for more than 25 years and I teach undergraduate students about care, safety, and protection of vulnerable adults – and yet I felt the ethics committee was asking me repeatedly to show I am “safe”. I stopped to reflect and realized the ethics committee members do not know me, and their job is ensure ethically sound research – and that my own value base actually encourages such rigorous examination. I have come to appreciate the rigour of the ethics committee.

I have remained aware and reflected on my family’s history with dementia and my career in this field. I came into this research with pre-conceived notions – some that I had to discover as I went along. Having a background in this field emerged as a mixed blessing, both helping to inform my work, but also demanding that I be constantly aware of my pre-conceived notions.

Chapter 4

Findings

4.1 Introduction

Chapter 4 focuses on cross participant themes, individual themes, and GEMs (see Table 1).

While IPA is a methodology that focuses on the individual participant and their experience, it is possible to draw parallels between the interviews of the participants and locate themes that show a consistency and coherency between their experiences – these were coded as cross participant themes. All cross-participant themes speak to the question of how holding faith impacts one who has dementia. Significantly, Chapter 4 offers long excerpts of participant statements, in respect for the idiographic foundations of IPA. Chapter 5 will offer more detailed analysis of cross participant themes.

Individual themes, GEMs, and analysis through the lens of Ricoeur are also presented in this chapter. This is in line with IPA being an idiographic method, that prioritizes the individual voice. The GEM is a relatively new way to analyse interviews in the IPA process and has been found to be helpful in shining light on each individual, truly respecting the individual voice and experience. Analysis using Ricoeur’s framework of empathy and suspicion has been helpful in challenging my own process and the codes that have emerged for me.

Ricoeur’s framework allows one to look at individuals from an alternative angle, acknowledging that with a methodology such as IPA, different researchers might have different themes emerge.

In my explanation of cross participant themes, I have noted where in the appendix each participant statement can be found. This is important, since the individual voice in IPA is prioritized, and it is necessary for the reader to be able to locate that individual voice, within the context of the larger and complete interview, if they choose to. In my discussion of

individual themes, GEMs and Ricoeur’s analysis, I do not give the line number for every participant quote, to avoid repetition, and make reading easier.

Table 1

Themes and GEMs

Cross-Participant Themes (5)
See Me/I am Not Lost
God’s Innocence/Radical Acceptance
Releasing Control/Radical Dependence
The Multiple Sides of Humour/Embracing the Laughing Christ
Counter Cultural Stories – the faith stories that help me
Individual Themes (2)
Embracing Change (and the Christian concept of Hope)
Help Me Worship
GEMs (3)
Daffodils
Lady of Guadalupe Rosary Group
“Quite happy sitting on the bottom shelf”

4.2 Cross-Participant Themes

4.2.1 See Me/I am Not Lost

Either explicitly or implicitly most of my participants expressed a desire to “be seen”. This was expressed in the context of their faith, seeing their faith as a source of support when others seek them out and interact with them in-person. Participants expressed the importance of others coming to them – and that in the context of their faith, it is important for friends, family, and church representatives to actively and explicitly “come to them”, sharing their faith with each other, in a bodily way. There is a sense that they feel more of a person when

someone chooses to approach and interact with them – making them feel visible and important, with their physical body acknowledged. Merleau-Ponty’s theories of embodiment speak to this. The way people sometimes respond to or speak about someone with a dementia diagnosis can make that person feel invisible (Alzheimer’s Scotland, 2021). The constant refrain of being “lost” in dementia can be counteracted by those with dementia “being seen”, and from a faith perspective, by helping people know they are seen by God also. Being seen by God is one of the ways my participants expressed the impact of their faith while they go through the dementia journey, and they felt more seen by God, when other people – God’s representatives – came to them and acknowledged their personhood.

All the participants were asked what the Church communities could do to help them in their dementia journey. When discussing what the Church could do to support him better, Richard said: “There’s nothing the Church can do to better support me better. That’s my constant, the Church, they are wonderful...an officer, he and his wife are always very communicative...we see each other each week at church or if I am working around the Church, they talk to me, they make an effort to talk to me, *they come to me* (emphasis added)” (Appendix 6b: L41). Adela expressed the importance of “seeing others” in her example of how she treated the children she taught in the past. “I was a head teacher in a Catholic school. I believed in helping all the children. Whatever their ability- if they were good students or struggles. I worked with them all. I’d go into the classroom and work with them, sit right down at the desk with them. *I sat right down – with them* (emphasis added). Nobody is beyond help. Nobody” (Appendix 6c: L5-9). Adela said twice that she sat “right down – with them”. It evoked the imagery of her getting down to the level of her pupils. The very physicality of it shone through. Very interestingly, it was paired with “nobody is beyond help”. Although she was speaking about her relationships with her students, it is not a far stretch to speculate that she felt the same about her own dementia journey and the need for others to come to her.

Adela also talked about the importance of the physical presence of the priests and Sisters and the opportunity to interact with them. “It gives me a great deal of consolation to have a priest here. And the Sisters. It is helpful to have priests *near to us, talk to us...to come to us. I’m sitting here and they come to me.... I get closer to God as I get older.* I’m sorry for those who don’t believe...they don’t know what they are missing” (emphasis added) (Appendix 6c: L39-42). Adela is conscious of the fact that she is in a care home and needs others to come to her, and she seems to associate others coming to her with a sense of “growing closer to God”. God – and others – both come to her, and this cannot be separated in her world.

Elizabeth also used the phrase “come to us”. “Our nuns and priests do a great deal for us with dementia – they give us daffodils. *They come to us and give us daffodils, they come and hand us the daffodils* (emphasis added)”. For Elizabeth, part of the comfort she gains from being in a Catholic Care Home is the very bodily presence of priests and nuns. Elizabeth’s faith is a source of comfort when those who represent the faith come close to her (Appendix 6c: L32).

Mark expressed himself in a very evocative fashion using colours. Mark said, in response to his feelings about the dementia journey “It is a series of black and white events. When I cannot come up with words or express myself or think things through...that is a time of “black”. “*White*” is the time men and women come and share with us in love (emphasis added). It is a time of family in love and support”. Mark’s times of “white” are when people approach him, see him, and share with him (Appendix 6a: L22-23).

Mark went on to talk about the importance of people acknowledging his personhood and including him. “For people with dementia, you sometimes cannot process information. I have trouble hearing and interpreting conversations at times. I sometimes do not recognize people, even loved ones I’ve known for many years. And so, when you have dementia, like I do, sometimes people do not ‘recognize’ you and leave you out. I’m talking about recognition as a person who wants to belong but cannot always get the words or thoughts out to share.

Many, though, show respect, talk slowly and directly to me (emphasis added)” (Appendix 6a: L87-88). Mark’s use of the phrase “recognition as a person” is important – for a population that often feels invisible, this type of recognition, as a person embodied, right in front of another, is key.

Andrew, like others, used the phrase “they come to me”. In discussing the confusion about having two names he said, referring to his faith community, “I’m really Otto but I’m called Andrew. Anyone who knows me knows I’m Andrew (amongst other things...!) They come to me and say ‘hi Andrew’ and I know they know me. They come up to me and say ‘hi Andrew’” (Appendix 6g: L102-103). Andrew’s repetition of “they come to me” and then “they come up to me” shows the importance of bodies recognizing each other, in real time and space. The constant refrain of “come to me” by my participants is very thought provoking, given the sense many with dementia have of being invisible (Bray, 2018).

Interestingly, the refrain of others coming to them was often made in the context of how faith communities support them, and the importance of those in their faith community including them. Faith and community, as expressed by bodily closeness, have great impact on how they feel during their experience of having dementia.

4.2.2 God’s Innocence/Radical Acceptance

Going into this project, I was very conscious of the anger that people feel when diagnosed with an extreme illness. Kubler-Ross (1969) posited the 5 stages of grief (denial, anger, bargaining, depression and acceptance) many years ago, but how these stages emerge for Christians in the dementia process has not been largely explored. Through my interviews, it became clear that one theme that emerged for 7 of my participants was “radical acceptance” and – for the majority – holding no anger toward God. This was not expected - more anger and questioning were anticipated. There is a long and cherished tradition within the Christian world of arguing, debating, demanding with God – as those did in the Psalms – and yet, I did

not get this response from my participants. Belief in God was not seen as a source of stress or disappointment when considering one's diagnosis, but on the contrary - one's belief in an innocent God seemed to be a source of great conviction and of great comfort.

Seven participants made strong statements about holding their faith, and their confidence in God, almost "separately" from their dementia. This sense of God's Innocence was expressed in many ways, but the clearest expression was Charlotte who said emphatically (and with humour), "I don't blame God for suffering, why should I? I might as well blame *you* [emphasis added]" (Appendix 6h: L 21-22).

The nature of suffering – and what in the Christian tradition is called "The Problem of Evil" or theodicy - has a 2000-year plus history of discussion. The nature of suffering is often cited as the number one reason people do not hold faith and/or leave their faith (Law, 2010). Yet – the participants I interviewed held a staunch understanding of God as a loving presence in their lives who held no responsibility for the plight they are in – I call this "God's Innocence" and argue that we can better make use of this concept in supporting those with dementia both in the field of social work and in faith-based work.

When asked about his feelings regarding his diagnosis Richard said "It's not affected my faith at all. That's still strong. I've realized and accepted that if you have a faith it doesn't exonerate you from all the ills of life - that come with old age - at all. You just live with that. It's a totally separate thing from my faith, it doesn't impede my practice of faith" (Appendix 6b: L 29). Richard was very clear in this statement that it hadn't impacted his faith "at all". While this will be further explored below through the Ricoeur lens of Empathy/Suspicion, at face value, it is important to note Richard said this with conviction – faith does not exonerate you from the ills of life. Adela was very clear she feels no anger at God. "I never feel angry at God - I only just ask God to help me...It doesn't matter - my diagnosis" (Appendix 6c: L26). These were compelling words from Adela, given her

discussion of her son's early death and her obvious grief surrounding that. Adela was very clear that her closeness to God was and always has been a source of support throughout her life, including in the loss of her child, and her experience with dementia.

Peter spoke about being "already healed by God" despite his diagnosis. "And I realized that I could apply that [my spirit of learning] on how I would deal with this diagnosis and basically God didn't give it [the dementia] to me. I mean I'm a physical human ... with frailties and imperfections. So, God really didn't have anything to do with this in terms of that - it's how I choose to deal with this and I came to the conclusion that I am healed. I am healed from the disease of having Alzheimer's. I am healed. I have it, but I am healed" (Appendix 6f:

L289). "God really didn't have anything to do with it" is a powerful statement from a man who has likely lived in a Church tradition that teaches God's omnipotence. This concept of God being without blame came across as key to being able to understand God and faith as entirely a source of support rather than a source of stress. Claiming to be "already healed", when one is diagnosed with dementia and declining, shows the power of believing in a God who makes all well.

Charlotte expressed herself succinctly when asked how she felt about her relationship with God when she received her diagnosis. "I don't blame God for suffering, why should I? I might as well blame *you* [emphasis added]" (Appendix 6h: L24-25). Elizabeth said quite clearly, as well, that she felt no anger. "Well, I'm not mad... Why should I be mad? I've never been mad at God" (Appendix 6d: L6-7). Clearly, for both Charlotte and Elizabeth, like the others, belief in and comfort found in God has not been diminished by their dementia diagnosis – God remains innocent in their eyes.

Brother James, Andrew and Richard were all clear that suffering, including their diagnosis, is simply a part of life. Brother James, in his own unique way, stated, "The answer is no. No, I'd be angry with myself rather than God. It's vast or meaningless. I don't know - it is for me

what it is” (Appendix 6e: L11-12). Andrew, like Richard, was very clear that suffering is simply a part of life. “I just accept that as a possibility” (Appendix 6g: L46). There was a real sense of calm and acceptance in the way these men made these statements – a sense that faith cannot be shaken by a diagnosis of dementia, and almost a sense of surprise that there is even such a possibility. This speaks to the firmness of faith and the importance of faith, in their lives in general and through their dementia journey.

Mark, in his writing, expressed that he felt anger at God when he initially received the diagnosis. He said it felt like “I had lost my freedom... a long hanging on the Cross” (Appendix 6a: L27-28). He goes on, however, to show how he embraces his faith as a comfort through his dementia journey. He stated: “I try to focus on love and sacrifice as demonstrated by Jesus, both his life and on the Cross. I try to keep my faith simple...faith and love in action, not just words” (Appendix 6a: L30). Clearly, despite his initial anger, the comparison of the dementia journey to Jesus on the Cross, as an act of love, is helpful to him.

Brother James’s analysis of hope – as stated elsewhere – is interesting. He did not think one should think about whether hope exists or not because then that poses it as a question, with the possibility that it “doesn’t exist”. Brother James is so adamant that it does exist – it simply “is” – he does not even need the question to be asked. As Brother James stated “Hope – I don’t like the word. The word is too structured. For me, in reality - it means there could be *not* (emphasis added) hope...if you even use the word.... hope suggests it might *not* (emphasis added) be the case” (Appendix 6e: L23-23). Brother James clearly has a probing mind, and this emphasis that hope exists without room for debate has substantial potential for exploration. If one is so certain that all that is entailed in the Christian concept of hope just ‘is’, there is an implicit optimism about life - even in the midst of a dementia diagnosis. This

can be important for a social worker or faith-based worker in their interactions with Brother James.

The theme of God's Innocence/Radical Acceptance will be discussed in further chapters, linking conceptual frameworks and theory into how we can use God's Innocence in our work with those diagnosed with dementia.

4.2.3 Releasing Control/Radical Dependence

One of the themes that emerged clearly was the impact of others on how the person with dementia feels and experiences the world. The others could be family members, friends, pastors, the Church, and God Himself. Another name for this theme might be "throwing yourself into the arms and faith and God." Holding faith, and having a faith community, emerged as a clear comfort, but the way in which others come to one in faith is key to determining the level of comfort offered.

As a person with dementia experiences further decline in their mental status, they also experience an increase in dependency on others. There are ways to understand this theologically that can inform how we in faith-based positions interact with others.

Significantly, the role of God as entity on whom one depends came out prominently in some conversations. For my participants, dependence on others and dependence on God interweave and both are ways of finding comfort and support.

Adela spoke about her dependence on God, throughout her life. "Belief in God helps me – I say 'Infinite mercy help me'. I say that all the time. I repeat it. 'Infinite mercy - help me.' I say that and I say it" (Appendix 6c: L4). Repeating that she "says it and she says it" shows that reaching out for God is constant refrain in her life. Adela abandons herself to God by constantly and explicitly putting herself in His presence, and her dependence on Him is complete.

Adela goes on to explain other prayers and pleas she makes when speaking to God by saying, “God, I love you, Jesus take me into your kingdom, never abandon me. You’re the source of my hope in life” (Appendix 6c: CL31-32). Adela is clear that God is ever present, and that her dependence on Him is what gives her hope. This sense of never being abandoned emerged strongly in my interview with Adela. Even in the process of dementia, she is clear that God’s presence is taken for granted, she is dependent on Him, and this helps her throughout her day.

Adela continues, at a later point in the interview, “I go to Mass every day – It helps me spiritually...I feel close to God...they take me down to Mass. It gives me a great deal of consolation to have a priest here. And the Sisters. I get closer to God as I get older” (Appendix 6c: L33-34). It is clear that Adela has a dependence on God but also the priests and Sisters to “help her spiritually”. Significantly, she seems to associate her growing closer to God with the consolation she receives from having the priests and Sisters close to her – she immediately linked the statement about growing closer to God to the preceding statement of how important it is to have the priests and the Sisters close to her.

Dependence on and need for the spiritual resources offered was clear throughout my interviews. Spiritual support needs to be brought to people with dementia, as it provides a source of comfort and coping. Elizabeth was very clear that her well-being would be enhanced by more prayer, more specifically a group around her to pray with. “I’ll tell you what I want – a prayer group. I wish we had a prayer group. A lady of Guadalupe group. This is what would be good for me. This is what I think about when I think about dementia” (Appendix 6d: L6-8). Elizabeth has linked in her mind her diagnosis with the need for a prayer group. She is clear that the ability to pray, and to pray in community, is what would be “good for her”.

Elizabeth addresses the intersection between suffering and dependence. She said, “Oh yes, I don’t think we can really avoid it. People should take it. We see a lot of suffering here. But the girls are wonderful. Some of the residents can be not very pleasant. There’s a lot of suffering. But the girls who help are so good.” It is clear, in the context of her care home it is the “girls” (the carers) and their approach to others that makes a difference in how Elizabeth understands and experiences suffering. Suffering does not exist in isolation and those around us can relieve it. We are dependent.

Charlotte stated that God is ever present, and always with us. “Of course, He’s [God] always with me and you, too, whether we like it or not” (Appendix 6h: L30). Charlotte is unwavering in her confidence that God is with her and total in her dependence on His presence. This was expressed with conviction. Her statement conveys a belief that God is here and He will remain here. Her dependence on Him is firm and unshakable.

Brother James engaged me in a discussion about heaven and hope. He said, “Heaven is now – people who are kind and generous” (Appendix 6b: L28-29). It is the treatment by other people that determines the well-being of Brother James - they have the ability to create Heaven on earth for him. The concept of Heaven resonates with Brother James, but he defines it by the treatment of others. Mark communicated in his writing that he is dependent on family and friends for him to be “ok”. “Our girls and loved ones around us offer so much for our lives... ‘White’ [seeing his life in colours] is the time men and women come and share with us in love.” Mark’s well-being is dependent on those who come to him in love. Mark goes on to discuss his dependence on people who help him from his church. He stated, “These guys who help me every week...they help me...love me...share with me...a true ministry.” He says, “I am bonding with more people that have expressed their love for us. I love the way Mel Bringle’s hymn expresses the experience of dementia. The hymn’s words ‘When memory fades and recognition falters...’ shares what is happening to me” (Appendix

6c: L43-44). Others need to actively reach out as the person with dementia is experiencing increased deficits. Others coming to Mark is “true ministry” - ministry is a source of support and strength when it is expressed through others coming to him – he is dependent on them for spiritual support.

Peter discussed the reactions of others on hearing about his diagnosis as key to his well-being. Peter also spoke of his dependence on God and his new relationship with the pet that entered into his life. “So that's a God thing. I really thought that God put that in my path” (Appendix 6f: L267). He goes on to speak again about the role of his family and God being in the midst of all he is going through – he can depend on God’s presence. Peter stated, “And so, and then you know weekends Saturdays with family and so that kind of a routine is very helpful. And I think God is just in the midst of all of that really is it's that presence and faith is for me the realization that no matter what happens God is present, no matter what.” It can be speculated that this deep-seated belief that he can depend on God’s’ presence, no matter what, is a source of comfort and security to him.

Richard spoke about how his wife’s reaction to his decline impacted him greatly. Richard said “[to his wife] you really quickly dispensed with a phrase you started to use ‘you worry me’” (Appendix 6b: L43). Richard mentioned this multiple times in the interview – the importance of his wife no longer saying “you worry me”. He came back to that at least 3 times. He stated, “a real helpful positive lesson is not to say ‘you worry me’ - the spouse has to accept it and embrace it as well. Where there is a repetitive response - it’s so negative and unhelpful. As if there’s something wrong with you that you have been the cause of.” For Richard the language used by those around him impact his well-being. While his focus was on the words of his wife, it is easy to speculate that this can be applied to those in his spiritual community as well – words matter, and that those diagnosed with dementia are greatly impacted and dependent on those around them using helpful terminology.

4.2.4 *The Multiple Sides of Humour – Embracing the Laughing Christ*

One of the things that struck me soon after beginning my interviews was the high use of humour of all of my participants. Some used humour when answering my questions, thus helping to set a relaxed tone. Some spoke of the use of humour in their day to day lives. Interestingly, a few had the insight to show how humour is used as a way to enhance well-being, cover gaps in memory, and ease conversation when they do not know how to answer questions.

<p>Brother James – “I have an excellent sense of humour. Or else I couldn’t live.”</p>
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Humour emerged as a theme throughout the interviews. In a sense, it was the unexpected backdrop to my interviews. While the subject of humour might not seem to speak to the issue of dementia and faith, I do think there is a connection. One of the research questions explored in this project was how faith communities can better support those with dementia, making their impact a positive one. The responses of my participants make a clear call for the use of humour in all aspects of their lives, and very much in their faith communities. As Elizabeth said “we need funny, not soppy” (when referring to her nuns and nurses). It can be speculated that the holding of faith makes it possible for my participants to hold a high level of humour and that the solid base of faith makes it possible to delve into the less predictable and more risky world of absurdity. This dependence on faith and humour combined can be a resilience factor. As stated by writer Marie Killilea “courage is a fusion of faith and humor” (Killilea, p.99, 1963). All of my participants showed a fusion of faith and humour throughout their interviews.

Charlotte showed a sense of humour throughout her interview, expressing herself clearly, staunchly, and with a twinkle in her eye. When discussing whether God was responsible for her dementia she said, “I don’t blame God for suffering, why should I? I might as well blame

you [emphasis added]" (Appendix 6h: L 24-25). She said this emphatically and with humour – and we both burst out laughing.

Charlotte's sense of humour reached its peak in the interview when she said to me, "You have to see the laughing side of things.... you don't know this - but I'm really 20 years old"

(Appendix 6h: L27-28). At this, she burst out laughing – Charlotte was 96 when I interviewed her, the oldest participant in my study. This sense of paradox – being my oldest participant, well into her 90s, and saying she was really 20, can be deconstructed in multiple ways, including ruminating on whether there is a part of Charlotte that still wishes she was 20.

Peter's discussion of humour was interesting, as he immediately noted the two sides of humour – how it can be used in a defensive manner or as a coping mechanism as well as its use for fun and joy. Peter stated, in terms of use of humour, "And one was my self-esteem - my low self-esteem - and I know I used humour to mask my feelings, you know, ha ha - make everything funny. You know. And then you don't have to deal with it. With your issues and so on. We shouldn't mask them. I've worked on that and at the same time, I've always felt that humour is very important, I mean I always - I think that - at a funeral you need to have that moment of laughter as well" (Appendix 6f: L453-454). Peter sees how humour can be used well in important life events, but also used to mask important or uncomfortable feelings. His mention of the use of humour at funerals has interesting implications for faith communities. Andrew laughed throughout his interview, often making jokes. He managed to express angst even in a joking style. When I asked about his feelings after being diagnosed with dementia he said "ughhhhh that's the answer!" followed by laughter (Appendix 6g: L25). This is an interesting use of humour – describing something negative in comical fashion, and laughing, possibly to take the sting out of the negative.

Andrew showed similar humour when trying to discuss the dementia friendly singing groups he went to. He stated "The fact that you can go along to the church and maybe some

afternoon during the week, have a coffee, there's a 'come and sing'" (Appendix 6g: L85-86). At this point he looked at his wife Carol, trying to clarify what it is called, and she said, "it's the dementia friendly services". Andrew then responded, "well I'm just demented!" (Appendix 6g: L88). He said this and laughed. Then he said to me "I have a peculiar sense of humour."

When we were discussing his two names Andrew said "I'm usually called Andrew -*she* only has 1 name [laughs, points to wife] and I have 2. I can't tell you why...but there you go [emphasis added]." He then laughed some more – this laughter felt like a response to him not remembering the reason for him having two names. When I asked Andrew about his former job he said, "Now I won't give you the cheeky answer [laughs]. I taught mathematics and what else. . . astronomy." I spent a lot of time thinking about Andrew's use of self-deprecating humour. One explanation could be lack of self-esteem, but alternatively it could simply be his way of being joyful. His joyous smile, and relaxed manner makes me think the latter. Another example of this use of humour is when he joked about all the instruments he used to play and acknowledged how he "played by ear." He said "Play by ear – well you should see my ears!" (Appendix 6g: L81).

Richard clearly enjoyed using humour to express himself, and interestingly, told two jokes that involved his relationship with his wife. Richard stated, "Yeah and I think probably you don't realise you got the encroaching issue of dementia – it comes without you realising it. It's only when you start to be repetitive in asking what you've already asked for. I know there's this old thing about husband not listening to wife [laughs] ...there's been a gradual awareness...it's no surprise...it doesn't give me any concern" (Appendix 6b: L20-23).

Richard used his humour as a way to make light and diffuse uncomfortableness surrounding his diagnosis and areas of decline.

Richard also joked about what could come in the future. He said, “I’m not at the point of waking up and saying ‘who are you’ to my wife – mind you that might be quite exciting” (Appendix 6b: L130-132). He then joked about beautiful women and how if he forgot his wife, he could “discover her anew” each morning. This was a very poignant joke, as it certainly could be the case that this happens in the future. There is a sense that Richard might be warding off the sadness of this possibility by making use of humour.

Mark wrote that humour plays a very strong role in his life and in the dementia process. Mark stated,

There is a role. We all have and need to have some humour. Probably every time I have attended a funeral, it has a little or a lot of humour. My sister Pat’s [funeral] was full of humour...exactly what she would want. She was a trickster and everyone she played a joke on spoke at her service. They were told that they could openly tell about their experience. So many people got up and told tales. We were all laughing at the memories. It was a recognition of what Pat was like. The picture she had on her office wall was of a Laughing Christ.

Humour has always been a part of my life. My family tends to be story tellers and laughing around the supper table or, in old times, around the wood stove was just a part of life each day (Appendix 6a: L106-122).

Re-reading Mark’s work multiple times resulted in me focusing on his statement about the Laughing Christ. Images of Christ abound in the western world, but the laughing Christ is not often seen. Willis Wheatly, the creator of one of the popular images of a laughing Christ, also called the image “Christ-the Liberator”. It is interesting to speculate if Mark’s attraction to the Laughing Christ is related to the feeling of liberation, through his dementia. As he said, “specific to dementia – humour helps us see the bright side of life.”

Brother James provided his analysis of humour, that it can be used in various ways and for various reasons. “A sense of humour is one way of disregarding questions, not answering questions...I have an excellent sense of humour or else I couldn’t live” (Appendix 6e: 31-32).

He felt that humour was key to well-being in his life, and indeed it makes living possible for him.

Adela and Elizabeth both expressed the importance of humour in brief statements during the interview and laughed at various times. Adela expressed humour when talking about her favourite saint, and the fact that he is often confused with Judas, the traitor. “Saint Jude is my favourite saint...the forgotten saint because of his name...they mix up the Judes! I love the Jude mix up [laughs extensively]. But he’s my saint” (Appendix 6c: L35-36). Elizabeth spoke about the need for humour in her life. She said to me “Our nurses have a good understanding, they are not all soppy, we don’t need soppy, we need comedy. We don’t need long faces” (Appendix 6c: L29-30). Both of these ladies hold a very strong Catholic faith, and while speaking of the importance of their faith, incorporated humour into the discussions. Their faith has been shown to be a source of great support to them, but an important part of this faith is the use of humour to express it – humour seems deep-seated in their very way of being, and in their strongly held faith.

4.2.5 Counter Cultural Stories – the Faith Stories that help me

Part of the Christian faith is a strong attachment to the Bible and the stories that are told (Copley, Freathy, and Walshe, 2004). How these stories are understood – as literal stories, analogies, or moral lessons – will differ between congregations and individuals (Dell and Joyce, 2013). Most of my participants spoke of the importance of “stories” in helping to make sense of their dementia journey, and one participant’s whole interview can be seen as a telling of his life-story. Peter said “let me tell you a story” when he wanted to stress the importance of a matter and he framed his life in narratives. His dementia journey seems inseparable from the stories of his life. Significantly, many of the stories either referenced explicitly or implied by my participants can be seen as counter-cultural stories either from the Bible or as taught by their faith, showing the Christian faith stories as a source of support,

comfort and encouragement through their dementia journey. This section will present excerpts from my interviews that show how participants “tell stories”, use Bible stories, or speak in a fashion that shows how framing their life by a certain story helps impact their well-being. Many of the stories they spoke about are stories that reflect how they understand their faith, and how their faith, as expressed in these stories, offers them comfort and support through their older age and dementia.

Peter’s entire interview had the theme of stories embedded throughout. He used the statement “I’m going to tell you a story” (Appendix 6f: L145) and mentioned the word “story” at various points throughout the interview. He started his explanation of how he came about his diagnosis with the following: “I’m going to tell the story. Back in 2018 the summer of 2018 I was out in the back-yard and I was just doing what I thought was going to be a normal project. Just something very simple and I couldn't do it, it just - it frustrated me - my blood pressure, went up - my stress level went up everything and I just yelled out “I think I’m losing it and you know - I think I’m losing it.” Peter’s explanation of the events of that day have become a story for him to tell.

Richard spoke about suffering by noting the story of Christ’s suffering. He stated, “We should demonstrate you’re not excluded from the ills of life. They are there for you to experience. It’s one of the principles of Christ’s life. Every individual Christian will approach it differently, but the faith is still there” (Appendix 6b: L89-92). Richard was adamant that a Christian should expect suffering – and that the Bible story of Christ’s suffering is key in helping one to accept that suffering. Richards adamance about accepting the ills of life shows that holding the Christian theology of suffering, and linking one’s own suffering to Christ on the Cross can be an important source of support for those diagnosed with dementia.

Mark noted the Bible stories that have influenced him. According to Mark, “The three stories that have influenced me are the Good Samaritan, the Prodigal Son and God in the Garden

with Adam and Eve. The Good Samaritan tells me that we have compassion on all people whether they are like us or not. The Prodigal Son speaks to our welcoming home even those who have gone astray as a Father welcomes his children with unconditional love. In the Garden, God asks Adam and Eve...and all of us ...plants and air and water and animals and people alike. All of the stories of Jesus speak to my faith. Faith without action is not true faith. What good is it? Jesus's willingness to be crucified. It's a deeper message there...the message that love entails service AND sacrifice" (Appendix 6a: L55-60). Mark clearly feels that the Bible story of Jesus on the Cross shows that sacrifice is part of love, and this speaks to how we live our lives – even through a diagnosis of dementia. It is possible to see dementia as the type of sacrifice one has to make in this life as part of the sacrifice entailed in the Christian journey.

Mark spoke of the Bible stories of suffering and the cross. He also connected this to his need to be "in ministry" and decided that while he is not a minister – he is still "in ministry". "I try to focus on love and sacrifice as demonstrated by Jesus, both his life and on the cross. I try to keep my faith simple...Faith and Love in Action, not just words. Both of my siblings went into the ministry. I sometimes wondered why I did not. But then I was reminded that *I AM IN MINISTRY* (Mark put this in large letters in his written text)" (Appendix 6a: L32-33). It is clear that the stories of suffering on the cross resonate with Mark, showing him that he can use his own suffering, through dementia, as part of his own ministry.

Elizabeth didn't use the word story or mention the Bible in particular but brought stories into her interview in implicit ways. She mentioned the importance of a Lady of Guadalupe group a number of times, repeatedly stating "I wish we had a prayer group. A Lady of Guadalupe group" (Appendix 6d: L8). Our Lady of Guadalupe is the beautiful story of a Marian Apparition in Mexico. Significantly, (and I discuss this more as a GEM), the Lady of Guadalupe is identified with a mother's comfort and love and tenderness. Clearly, Our Lady

of Guadalupe is a story that resonates with Elizabeth, and possibly with her need for love and nurturing.

Adela, while also not speaking of the Bible, loves the story and myths surrounding Saint Jude (Appendix 6c: L34). Saint Jude is the Patron Saint of Lost Causes. In mentioning Saint Jude and the meaning this saint has in her life, Adela was seeming to say that her life - even with her diagnosis – is not a lost cause. Saint Jude, who solves difficult problems, and overturns supposed lost causes, offers her comfort.

4.3 Individual Themes

The following is an exploration of individual themes that emerged from the interviews. I have chosen to focus on the 3 particular individual themes that were not coded as cross-participant themes, but that offer opportunity for reflection and seem to strongly reflect how these particular individuals of faith are experiencing their dementia journey. The ideography of IPA aims to ensure that the individual voice is never lost. These individual themes help us re-explore the research questions, looking at how the holding of faith impacts one who has been diagnosed with dementia.

There are multiple individual themes that emerged through my interviews. Due to the limitations of space in this study, they are not all discussed in depth. Additionally, while cross-participant themes are discussed more fully in Chapter 5, due to space limitation, individual themes are discussed more briefly here. It is my hope that my reflections on the chosen individual themes are helpful in showing how an idiographic, person-centred focus in IPA research can help the participant voice emerge and inform social work and faith-based practice.

4.3.1 Embracing Change (and the Christian concept of Hope) (Peter, Appendix 6f)

One of my research questions asks how the Christian theology of Hope impacts someone on the dementia journey. A theme that emerged strongly for Peter will be called “Embracing

Change”. It is Peter’s inherent hope, in Christ, that has always made embracing change possible, in an uplifting and positive manner, and this link between hope and change helps inform our understanding of the Christian theology of hope and how it impacts someone when they receive a diagnosis of dementia.

Peter’s whole life seems to be reflected in how he has embraced change. Being a storyteller, Peter told me stories from many stages in his life. He spoke explicitly about how he embraced the various changes, disappointments, and surprises that life presented to him. His language is inclusive, and this way of being is reflected in how he has handled his dementia diagnosis and understands his faith along this journey. Interestingly, many of his statements include the word “behold” or the phrase “lo and behold” which seems to be how he expresses the results of his “embracing” attitude. He would tell me how it turned out for him, often well, and with a sense of God’s Providence behind it. Peter’s comments about change show him to be a Christian of “hope”, an attitude he maintains has helped him throughout his experience of dementia.

In reference to changing his Church tradition and embracing a new church Peter stated, “My wife had no desire whatsoever to convert to Catholicism and I felt that it was very important to go to church with my family and I decided to do that - and so I got very active in the United Methodist church. That's what she was a member of. And we started attending. I was a Sunday School teacher for children.” Peter was clear that he was willing to embrace an important change for family unity, even when his wife was not - and he became “very active” - he embraced it fully.

In reference to changing careers when he realized there must be “something more” Peter stated,

“Right - so - and when I was about 40 I began struggling, I was in sales and marketing that's where my degree was in and I even lived in Irvington New Jersey, for a couple of years - I

was selling computer software that for hospitals that ran on IBM equipment, so I was doing a lot of team selling with IBM. So, I did that, but I felt that there was something more to life than that and to make a long story short, I felt the essence of a call to ministry and went back and began attending seminary as a student pastor in the United Methodist church... So that's what I did - went through all the process to become ordained elder.”

What stands out here is Peter's use again of the word story - “to make a long story short” - and his feeling that there was something more in life. “Something more” is noted on Peter's chart as an individual theme. Peter speaks to his life as if it is a journey, with stops, obstacles, opportunities and surprises, and makes considered decisions on how to move through it – his love of God embedding the journey while he always searches for “something more”. This can be seen in how he has embraced new ways of being after his diagnosis of dementia – for example, seeing God in the dog he now loves, and the work he does to help others understand his diagnosis.

In reference to realizing he needed another change for the benefit of his family, and embracing new opportunities Peter stated,

“It became difficult – it's very difficult when you take a family who is used to one way of living coming through sales and marketing and those kinds of things to a lower level of income as a student pastor and that was very difficult and It worked for a while, but I knew that this wasn't quite it for me and I needed to take a leave of absence. So I took a leave of absence from Ministry for about four years and I began working for people with disabilities, I was a home manager and worked for a company that had group homes and all of that, before I began to feel a sense of call to go back into ministry – and then I went through a divorce. Then I felt a sense of need to go back and the United Methodist church - they wanted me to come back. But I wasn't itinerant - you know the Methodist say you're at the discretion of the Bishop -you move as you move. And I just didn't feel that part of it in my heart, so I began to search - a friend introduced me to the United Church of Christ. And I began to see a call with

the United Church of Christ - I found some commonality with them and connected with them and Lo and behold, after going through that long process in 2001 – I became a part of them.”

There are words that Peter uses in this section that speak to the way he sees the world and embraces change. He speaks of connectedness, of needing to be “part of it in my heart”, and a “sense of a call.” His calling from God is never separate from how he approaches the changes in his life. Certainly, these are the kinds of phrases that those in both the faith-based field and in social work can explore in their understanding of someone with dementia - many people see faith as a road to connectedness (Swinton, 2012) and for someone like Peter this is important in all aspects of his life. When Peter experiences life as closing in on him he finds new ways to embrace what is and to find his new normal, including those he loves in the process.

When discussing a need to supplement his income Peter uses the term “lo and behold.” “Lo and behold” is a phrase Peter used several times, to show the results of the changes he has embraced in life. It is an optimistic phrase - it expresses “surprise or wonder” (Merriam-Webster, 2023). For Peter, it seems to show him retaining a sense of optimism even when the “lo and behold” refers to some difficulty. Mark Kramer (2020, p.3) defines the phenomenology of wonder as “full engagement with something that bewilders you.” Kramer states, “I study wonder, imagination, and enchantment because I believe these are human capacities that have been given short shrift by our culture,” (p.1). By using the phrase “lo and behold” Peter himself is (perhaps not consciously) engaging in a phenomenological turn, showing his sense of surprise at what presents itself. He assumes an “...attentive and naive openness to descriptions of phenomena, an uncertainty about what is to come and a willingness to wonder about the experiences...” (Kleinman, 2004, p.12). When engaging with someone like Peter, whether from a social work or a faith-based angle, one should consider how to capture the person’s sense of wonder and share it with them.

Peter discussed coming to terms with his diagnosis. How he did so shows how he embraces the difficulties that life brings to him. He stated, “So, the first thing I did was Google Alzheimer’s and came upon the Miami Valley Dayton Area Alzheimer’s Association, so I got connected with them and I started attending their workshops, you know, learning all about the warning signs. Understanding dementia and Alzheimer’s effective communications – I learned all of that... and behold, I am now Community Educator for them.” He says “the FIRST thing I did was Google Alzheimer’s” - Peter is not a passive recipient in his life but one who grabs opportunity, even in circumstances that are difficult. This is the type of “idiographic”, person-centered finding - very particular to Peter - that can inform how those who work with him interact and support his way of being. Again, Peter uses the word “behold” here to express wonder at how well it worked out - his active learning resulting in him becoming a community educator. Peter’s willingness to learn and grow shines out here. Getting a dog after his diagnosis was an important story Peter shared. He stated, “In August, I was diagnosed. In September came the dog. My wife said, ‘I’m not dealing with this.’ Right - I agreed – she’s not dealing with this.” Peter embraced the dog and decided that God was instrumental in sending him the dog. He said, “it’s a God thing.” This is another example of Peter embracing life, change, and opportunity. “It’s a God thing” is important for Peter, accepting and using the “God things” to help him through his dementia diagnosis. Peter has shown, throughout his interview, how the “God things” in life remain a constant source of support and well-being. Peter embraces change, living in wonder, and accepting the God things that come his way.

4.3.2 Help Me Worship (Adela, appendix 6c; Elizabeth, Appendix 6d; Peter, Appendix 6f)

The theme of worship was mentioned often and in multiple ways with most of my participants but a few were very explicit in their need to be helped to worship, warranting this as an individual theme. Adela and Elizabeth both expressed the need to worship – and

expressed it in a way that implied others must now be intricately involved in this. They made statements about the importance of this even when we were discussing other, seemingly unrelated, subjects. Worship was clearly ever present on their minds. Peter's focus on worship was more explicit, looking at his own role as a minister and his own need to help others worship well. All of my participants held worship to be important and for Adela and Elizabeth, the need was clear, explicit, and often expressed emotionally.

Adela stated, "Belief in God helps me – I say, 'Infinite mercy help me'. I say that all the time. I repeat it. 'Infinite mercy - help me.' I say that and I say it." For Adela, worshipping throughout the day, with regular invocations, is clearly a source of comfort. Later Adela said, "I go to Mass every day – It helps me spiritually...I feel close to God...they take me down to Mass." When Adela said "they take me down to Mass" she stated with in a very strong voice, making eye contact, and tapped the table with her hand. Adela is dependent on others to take her to Mass, and is clear it is, and should remain, a daily activity. Being in a Catholic Care Home, where daily Mass is offered, is key to her happiness.

Elizabeth stated, "I love the Magnificat. A lady's daughter gave me a version of it... I'll tell you what I want – a prayer group. I wish we had a prayer group. A Lady of Guadalupe group. This is what would be good for me. This is what I think about, when I think about dementia." Elizabeth made it clear that her thoughts about her own diagnosis are never separate from her need for support from her faith and an ability to worship.

When discussing the concept of hope, Elizabeth said, "Hope – I think a lot of people don't feel it; don't see it; so many people don't think about anything. They don't see it at all. It would be nice to have a prayer group." Interestingly, we were not discussing prayer groups at this time, but it was important to Elizabeth to mention this suggesting it was ever present in her mind.

Peter's statements on the need for worship were different. He spoke a great deal about creating worship opportunities for those for whom worship has become difficult – those with mental illness or dementia. Peter said, in discussing opening up worshipping opportunities, “that's what we're hoping. To do that as well with our group and how can we congregations be open and welcoming to these people. And it takes some education, it takes teaching and showing them how.” Peter was very serious when he was telling me this – looking at me intently, speaking with emphasis.

Peter explained a situation in which he was able to help someone else worship. He said,

A doctor started attending our small church, because he had been in Springfield at a bigger church where his wife and she were beginning to experience dementia. And being disruptive in worship he needed a safe place. I mean, she used to get up I'd be up there preaching, and she'd do this. She would get up and put her coat on - And go. - I wouldn't say anything but I'd finish up and none of us ever said anything or did anything - we just welcomed.

Peter spoke eloquently about how he understood the disruption and the need to have an open, understanding setting for everyone to worship. He got rather excited telling me about this woman and the need to help her worship. It is interesting to speculate if Peter is also thinking about his own future. It is possible that as he discusses someone else with more advanced dementia than his, he is thinking about a time when he will need the compassion and understanding of others in the worship setting.

Peter discussed the need for dementia groups, stating, “I can do workshops for congregations. I've gone to a number of our congregations - my cluster group of churches - and just talked about my story, and what we can do as churches to be welcoming to individuals who are differently abled than we are”. He is thinking beyond dementia, to those who might need help for various reasons. Peter went on to say, “And there's a process - being welcoming, inclusive, supportive and engaging with people because that's what I found most difficult for me as a pastor - knowing people in my congregations with disabilities.” It is interesting that

Peter is able to critique his own former lack of understanding and what he sees as his inability to relate to those who are “different”. This informs how he now wants to approach teaching others.

Peter was very concerned with helping others worship, which may foreshadow his future worship needs and challenges. Peter is at a stage in his dementia where he speaks far more extensively than Adela and Elizabeth, yet, in their own ways, they all expressed the central place of worship in the life of a believer. This need does not change when one receives a diagnosis of dementia. This call for help - whether Elizabeth stating repeatedly the need for a Lady of Guadalupe rosary group, Adela calling out to God, or Peter’s concerted efforts to have more open worship - can inform how we in faith-based positions consider the needs of those with dementia, and the importance of being very deliberate in how we create worship opportunities. In further chapters the concept of Dementia Friendly Churches is discussed, in reference to these points.

4.4 GEMs

The concept of the GEM emerged for me as an exploratory way to consider the words of my participants. Ashworth uses the phrase “a hunch” to describe the GEM - certainly this might be seen as a controversial way to engage in analysis but if behind each “hunch” there is considered thoughtfulness, and reflection, we can grasp something important for individual participants. It is admittedly a risky endeavour to start speaking about participant GEMs because much of it seems speculative. And yet, if done with integrity and reflexively, it can contribute to understanding our participants’ world.

Three primary GEMs stood out during the analysis process: “daffodils”, Lady of Guadalupe rosary group, and “ok to sit on the bottom shelf.” The first two were said by Elizabeth. Elizabeth spoke about being brought daffodils by the priests and nuns and her wish for a

Lady of Guadalupe rosary group. The third GEM is Richard's statement that it is "ok to sit on the bottom shelf".

4.4.1 Daffodils (Elizabeth, Appendix 6d)

Two statements of Elizabeth's emerged for me as containing hidden GEMs. There was almost a moment of "recognition" for me when re-reading Elizabeth's transcript and seeing these statements. I immediately felt a connection to and recognition of something she might have been trying to express, or something she was feeling. Elizabeth stated, "Our nuns and priests do a great deal for us with dementia – they give us daffodils. They come to us and give us daffodils." Daffodils occurred to me as a GEM.

Daffodils represent spring and beauty. They are lovely. According to Floralay (2022, p. 1) "The daffodil symbolises rebirth and new beginnings. It's one of the first flowers to bloom at the end of winter, announcing the beginning of spring and signifying the end of the cold, dark days." In her mention of daffodils I recognised a need for beauty in Elizabeth's words. I also recognised a need to reclaim all that dementia takes from one – new beginnings, a sense of springtime. Elizabeth's statement made me consider the role of social workers in older people's lives, and if we sufficiently consider ideas such as beauty. Even a quick search of the literature pointed to a lack of attention to this. This is an area of great potential for research, and one I hope to explore more in the future.

4.4.2 Lady of Guadalupe Rosary Group (Elizabeth, Appendix 6)

Elizabeth stated, "I wish we had a prayer group. A lady of Guadalupe group. This is what would be good for me. This is what I think about when I think about dementia." Elizabeth's repeated mention of Our Lady of Guadalupe is poignant. Our Lady of Guadalupe is what is called an approved Marian apparition - times when, according to many Catholics, Mary appeared to people to spread messages. For staunch Catholics, like Elizabeth, Marian apparitions likely have a place of importance in their spirituality. Mary, the mother of Jesus,

is often referred to as “Mother Mary” by Catholics. Our Lady of Guadalupe remains one of the most loved apparitions, as it represents Mary as a loving and compassionate mother.

Mary’s words to the receiver of her apparition include the following:

Listen, put it into your heart, my youngest and dearest son, that the thing that disturbs you, the thing that afflicts you, is nothing. Do not let your countenance, your heart be disturbed. Do not fear this sickness of your uncle or any other sickness, nor anything that is sharp or hurtful. Am I not here, I, who am your Mother? Are you not under my shadow and protection? Am I not the source of your joy? Are you not in the hollow of my mantle, in the crossing of my arms? Do you need anything more? Let nothing else worry you, disturb you. Do not let your uncle's illness worry you, because he will not die now. You may be certain that he is already well (Xavier University, no date, p. 1).

In Elizabeth’s call for a Lady of Guadalupe rosary group I felt a call for a compassionate mother – one who covers us with her mantle and makes all ok. Ageing is a scary process and ageing with dementia even more so. Perhaps, implied within Elizabeth’s wish for a Lady of Guadalupe rosary group, is a need for a compassionate mother. This suggests a real opportunity for further exploration into how those with dementia might hold a deep need for a mother figure - and can inform our own compassion when working with those with dementia. Elizabeth’s need for those in the faith community to approach her with beauty and loving kindness and the impact this has on how she feels are apparent in these GEMs.

4.4.3 “Quite happy sitting on the bottom shelf” (Richard, Appendix 6b)

The relevant quote for this GEM references a bookcase analogy, which will be explored first. The Bookcase Analogy is an explanation used by the Alzheimer’s Association (England) to explain what happens to our memory during the dementia process (Greensleeves Care, n.d.). Our new memories are on the top of the bookshelf of the memory bookcase, but this top is very shaky and inaccessible. The embedded, long seated, life-long memories remain at the bottom of the bookshelf – giving us our life’s foundation. There is a second bookcase - our

current feelings are on a second bookshelf, and we still can reach the top and retain the feelings. However, we do not always know why we have these current feelings as our memories are on the bottom shelf of the memory bookcase.

Richard and his wife discussed the Bookshelf analogy as it had helped them understand what was happening with Richard. Richard ended by saying, “following in that analogy of Ali’s bookcase, if you accept the fact that you don’t want to be put back on the top shelf...accept quite happily coming down a few levels...I have no problem...I’m quite happy sitting on the bottom shelf.” Richard’s reference to “the bottom shelf” stood out to me as I went back through his transcript and Zoom video of his interview. I pondered what it means to sit on the bottom shelf. He may have meant he is happy to be on the bottom shelf of memory - or even the bottom shelf of life, as his dementia progresses or it may be an analogy for his acceptance of his whole situation. Possibly he feels having dementia automatically implies one is on the bottom shelf. The imagery in this is what is so moving. The Christian faith teaches that humility is a value worth honing, and it is possible that Richard being happy to be on the bottom shelf is part of his embracing of Christian humility, Richard went on to say his diagnosis “has not affected my faith at all. That’s still strong. I’ve realized and accepted that if you have a faith it doesn’t exonerate you from all the ills that come with old age at all. You just live with that. It’s a totally separate thing for my faith, it doesn’t impede my practice of faith.” This is a statement of very profound acceptance and seems to align with him saying he is “quite happy to sit on the bottom shelf.” It must be noted, however, that Richard made other statements implying that he did feel some difficulties with having dementia and this is further explored in the Empathy/Suspicion section below.

If we accept Richard’s statements about his journey and being “ok sitting on the bottom shelf”, it might be worth considering if the term “bottom shelf” itself needs deconstructing. If

Richard sees himself “on the bottom shelf”, it is important to be aware of the potential negative connotation to that statement. Social workers and faith-based workers may help clients such as Richard by looking for opportunities to show him that dementia does not mean “sitting on the bottom shelf” in all areas of life. The implications and subtext of what one says can be important for understanding how best to help. This is the type of GEM that potentially gives both a social worker or a faith-based worker much to think about and deconstruct.

4.5 Ricoeur: the Double Hermeneutic of Empathy/Suspicion - Examples from My Participants

This section offers me an opportunity to critique my own work as it relates to the themes that emerged for me during the research process. Qualitative research can be seen as a subjective activity, in which the researcher has a particular lens through which the world and the interviews are seen. While bracketing is key to phenomenological analysis, it is acknowledged that no amount of bracketing results in completely unbiased results. Looking at my results through the framework of Empathy and Suspicion has allowed me to challenge my own findings. In this section I will look at my participant interviews and emergent themes with a critical eye, focusing on the phenomenological double hermeneutic.

Ricoeur’s work is helpful in understanding the concept of the double hermeneutic and has helped me delve into a deeper level of analysis, moving beyond the aforementioned themes. Although I have already explored individual themes, GEMs and cross-participant themes, I think it is important to look at areas where my own findings can be challenged and deconstructed. In this section, I challenge my own findings by using Ricoeur’s Empathy and Suspicion model and show how I use these concepts to help unpack the lived experience of my participants (Ricoeur, 1970). Additionally, I explore the importance of social workers and

faith-based workers learning to think in the way of the double hermeneutic, in order to truly understand those they work with - a challenging task.

According to Smith (2004, p.13), “Doing IPA means navigating between different layers of interpretation as one engages deeply with texts of participants’ personal experience.” Ricoeur (1970) proposes a hermeneutics of empathy and a hermeneutics of suspicion, showing one way to envision the double hermeneutic. I have used this model of the double hermeneutic in analysing my findings, re-envisioning empathy and suspicion as “restoration” and “demystification” (Josselson, 2004). Josselson prefers the terms “restoration” and “demystification” to Ricoeur’s “faith” and “suspicion”, as she believes them to be more respectful to the user-voice.

For Ricoeur (1974, p.13) interpretation is “the work of thought which exists in deciphering the hidden meaning in the apparent meaning, in unfolding the levels of meaning implied in the literal meaning.” Ricoeur takes “a both/and” approach, asking us to imagine what it is like to be another person, but also being critical and “probing for meaning in ways which participants might be unable or unwilling to do themselves,” (Eatough and Smith, 2017, p.14). As Kearney (2017, p.16) says “it is not sufficient simply to describe meaning as it appears. We are also obliged to interpret it as it conceals itself.” For Ricoeur, we remain “sympathetic” to how it appears and “suspicious” about the hidden layers (Ricoeur, 1970). I attempted to do this with my participant interviews and my own analyses. I am also convinced that this level of analysis can be engaged with by those who work to support individuals with dementia, such as social workers. I can envision, for example, a social worker sitting with Andrew, and trying to support his independence and self-esteem - the social worker would need to hear his optimism about life while also “reading between the lines” into his feelings of being “lost” when he gets frustrated by not remembering how to drive home. The social worker would have to engage in the “both/and.”

The “both/and” approach can be explored in multiple comments of my participants – for example Peter’s clear statement that he does not want to focus on or sing about suffering – he prefers to stay joyful – while then saying how much he appreciates Scott Peck’s writing about life being difficult (Peck, 1978). The conflict emerges and shows the ambiguity of “how” someone with dementia experiences their world. While Peter (and others) clearly felt a level of optimism and a great hope in God and their faith – there could there be another side to their statements. Grasping this ambiguity can enhance our analysis as researchers and our understanding as those in positions of support for those with dementia. While I have been able to ruminate on Peter’s ambiguity while re-playing the Zoom video of his interview, I am also speculating about how a social work practitioner could engage in a similar level of analysis. Being able to listen in this manner goes beyond the normal assessment form used in many social work local authorities.

Josselson (2004) further explores the “both/and” perspective, helping to show its richness. She describes her system of restoration and demystification the following way, “Because meanings cannot be grasped directly and all meanings are essentially indeterminate in any unshakable way, interpretation becomes necessary and this is the work of the hermeneutic enterprise,” (p.3). Josselson encourages us to restore meaning and help people uncover meaning, in creative ways.

Josselson (2004, p.13) notes “...surface appearances mask depth realities...the researcher may, for example, be alert to various forms of self-deception that may be operative; feelings and words that may not match.” Sometimes people say things that seemingly conflict. This was seen multiple times by me - for example, Richard stating he is not concerned about having dementia and then going on to express frustration at having dementia. Adela expressed something similar. Adela is the expert on her own feelings, as we say in the social work profession and yet, despite saying her diagnosis does not matter, I could hear real

anguish behind the plea for “Infinite Mercy” to help her. When Peter insisted he does not see life in terms of what we suffer, he followed it by later expressing his admiration for Scott Peck and the belief that life is difficult - it is possible that what is being “disguised” is a tension in his feelings.

The notion of “disguised” communication is contentious, however. It is argued that our interpretation may be biased if we as interpreters of our participants’ statements claim “disguised communication.” Practice wisdom is a notion that can help. “Practice wisdom in social work is not only the wisdom of analytical experience, but it is also the wisdom or a quality characterized by courtesy, kindness, consideration, compassion and benevolence” (Cheung, 2016, p.1). Approaching a social work client, or a research participant, who has dementia, with compassion and benevolence might help us see beyond the words, and move beyond a strict analytic analysis, while still respecting their explicit statements. It is important for researchers to discover inherent meaning in the narratives we collect while remaining faithful to the intentions of the participant telling their story even if multiple narratives exist or the participant’s intentions are layered (Tappan, 1997).

Remaining reflexive is important for maintaining ethical standards while engaging in restoration and demystification. Various models have been proposed for reflexivity. I have used a circle of reflexivity approach, continuously “watching” myself and ensuring I am not imposing my values, my politics, or my preconceived theories into my attempt to demystify the words of my participants. This was especially important in my analysis of Brother James because he made statements that were challenging and that I had to step away from and allow “to be”.

According to Haynes (2012, p.73), “researcher reflexivity involves thinking about how our thinking came to be, how a pre-existing understanding is constantly revised, in light of new understandings, and how this in turn affects our research.” The concept of “thinking about

how our thinking came to be” implies multiple levels of reflection, constantly reaching back to why we think what we think, as the researcher. When Adela told me that she uses the constant refrain “Infinite Mercy, Help Me”, on first hearing this, it occurred to me as a pious Catholic saying that many will have been taught in Church. When I engaged with “thinking about my own thinking” I realized I was imposing a simple interpretation on a very heart-felt exclamation, that could reach back to how Adela coped with the loss of her son, early in her life - and how she now uses those coping mechanisms in her dementia journey. Reflexivity is a deeper and enhanced reflection. Using reflexivity along with Ricoeur’s model helped me to “see” my participant’s statements in new and creative ways and served the double purpose of “checking” myself in terms of my own biases and locating the areas of “suspicion” (demystification).

Colleen Reichman (2022) talks about the power of holding two emotions at once. She discusses inserting the word ‘and’ between two feelings rather than ‘or’ allowing the person to feel and honour two emotions simultaneously that seem to conflict. She believes that doing so broadens one’s perspective about the world and people around us. Helping those with dementia feel and honour their multiple and seemingly conflicting feelings about their faith and their diagnosis could be a task for all who seek to support them. We will see the value of using the “and” word below, in my examples of Richard and James.

4.5.1 Richard: Examples of Demystification/Restoration, Empathy/Suspicion (6b)

Richard’s interview offers an opportunity to show the reflexive cycle and the double hermeneutic, using Ricoeur’s empathy and suspicion model. I spent a great deal of time reading and reflecting on Richard’s text. Richard claimed his relationship with God and faith were unaffected by his diagnosis. Yet, later in the interview he stated, “if you embrace it [the dementia] you are still in control” and that faith “helps you through them [doubtful thoughts].” This acknowledgement of “doubtful thoughts” is important, and relevant to how

we as faith-based workers, social workers, and educators need to interact with those whom we are working. It speaks to the need for what I will call “enhanced listening” and not accepting at face value “first statements”.

Richard’s acknowledgement of “doubtful thoughts” and needing to stay “in control” seemed to “creep in” after a very upbeat exhortation about his relationship with God being unaltered. This warrants further reflection. All of my participants expressed a deep belief in the “goodness of God” and the comfort their faith gives them, and yet it is clear that there might be something more nuanced happening for them. It is possible that deep-seated faith in God’s goodness exists simultaneously with doubt, and that the lesson for those of us seeking to support those with dementia is attention to both of these realities. It would be easy to accept at face value Richard’s “no negative response to that at all” - that his faith is firm as is his conviction that God is good. Yet, it would ignore that subtle comment about embracing dementia to remain in control - acknowledging that control is being slowly lost and that he has no choice but to embrace it. This type of analysis, of thinking and re-thinking Richard’s words, on the part of the researcher, social worker, or faith-based worker, can make for a more empathetic encounter, where our own words and interventions can speak to both realities for Richard.

4.5.2 Brother James: Examples of Demystification/Restoration, Empathy/Suspicion (Appendix 6e)

Brother James is also an example that helps us see how empathy/suspicion, or restoration/demystification can help enlighten us as to what our research participants are expressing. Brother James is what I call my “outlier” participant. He was the participant who had the most complex answers to my questions, showing a great deal of ambiguity and ambivalence. While choosing to stay a Marist brother, going by the name Brother James, and having a crucifix and other religious items in his rooms, Brother James also stated he has

reservations about the Church and even about the term “faith”. He said “I don’t know who God is. I change my mind every day.” When asking him about doubt he said, “what kind of question is that? Doubt is there. Faith and doubt.” His answers about hope are extremely interesting. Brother James said he does not hold hope, because even having to use the word hopes implies there can be such a thing as lack of hope. He seems to see hope as so self-evident, it does not need a name, and giving it a name implies the opposite is even a possibility – a possibility that is not open to him. Brother James managed to say in the same conversation that he does not hold hope because he holds hope.

The enigma of Brother James can help to further enrich our understanding of restoration and demystification, and then explore the professional ramifications. Social work values claim that the client is the expert on their own needs and experience (Murphy, Duggan and Joseph, 2013). The restoration perspective also assumes the participant is the expert on their own experience and maintains that the individual is capable and receptive to share meanings with the researcher (Josselson, 2004). According to Ricoeur “Phenomenology is the instrument of the restoration of meaning,” (Ricoeur, 1970, p.28). Social workers, while taught to think holistically, are not always taught to think phenomenologically and in the language of “restoring meaning”.

Social workers need to learn to work with someone like Brother James, understanding his very nuanced feelings about his faith, and engaging these feelings in their work with him, with all the paradoxes. Social workers need to develop a comfort level about conversations of faith before they can even start to work with the nuances. It is very likely a social worker coming from a secular perspective might not experience the level of depth behind Brother James’s words and not be able to engage in the double hermeneutic. A social worker who hears Brother James say that he “doesn’t even know what faith is” might conclude that his faith is meaningless to him, yet that would be far from the truth. It would be impossible for a

social worker to even begin to understand the importance of hope in Brother James's life if the Christian concept of Hope has never been considered, and his ambiguous statement about the role of hope could easily be misunderstood. Brother James, like my other participants, holds faith as a source of comfort and support, but it is not as easy to discern this on first hearing his words – it takes reflexivity and openness to the 'both/and' of phenomenology. Furness and Gilligan's (2010) model for reflective social work practice is helpful, and it has a phenomenological bent that can help both social workers and researchers engage in the phenomenological process. They note the considerable difficulties social workers have in responding to spiritual needs and set out a model of probing questions that a social worker can ask him/herself to make sure they are remaining reflexive about spiritual matters. Key to this model is a call to remain open, interested, and creative in one's approach and outlook and an openness to change when change is necessary (Furness and Gilligan, 2010).

This particular model has many strengths when one is engaging with people of faith who have been diagnosed with dementia. Question 5 of the model is particularly important from an empathy/suspicion angle – asking if one is “sufficient to openness and willingness to review”. This is something we as social workers are encouraged to do throughout our relationship with our service users but is rarely explicitly applied by social workers to the field of faith, and certainly not taught in relation to faith in our curriculums. If encouraged to hold “sufficient openness” perhaps the dichotomies and the “holding of multiple feelings at once” will emerge for the social worker.

If we engage with Brother James through the lens of this model, and look at his statements on hope, another probing question in the Furness/Gilligan model emerges as particularly important. One must consider how to be creative in response to Brother James's “strange” statements about hope. It would be very easy to dismiss his statement as one indicating a “lack” of hope, which could then reflect how he feels about his experience with dementia—

but a creative response would be to consider how the deeper nuance might reflect a great deal of hopefulness, and that hope is a spiritual resource within him that is harder for us to grasp than for those participants who were more explicit.

In the social work interview, we listen with empathy. In the research interview we also have to approach the written interview with empathy, remembering the person behind the words. As well as using the above model as presented by Gilligan, it might be helpful for social workers to consider the perspective of Buber. Buber (2000) posited the “I-Thou” relationship, arguing that we must always see the other as a subject and never an object. It’s an approach that must be taken, by the social worker, the faith-based worker, and the researcher. This technique of fully appreciating, in the moment, the other as a human is what has helped me retain the restoration and demystifying perspectives, looking at every statement as one given by a valuable human being, with a true curiosity in what is trying to be expressed. All that has emerged for me has been looked at in light of the very “human-ness” of the participant, even while reading a script. There was no time, in all of my reading, that I did not stop to consider the way my participant looked, his or her tone of voice, the very strong connection created, and the very value of this person - even over Zoom. The “I-Thou” was never forgotten. Deliberately using the “I-Thou” perspective when considering Brother James prompted me to reconsider some of his answers. Part of this involved taking him at his word – while demystifying his statements and remaining curious and questioning. It would be easy to have interpreted Brother James as trying to avoid answers with what appeared as evasive answers – but when considering the sheer human-ness of him, and the experience of his dementia, I could reach beyond evasiveness and envision him as a man trying hard to convey something that was deep and difficult to express. I could “look over his shoulder” so to speak, and re-look at his statements, in a way that helped draw out his possible underlying meanings.

The “I-Thou” relationship is key to all social work and faith-based work and has been a key feature of my relationship with my participants for this project. It has been imperative to see them all as individuals and let the idiographic approach of the IPA technique shine through. Part of this has been “taking them at their word”. This is also in line with person-centred social work practice and relationship-based practice (Ingram and Smith, 2018; Murphy, Duggan and Joseph, 2013). This perspective helped me as a researcher see the human in front of me, even when re-reading his or her words in a transcript.

4.6 Conclusion

Chapter 4 has focused heavily on participant statements, showing cross participant themes, individual themes and GEMs. The Cross Participant themes of See Me, God’s Innocence, Radical Dependence, Humour, and Counter Cultural Stories have been discussed, with emphasis on participant statements to show why they were coded as cross participant themes. Chapter 5 will analyse all 5 of these themes in more detail, building a theoretical and phenomenological way of understanding them.

Individual themes were reviewed, giving time and attention to the particular individual voice, as is consistent with IPA. GEMs were considered as a relatively new and cutting-edge concept in the field of IPA research, and I attempted to show how particular GEMs stood out for me within certain participant interviews.

Finally, this chapter ended with a discussion of Ricoeur’s empathy/suspicion model. This afforded me an opportunity to dig deeper into participant statements, showing that there might be more than one understanding of statement, and more than one way to develop themes. Being able to look at particular statements and my own interpretations with a critical framework helps to ensure quality assurance in a qualitative study.

Chapter 5

Discussion and Analysis

5.1 Introduction

Chapter 5 will focus on discussion and analysis surrounding the cross-participant themes that have emerged. Cross participant themes will be discussed and analysed in relation to theoretical backdrops that have emerged through the course of my research. IPA is an inductive process where what one experiences drives the next steps, thoughts, and development of theoretical context. I am offering a rich discussion that has emerged through my interaction with the participant scripts and offers insight into the question of how holding the Christian faith impacts one through the course of dementia. Because participant statements drove this analysis and IPA research integrates all aspects of the participant experience through the whole research process, I will be referring to statements made by participants, in this discussion chapter. To review, the 5 cross participant themes that will be discussed and analysed are See Me/I am Not Lost, God's Innocence/ Radical Acceptance, Releasing Control/Radical Dependence, The Multiple Sides of Humour/The Laughing Christ, Counter Cultural Stories/The Faith Stories that Help Me.

5.2 Cross Participant Theme: See Me/I am Not Lost

See Me/I am Not Lost is a cross participant theme that is crucial for helping understand and combat the sense of isolation and invisibility that many who have dementia feel. All of my participants, given the progressive nature of dementia, are moving towards a time when they might not recognize others at all, and might not be able to take the initiative in approaching others. Significantly, for some of my participants, their bodies will become the mechanism by which they express their faith, making it imperative that others come to them, and share in their bodily worship.

Concepts such as personhood prioritize cognition and because of this many feel that “...persons with severe dementia are threatened to lose their status as persons” (Fuchs, 2020, p. 665). Fuchs’s (2020) phenomenology of embodiment, where bodies are seen to hold memories within them, helps to dispute this notion that we are all simply our minds. His theory of embodied memories can be seen in Elizabeth’s love for the rosary (a bodily practice fixed from childhood), or her bodily reaction and response when the priests “come to us” and “give us daffodils”. Adela, as well, in her rote prayers and phrases - whether it’s the Our Father as said in Mass, or the repeating of “Infinite Mercy Help Me” - shows how the embedded memory can be out-with our cognition, and prayer can be ingrained as life-long practice. Elizabeth and Adela are “persons” not just because of their current cognitive abilities, but because of every memory their body retains. The importance of the body can be seen in the constant refrain of all my participants about the importance of others coming to them. As Andrew said, “they come to me, and say my name.”

The body is necessary for exploring the senses and engaging with other people and the world around us (Fuchs, 2020). I note Adela’s emphatic insistence that she “sat right down with [her struggling students].” Her body was next to their body, on the same level, changing the power dynamic. It was her “encounter with other humans and the world”, as Fuchs described.

Adela’s example of sitting with her students - on their level - was one from many years ago and yet a memory that retained its importance to her. It is easy to speculate that Adela intuits the need for bodies to be seen and respected and this need continues through the experience of dementia. Fuchs (2020) concerns himself with what he calls the “pre-reflective” self – the self that exists in the body, beyond the faculty of reflection. When considering how the holding of their Christian faith impacts my participants, for some these “bodily memories” of faith practice are what sustains them even when cognition fails.

There is a critique of Fuchs's view, however, that warrants attention. Zahavi (2006) objects that pre-reflective self-awareness is not how we consider the "self" at all, on a regular basis, and therefore might be a difficult concept to really embed in work with those with dementia. I find this a compelling critique as most of us do not consciously think of ourselves "as" our body, and of course do include our cognition and mental memories, our sense of humour and ability to communicate verbally in how we conceive of self. Yet, it seems that Fuchs is showing us a way to add to or improve upon what is considered a "person". His theory in no way means we have to only define personhood in a bodily way, but it gives us an expanded notion of personhood, pushing us to consider our bodies as key to what it means to be ourselves, and moving us beyond the 20th century discourse of analytic ability equaling personhood. This is key to working with those with dementia, who need to be valued as embodied people still living in this world.

Fuchs (2020, p.668) responds to critiques such as the above stating, "The majority of that which we have experienced and learned does not become accessible to us in retrospect, but far more in the practical movement of everyday life: habits are built in us through repetition and practice and they are activated by themselves; established processes of movement are merged into our flesh and blood." One of the participants, Andrew, expressed this beautifully, perhaps without realizing it, when he spoke of his body moving along with the bell, when he was a child. Andrew was given the job of ringing the bell, and heralding people to church, when he was around 12 years old. He explained it in the following way:

I was 5, or 12. How old was I? I rang the bell for many years. Did you know, when you ring the bell, your body moves with the bell? The rope moves, the bell moves, and you move. One time I rang it too hard and broke it. It all went wonky (laughs). And it was loud so loud. But I was strong. I moved with it. And one time I threw the rope over the bell and it didn't work. It was all my body, I had to do it right.

Andrew stressing it “was all his body” and “he moved with the bell” as he heralded the worshipers to church, and how the movement of his body was integral to the bell even ringing, shows the power of the body in who we are and how we experience the world around us. Andrew’s body learned to move with the bell, so that the bell would ring. The ringing of the bell invited worshipers into the church and a communal time of worship. The body is a source of opportunity, as shown by Andrew, and one which must be considered when thinking about the faith of those with dementia.

5.3 Cross Participant Theme: God’s Innocence/Radical Acceptance

The theme of God’s Innocence helps us understand the way in which difficulties might be approached by those who hold a strong faith, throughout their lives. The participants I interviewed were adamant in their acceptance of their diagnosis and their confidence in God’s goodness. All 8 participants made strong statements about holding their faith and confidence in God apart from their dementia. I seek to understand this and develop it through the related lenses of God’s Innocence and kenosis. while also touching upon Process Theology and its potential applicability and fodder for future study.

Balthasar is noted in the Catholic tradition for his kenotic theology – that God’s very nature is not power but is self-giving love. God is in a constant state of pouring out love within the trinity – the Father, Son, and Holy Spirit – and to all of human-kind (Yoder, 2014). God’s love - and not His power – is His primary trait, and all of life is a repetition of self-giving love. Kenosis offers much to think about in terms of generic ageing and more specifically the dementia process. Mary Pandiani (2017, p.1) has offered the term “Elegant Kenosis”, from her PhD, and I find it worth quoting her beautiful word here:

“Elegant Kenosis is an imaginative and inventive theological term of my own creation, a touchstone that helps to discern ageing choices. Following Jesus Christ’s action in Philippians 2:7, the process of *kenosis* is the choice to empty one form of identity to take on a new one. In the transition of ageing, *kenosis* is the intention to release a former way of life to enter

another. Significant emptying occurs with losses that accompany ageing. To offset the discouragement that comes with loss, the unique contribution of the second half of life focuses on giving one's life away by choice. Decisions based on reflection, choices, and God's grace, replace cultural compulsions or unconscious actions. Combined with *kenosis*, *elegance* reflects a desire to enter the ageing process with grace and simplicity. To face losses in this way requires discernment and a sense of things significant. Culture's pressurized axiom, "avoid ageing at all costs," creates a din that makes other choices hard to hear. Through *Elegant Kenosis*, one has the choice and capacity to age gracefully by living into freedom that comes from contemplative practices."

It can be argued that my participants are engaging in this process of Elegant Kenosis by their insistence that the process of dementia just "is" and choosing not to connect anger or blame with their understanding of God. All seem to accept their decline, both physical and mental, as what it means to be human and to be one of God's children. Hinshaw (2023) discusses the "humility" needed for and related to kenosis, a concept that is completely absent from the social work field and social work education. All of my participants seemed to live with an innate humility, perhaps honed from a lifetime of experience, helping them on their journey into elegant kenosis. Kenosis is discussed again in Chapter 6, in regards to the social work profession and curriculum development in academia, as well as related to the theme of "Releasing Control/Radical Dependence".

5.4 Cross-Participant Theme: Releasing Control/Radical Dependence

Releasing control and embracing dependence is contrary to mainstream western culture in which control, agency, and independence are stressed as positive values. Dependence is not often discussed in a positive light. Yet, all 8 of my participants spoke of their dependence on God and others as a source of support and comfort as they try to live out their faith. Dependence, when combined with love and kindness, emerged as a positive value, and one which needs to be re-claimed in our culture.

Thinking about both dependence and surrender has led me down interesting theological paths. Relational Theology, Kenotic Theology, and Abandonment Theology have informed my thinking. While there has been much written on the dependence of those with dementia, and the relational model of care, there has not been as much written on how the Church itself (and almost nothing from a social work perspective) can foster a “kenotic” community that embraces the relational model fully and shows the necessity of holding a kenotic and relational theology “in abundance”.

Twentieth century Catholic theologian Karl Rahner’s theory of “abandonment to others” has been helpful in analyzing my participants’ statements that show them releasing control and embracing dependence. Rahner (1978) discusses an intersubjective reduction which argues that we are all transcendental beings who are open to alterity, to otherness. He argues that we are reaching for others by our nature, it is who we are (Rahner, 1978). This openness to others – this almost instinctual reaching - came out clearly in my participants’ statements. As Adela stated “I say over and over ‘Infinite Mercy help me’” – she is reaching out to God, as she sees Him as Infinite Mercy. This dependence on God is a clear comfort for Adela – she abandons herself to God, not in weakness, but in assurance of His love.

In Rahner’s (1978) own spirituality, he aims to practice his faith with a radical surrendering to God – and to “the other”. He believes “abandonment” belongs to the essence of human nature, as demonstrated by Jesus Christ. Thinking about my participants’ statements, it is clear that the abandonment is a two-way street – it is not simply the person with dementia abandoning themselves to those who help them – but the helper willingly abandons themselves to the person with dementia. When one releases control, there might be someone who has to then retain the control. This emerges in the following statements by Mark, who is calling for recognition by others, even when he, Mark, cannot initiate it. When others choose to approach him – then they are engaging in what he calls “true ministry.” As stated by Mark:

“I love the way Mel Bringle’s hymn expresses the experience of dementia. The hymn’s words ‘When memory fades and recognition falters...’ shares what is happening to me... For people with dementia, you sometimes cannot process information. I have trouble hearing and interpreting conversations at times. I sometimes do not recognize people, even loved ones I’ve known for many years. And so, when you have dementia, like I do, sometimes people do not “recognize” you and leave you out. I’m talking about recognition as a person who wants to belong but cannot always get the words or thoughts out to share. Many, though, show respect, talk slowly and directly to me.”

Rahner - while not strictly a phenomenologist - takes a phenomenological turn in some of his thinking (Rosok, 2018). Rahner discusses the preconscious “givenness” of one that impacts the consciousness of the “other” (Rahner, 1978). Rosok interprets Rahner’s work as setting a “...theoretical basis for any loving relationship,” (Rosok, 2018, p.40). These are complex concepts to break down, but clearly point to an understanding of the human being as the giver and recipient of gift. As Rahner states “In other words, man utters himself and constitutes himself in his concrete nature and thereby opens himself to the very fact of a break-through from outside,” (Rahner, 1978). All of my participants, in releasing control, are asking to be receivers of gifts from others – and when this is done well within their faith communities, it shows faith communities to be a source of great well-being and comfort.

Rahner sees both the ontological “way of being” as self-givenness and a moral obligation in self-givenness. In “Love of Jesus and the Love of Neighbour” Rahner describes loving one’s neighbour as the foundational moral activity of humans (Rahner, 2000). It is foundational because through relationships with others is how humans “finds and fulfils himself”. It struck me while listening to all of my interviews how we are all increasingly dependent on the love of others, and that there is a resultant moral obligation to provide this, a view that seems consonant with Rahner. This moral obligation can be seen as counter cultural, in an era that

values self-development and fulfilment more than other-fulfilment (Swinton, 2012). For those on the dementia journey who do hold a Christian faith, we must draw on the deep tradition of self-giving-ness and dependence as a possible value, within the faith, and not be afraid to talk about the moral obligation to “give”. It is when others give to them, come to them, and see them that my participants feel God’s love and comfort.

Related to the concept of self-giveness is Kenotic Theology, a concept that emerges multiple places throughout this thesis, and is discussed more extensively below in my recommendations (see kenosis and empowerment, chapter 6). Kenosis is an area of study that needs far more attention for the understanding of ageing in general and certainly the understanding of dementia (Hinshaw, 2023). Associated in Catholic theology with Balthasar and in Protestant theology with Moltmann, there is a depth in kenosis to help us understand how to work with those with dementia, and how to help those with dementia, carers, and all of us see the world around us.

Kenosis can be defined, initially as the full or partial renunciation of the divine nature by Christ in the Incarnation (Brazier, 2012) and more generally, “‘to empty’ or ‘pour out’ one’s self” (Dawe, 2009, p.343). Many Christians speculate that the whole nature of the universe is one of kenosis – a renunciation of self, which was “perfected” in Christ. Some Process Theologians have embraced kenosis in the sense that evolution itself is a kenotic process. De Chardin discusses the earth as itself under construction, with kenosis and dying to self being a part of creation (De Chardin, 1971). Ilia Delio discusses creation being God’s kenosis of divine love (Delio, 2021). She believes love is an energy entrenched in molecular forces. Holmes Rolston, III (2001) discusses the link between kenosis and an evolutionary, biological world, and also links kenosis to the ‘suffering for others’. According to Rolston III (p.58) “Biological nature is always giving birth...[and] always in travail.” He argues that part of that travail is a constant giving up for new life. By Rolston’s account, when humans give up life,

it is similar to the dying within physical nature to make room for new life to emerge. We give up life by suffering for others which then gives new life to others. This clearly resonates with my participants, for as Brother James stated “heaven is now - people who are kind and generous”. It is when others in the faith communities “give themselves up” in generosity that Brother James feels Heaven.

Rolston III (2001, p.59) goes on to say:

The abundant life that Jesus exemplifies and offers to his disciples is that of a sacrificial suffering through to something higher. The spirit of God is the genius that makes alive, that redeems life from its evils. The cruciform creation is, in the end, deiform, Godly, just because of this element of struggle, not in spite of it.

Delio (2021) and Rolston III (2001) both argue how a “giving up” for higher purpose is inherent in nature. Jesus chose to self-empty for the well-being of the world – and there is an argument to be made that everyone of us can choose to self-give, even through suffering, for a higher purpose. Certainly, the carers and family members of those with dementia are in a position to engage in a voluntary giving up for the well-being of their loved one, as that very loved one is engaged in a giving up of autonomy and self-sufficiency. For those deeply involved with their Christian faith, having their faith community engage in radical self-giving can offer a level of support that transcends simple physical care and becomes spiritual care, even when this entails suffering.

Hinshaw (2023) offers much to think about when considering kenosis and the process of dementia. He rightly acknowledges that embracing kenosis is counter cultural in a culture where productivity is over-valued. He states “Only by voluntary kenosis i.e., embracing our limits and practicing restraint, can we begin to free ourselves of the delusive notion that real substantive progress entails production and consumption” (p. 204).

The participants I interviewed have moved beyond a life where production is a priority (or even, for some, possible) and yet still live in a culture and society that has not learned to see

the value in passivity. The radical dependence expressed by my participants reflect a stage of life where “elegant kenosis”, as phrased by Mary Pandiano, can be embraced to sustain well-being and a sense of worth. Depending on a God who has been loved throughout their lifetime and into their old age, my participants value a state of further dependence on God. Significantly, and as will be addressed in Chapter 6, social workers are not prepared to discuss theories such as abandonment and kenosis, and therefore not well equipped to use these theories to help service users with diagnoses of dementia.

Hinshaw (2023, p. 222) states, “Perhaps more than anything else, the kenosis associated with ageing and chronic serious illness raises a fundamental question. Are the purpose and meaning of life circumscribed within one’s active life or is there something more?” My participant statements show individuals finding purpose and meaning in the “something more”. Mark discussed that the “white” times are when those he loves are around him, in relationship with him, showing meaning in the love and presence of family members. Peter spoke elegantly about the Serenity Prayer and learning to live, each moment, in serenity. Adela spoke clearly about her well-being tied up with being taken down to Mass, on a daily basis – she stressed “they take me”. Richard spoke of the importance of “not wanting to be back on the top shelf” and being ok in his decline. All are letting go and finding joy beyond anything related to productivity.

In their dependence and acceptance of their declining bodies and minds, my participants all participate in kenosis, and in some sense their caregivers do too. Their caregivers also did not choose for their loved one to have dementia, but in choosing to spend their time and energy on the caring for others, they are doing so at the expense of other types of activity. Further research is warranted about how much the “giving up” entailed in care giving can be embraced by our culture as an outpouring of love and seen as its own type of kenosis, and how this might ultimately impact how social workers work with carers. Hinshaw (2023, p.

221) states “As the functional decline of ageing and chronic illness begins to manifest itself, not only does our performance slow down, but the quality of that performance may eventually deteriorate as well. It is this threat from kenosis to our “usefulness”, our place in society and family, that shakes us to our core.” Perhaps some of the “usefulness” in the dementia experience is in teaching others how to pour themselves out in kenotic love. The theory of kenosis speaks to both the one with dementia and their caregiver.

Caring for, and “coming to” those with dementia – having those with dementia as radically dependent on our ways of approaching, communicating with and caring for them – needs to be acknowledged as challenging for everyone. It is not helpful for anybody – those in the social work profession or those engaged in faith-based work - to try to hide the complexities with platitudes about helping others. This is where we need as faith communities to explore whether these theologies can embed our faith and move our Churches towards being truly relational, kenotic settings. We cannot expect any of us to step into the role and way of being of total self-giving unless we hold a very firm understanding, purpose, and belief in self-giving.

John Swinton (2012) speaks of this “givenness” in the language of the “divine thou”.

According to Swinton, Christians must have an alternative understanding of personhood, and explore relevant theologies and philosophies to help ourselves understand what it means to live a life of self-giving. Swinton defines being human as being (1) dependent and contingent, (2) embodied, (3) relational, (4) broken and deeply lost, and (5) loved and profoundly purposeful. The 5 criteria as presented by Swinton helps to understand, for example, Adela’s life experience, in which she is broken over many life events, including the loss of her son, dependent on her care home for maintaining her physical life, yet cherished and loved and therefore “profoundly purposeful” by her very dependence on God.

Mary Jo Iozzio (2005) also discusses dependence and focuses on our ultimate dependence on God. While acknowledging that we are radically dependent on our parents, families, and friends, she says that the ultimate radical dependence is on God, and that this fact challenges the value of autonomy that has a primary place in our culture. Swinton (2012) speaks of radical dependence by quoting Corinthians: “yet for us there is but one God, the Father, from whom all things came and for whom we live; and there is but one Lord, Jesus Christ, through whom all things came and through whom we live” (1 Corinthians 8:6). My participant Charlotte - the oldest of my participants - would agree with this analysis as she stated clearly “Of course, He’s [God] always with me, and you, too - whether we like it or not.”

Radical dependence is a theme that, given the Biblical witness and theological writings of givenness and kenosis, needs to be embraced by our faith communities, in teaching, preaching, and way of being. For those in the social work profession, it will be a harder concept to embrace – this is addressed more fully in the next chapter section on Empowerment and Kenosis and the challenges to the social work profession.

5.5 Cross Participant Theme – The Multiple Sides of Humour/Embracing the Laughing Christ

The theme of humour emerged in all of my interviews. My participants often looked joyous when using humour to make me laugh. This combination of joy and humour can be seen as part of the Christian joy they hold. For some of my participants, it seems as if their strong faith actually frees them to make use of humour to ponder and explore the strangeness of life. Their conviction of God’s love and care for them allows them to let go and live in joy, which includes a use of humour that is core to their faith.

Some of my participants used humour when answering my questions, thus helping to set a relaxed tone. Some spoke of the use of humour in their day to day lives. Interestingly, a few had the insight to show how humour is used both as a way to enhance well-being, and also, as

a way to cover gaps in memory, and ease conversation when they do not know how to answer questions. I found this very insightful and began exploring what it might mean for their faith and dementia journey and how we in faith-based positions or the social work profession could enhance our own use of humour in appropriate ways.

Finally, I note the concept of humour as “protest” against the difficulties in life (see discussion of Easter laughter below). It has long been acknowledged that humour is a part of the human condition (Amir, 2021), but its role in the faith journey is not well studied.

(Spoliar, 2022). Conrad Hyers (1969, p.4) states “human existence as such may be defined as a running interplay between seriousness and laughter, between sacred concerns and comic interludes”. It emerged from my interviews that humour has multiple roles for those in the dementia journey – that of sustaining joy, within the complexities of dementia, that of masking forgetfulness, that of living with the incongruities of the situation, and possibly that of allowing them to protest against their condition in a safe way.

Beard and Fox (2008) found that people with early-stage Alzheimer’s Disease use humour to help normalise their lives. Andrew showed a sense of using humour in this way when he responded to his wife’s comment about going to Dementia Friendly Groups – “well I’m demented” he said and laughed out loud. It is a speculation, but there was a sense of possible embarrassment at the mention of Dementia Friendly Groups and his ability to claim “well I’m demented” in a funny way might have eased the embarrassment and normalised it for him.

Humour allows different people to approach similar situations from different perspectives (Mak and Sorensen, 2018). Humour serves as a coping mechanism for challenging situations. It can break the tension and make uncomfortable topics easier to discuss (Chapple and Ziebland, 2004). Approaching the same situation from a different perspective was shown by Richard in his humorous comments about waking up and potentially not recognising his wife

– focusing on “waking up with a new woman every morning...getting to know her for the first time”, and then laughing heartily.

MacRae (2010) found humour changed the focus of people with dementia and helped them focus less on their own defects as well as reducing overall stress. These studies suggest that integrating humour into their everyday lives of those diagnosed with dementia may result in improved well-being. Andrew mentioned to me being a teacher in the past and then discussed (with laughter) how they let him be a teacher “even though he had 2 names”, and that he was a teacher “of sorts”. These comments display a self-deprecating sense of humour about who he was before his diagnosis of dementia.

Although these studies all indicate that humour is a key concept for the dementia journey, there does not seem to be enough exploration of humour from the angle of faith. Fred Layman (1982) addresses the fact that religious disciplines rarely address humour, particularly in current times. Given the importance of faith in the life of my participants, and the clear need for humour, it seems that the faith community is missing an opportunity to understand humour and support those with dementia by making use of it.

Why humour is not studied more in relation to theology and faith is contested. Layman (1982) speculates on the history of philosophy, going back to Plato and Aristotle, and argues that there has been a collective understanding that “tragedy” has a more noble role in the human condition, and this understanding has trickled down through Christian theology and history, culminating in the existential theories of anxiety and despair in the 20th century. On the other side there have always been Christians who considered the role and nature of humour. According to Chesterton (2006, p.155), “There was some one thing that was too great for God to show us when He walked upon the earth; and I have sometimes fancied that it was His mirth.” Layman (1982) discusses humour as an aspect of God’s quality of mercy. Elizabeth’s insistence that “we don’t need soppy, we need comedy” can be seen as a call for

God's love and mercy to be shown by the use of humour from her nurses, nuns, and priests.

An interesting study would entail knowing if (and how much) guidance nuns, priests, and ministers receive on the use of humour with those they are serving.

Fred Layman (1982) also explores Biblical Passages that show humour as an aspect of God's nature or as important to the spiritual journey. For example, he notes three passages in the Psalms (2:4, 37:13, 59:8) that have God laughing. In all 3 passages His laugh is actually one "...of derision at the comic pretensions of the nations which exalt themselves against Him," (Layman, 1982, p. 9). God almost seems to be laughing at those who think they can control life. Those with a diagnosis of dementia are in a constant process of letting go of control, and this itself can possibly be a source of laughter. The use of these Bible passages can be especially important to my participants who are from various Protestant denominations, where the Bible is given great prominence in how one understands God's nature.

There are also positive examples of laughter and humour in the Bible. Humour and playfulness can be seen in the Old Testament. In Psalm 104:26 It is implied that God made the sea creature to play with it. The book of Job lists a series of things which are possible for God but not possible for Job and implies that God plays with crocodiles (Job 41). Proverbs 8:31 speaks of wisdom as "God's craftsmen in the creation, delighting God and playing before Him all the while, playing on the surface of His earth".

Fred Layman (1982) also discusses laughter as a source of joy. Sarah first laughs out of unbelief, but that sentiment is later replaced by a laughter of joy when her promised son is born. As she explained, "God has brought me laughter, and everyone who hears about this will laugh with me" (Genesis 21:6). Job 8:21 says "He will yet fill your mouth with laughter and your lips with shouts of joy." A verse within the book of Psalms states "When the LORD restored the fortunes of Zion, we were like those who dreamed. Our mouths were

filled with laughter, our tongues with songs of joy. Then it was said among the nations,
The LORD has done great things for them” (Psalms 126:1-2).

This sense of playfulness was apparent with all 8 of my participants. While there was clearly a sense of pathos – humour used to speak of sad situations in a manner that possibly showed the sadness through humour – there was also a real sense of the use of humour bringing joy.

Re-watching the videos of my Zoom interviews, and focusing on the eyes of my participants, I saw a high level of joy emerging, and noted the frequent sound of laughter.

Humour and playfulness also make an appearance in the New Testament. Jerry Gill notes humour in the New Testament in the communication of Jesus. According to Gill (1950, p.139)

Jesus frequently answers questions with his own question, uses puns and interacts using “off beat”, seemingly irrelevant and non-verbal behaviour. It is important that the context and content of his remarks are read with a sense of humour. If not read this way, his interactions could come across as evasive, rude or offensive – both to the hearer and to the reader.

Father James Martin has written a book called “Between Heaven and Mirth” exploring the role of humour and laughter in religious faith. According to Father Martin (2012, p.2-17), Holy people are joyful because God is the source of all joy and being holy brings us closer to God. Sigmund Freud believed that some joy and humour stem from the unconscious, the level below our rational faculties. The French philosopher Henri Bergson (1900, 2009; p. 1) in his essay ‘Laughter’ notes, “Comic absurdity is of the same nature as that of dreams.”

It has been noted that “The act of laughing comes in response to something humorous or, as above, ‘absurdly incongruous”” (Martin, 2012, p.18). This point is relevant to those living with dementia. The incongruity of, for example, Charlotte stating to me “I’m really 20 years old” when she is actually 96 produced a feeling of mirth in her and allowed me to empathise with the feelings she might have of sometimes indeed wishing she *were* 20. Humour can be

used in a non-threatening way to express a “truth” that might otherwise be hard to express.

Richard joked about not yet being at the stage where his wife seems like a new woman every morning – but I wonder how much of this “joke” was masking a fear or expressing a fear in a positive way.

The Catholic Catechism itself addresses humour. Section 1676 states “At the core of the faith of believers there is a “storehouse of values” that offers wisdom for the Christian life. Such wisdom provides reasons for joy and humour even in the midst of a very hard life”. (Catholic Catechism). The Catechism discusses the “wisdom of the people” (the full community of believers) encouraging and teaching joy and humour in difficulties.

This focus on the wider Christian community is key, as humour can be seen as a relational event, and certainly the wider Christian community can be encouraged to make use of humour as a spiritual resource. My participants, while discussing the importance of their faith, embedded humour within that discussion, showing that as opposed to always being a serious endeavour, faith and humour can be linked to spread joy.

5.5.1 Humour as Protest

In *Laughter: A Theological Reflection*, Karl Josef Kuschel (2012) mentions a little known Catholic tradition - “*risus paschalis*” - the Easter Laugh. This concept struck me as a very powerful one that can be used in our understanding of laughter and dementia. The Easter Laugh is an ancient tradition in which priests would make jokes (sometimes extreme jokes), and those coming to Mass would dress up in funny costumes and do all they could to spend the day in reckless laughter. The idea behind the Easter Laugh was that Easter was seen as a time to make fun of the devil – to scoff at him – and show him how all his evil plans had gone awry with the rising of Jesus.

The power in the Easter Laugh is what struck me, especially as I have been ruminating on the sheer power of humour in my participants’ lives. While none of them framed their laughter

around the term “protest” – there definitely feels to be an implicit sense of protest in the desire and ability to use humour in the face of a dementia diagnosis. I think there is a case to be made that we in the Christian world can actively re-claim humour in the way it was used in the Middle Ages, to help people “mock” their own decline. There was a sense of Charlotte mocking her age in her proclamation “I am really 20 years old”.

Attention has been given to the Easter Laugh in current time, as the following from Pope Benedict XVI indicates. According to Pope Benedict XVI (*Easter Laughter*, no date):

In the Baroque period the liturgy used to include the risus paschalis, the Easter laughter. The Easter homily had to contain a story that made people laugh, so that the church resounded with a joyful laughter. That may be a somewhat superficial form of Christian joy. But is there not something very beautiful and appropriate about laughter becoming a liturgical symbol? And is it not a tonic when we still hear, in the play of cherub and ornament in Baroque churches, that laughter which testified to the freedom of the redeemed? And is it not a sign of an Easter faith when Haydn remarked, concerning his church compositions, that he felt a particular joy when thinking of God: “As I came to utter the words of supplication, I could not suppress my joy but loosed the reins of my elated spirits and wrote ‘allegro’ over the Miserere, and so on?”

Reinhold Niebuhr (2013) has also written on the role of laughter in our faith. “Humour is, in fact, a prelude to faith; and laughter is the beginning of prayer... The intimate relation between humour and faith is derived from the fact that both deal with the incongruities of our existence... Laughter is our reaction to immediate incongruities and those which do not affect us essentially. Faith is the only possible response to the ultimate incongruities of existence, which threaten the very meaning of our life,” (p.111-112). It is the phrase “incongruities of our existence” that resonates with the way my participants communicated and their use of humour. In Andrew’s statement of “*She* [emphasis added] only has 1 name” - referring to the fact that he is called both **Henry** and Andrew, and can not remember why – there was a sense

of turning the conversation to his wife and the incongruity of her 1 name compared to his 2 – and the humour inherent in the person who “has” the 2 names not being able to remember why.

Richard, poignantly stated to me “I’m not at the point of waking up and saying 'who are you' to my wife – mind you that might be quite exciting” and he joked about waking up to a beautiful woman...his wife...and discovering her anew. This was a very meaningful joke, because there is something very sad about the thought of Richard not recognizing his wife, and the incongruity of his deep knowledge of his wife, and their very close connection through this journey, and yet anticipating a time where this connection might seem lost.

Richard was able to lighten the statement about a coming time when he might not know his wife by making a humorous comment about re-discovering her a-new – in that one statement using humour as well to compliment his wife. When considering humour as the “prelude to faith” as posited by Niebuhr (2013) we can perhaps see Richard’s use of humour as confirming his faith that “even if and when” the worst happens – and he forgets his wife – there is still joy to be found.

5.6 Cross Participant Theme – Counter Cultural Stories – the faith stories that help me

Unsurprisingly, Bible stories feature in the lives of my participants, as well as other stories that speak to their faith. It is evident that my participants rely strongly on both the uplifting stories in the Bible and those stories that show the nature of suffering. Significantly, many of the stories relied on are counter-cultural and show how the Christian faith involves an acceptance of decline and suffering.

5.6.1 The Counter Cultural story of “I Am Healed”

Peter’s insistence that “he is healed” is very compelling. “I have Alzheimer’s, but I am healed.” The stories of Biblical healing in the Bible have been claimed by Peter, who uses

them to reinforce his core belief that God has healed him – even in spite of his diagnosis. It is certainly a jolt to hear the conviction he stated this with – there was no ambiguity.

While Churches of all denominations certainly tell the healing Biblical stories – I think there is certainly a call for them to make explicit how the counter-story of healing can be claimed. How practitioners can encourage people to think in terms of telling the counter stories of their illness is an important area of study.

John Swinton (2012) writes about counter stories in his book *Dementia: Living in the Memory of God*. He states “...the primary counter-story is the story of the gospel” (p.25). He discusses the need to re-frame whole ideas in order to truly claim the counter-cultural story. The story that needs to be countered and reconfigured is the story of dementia as simply a neurological problem that leads to an inability to function and the story that there is something “defective” in who someone with dementia is.

Jonas-Simpson et al (2012) conducted a study involving having health care professionals go through a phenomenological shift in their thinking, helping them to create a different story about their patients. After watching a play called “I Am Still Here” many reported a shift in their thinking regarding issues such as hope vs despair, and what it means to be human. It is interesting to note how the experience of watching a play made a shift in a way that (possibly) reading a research paper might not. “Researched-based dramas suggest favourable impact on healthcare professional practices and require further exploration as a pedagogical tool and medium for knowledge mobilisation” (p.1952). It is a pedagogical tool not seen in social work education and certainly not seen from a faith-based perspective in social work education. I have long believed that those in social work education need to make more use of literature, films, plays and poetry, and we could do this to try and help our students “tell a different story”.

Post (1995, p. 26) proposed “What pictures shall we draw of the person with dementia? No ethical question is more basic than this.” Drawing these “pictures” in our minds and our psyches can impact how we approach those with dementia and those with dementia who hold their faith closely. Nolan (2004) makes a call to move beyond psycho-sociological approaches in how practitioners interact with those with dementia. It is clear that techniques such as research-based dramas could remove us from the common psycho-sociological approaches and help us form an understanding of the counter stories. As stated by Peter - "I am healed" - he is a child of Christ and therefore healed. It is important to understand the impact of this faith story as a source of deep sustenance to Peter.

5.6.2 The Counter Story of Carrying Our Cross

Richard did not use the word “story” explicitly but discussed the “principles of Christ’s life” and that these principles teach that “you are not excluded from the ills of life”. One of the over- arching themes of the Gospels is the call for believers to “carry our cross” (Luke 14:27). This is an exceptionally counter-cultural message, in a society that values ease, happiness, and self fulfilment. Yet it is not clear that those involved in the Church, or those in the social work profession, fully embrace this counter cultural story.

The paradox of the Christian faith has shown itself in the course of my research. Above I wrote of the counter-cultural story of “I am healed”. Here I am discussing the counter cultural story of “carrying one’s cross”. In a phenomenological study paradoxes (and seeming paradoxes) naturally emerge. It is possible that both “being healed” and “carrying one’s cross” are actually two sides of the same coin, representing the reality of what it is like to be a human being.

Bible stories are full of this paradox of both being healed and carrying one’s cross. The story of Lazarus comes to mind (John 11:38-44). Of all the healing that took place in the Bible, Lazarus was one of the most extraordinary – he was brought back from the dead – the

ultimate healing. And yet he was still a physical human who was going to die again - his fragility and inherent decline had not changed. This powerful story has relevance for Peter's references to the Biblical stories of Jesus saying "your faith has healed you" (Matthew 9:22) and claiming to be "healed" himself in that way – while still having the illness.

5.6.3 The Counter Stories of Service and Sacrifice

Mark wrote explicitly about the Biblical stories that have influenced him on his journey and throughout his life. These are stories of compassion, welcome and care. He ends with mentioning Jesus's crucifixion and the fact that "love entails service *and* [emphasis added] sacrifice". Again, this is telling a counter story. Sacrifice is no longer popular - the idea of an innocent dying in the place of others is mystifying. Sacrifice (of a lesser sort) is much needed both from those caring for those with dementia, and those who have had a dementia diagnosis. Yet, if linked to the suffering of Jesus on the Cross – there can be an acknowledgement that while their suffering is "real" it is also "redeemed". This counter story is related closely to *I Am Healed and Carrying One's Cross*.

Mark speaks paradoxically about suffering - he notes "I have a choice of loving myself and others or suffering. I choose to show love and joy and getting by the best we can". This statement implies that choosing to love can overcome suffering - or at least help one live with it. The story of Jesus loving the world while He suffered on the cross shines through Mark's way of approaching his dementia. Jesus- and Mark – choose love.

5.6.4 Peter - Hear My Story

Peter's approach to answering my questions was a very narrative approach. He seems to "live in" the stories of his life, and they shape who he is and how he sees his diagnosis. Peter said "I can tell you great stories from the past." He said "I'm going to tell you my story" (before going on to tell a long story about his life that was meant to be the backdrop of him

answering a question) (Appendix 6f: L145). I learned about Peter through the stories of his life.

In my notes written straight after Peter's interview, I wrote: "The details are very important to Peter – he wanted to make sure I understood the context of his life. When I asked Peter about his feelings about his diagnosis he said, "Let me tell you a story" and then went on to describe the details of the day he realised something was "not right". Peter's ability to communicate with such a level of detail made me able to picture the day in my mind – I could "see" Peter in his garden, I could "see him" approaching his wife in distress, saying to her he "forgot what he was in the garden for".

Peter's storytelling emerged for me as a cry for how important it was for him to "be heard". "Being Heard" is a Biblical theme, embedded in many Bible stories. David, in the Old Testament, learns to listen and re-listen to God's voice. He speaks of David 'humbly' listening again (1 Samuel 23:1-5). David was a 'cautious listener' (1 Samuel 23:14-23), Richard listened when he "saw the circumstances around him" (1 Samuel).

The Bible implicitly and explicitly discusses the importance of listening throughout both the Testaments. Jesus spoke in stories and parables, often using stories to express a wider meaning such as the stories of the Prodigal Son, the Good Samaritan, and the Late-coming Workers (Luke,15:11-32; Luke 10:25-37; Matthew 20:1-6). The Prodigal Son teaches forgiveness, the Good Samaritan teaches love of neighbour, the Late Worker teaches mercy over justice. Jesus used parables as a way to "be heard" in a deeper way than direct commands. Peter's focus on story emerged as a powerful reminder to consciously consider how we "hear" those with dementia, and how they can use their own stories to offer an understanding of their faith and dementia journey, such as Jesus used stories to be understood.

Draper et al (2015) discuss the phenomenology of the story and encourage listeners of a story to become a part of that story - to try and be, even for a moment, a character in it. Draper's discussion of the bodily way we all get embedded in others' stories is helpful - his example is how when we explain how we hit our thumb with a hammer, someone else's body will shudder - this someone else has entered the story. When thinking about the stories told by my participants - for example, Andrew ringing the bell when he was 12 to herald in the worshippers and Veronica's story of her mother's spirit coming to her, after her mother's death - I began to envision what it would have been like to be part of those stories. I imagined being a parishioner watching a 12-year-old Andrew joyously ring the bell, his body moving in time to the bell. Even "living in" this story for a few minutes helps me understand Andrew as a "body in this world", and consider the various stages of his physical life, from childhood, into young adulthood, and now into older age. The whole of Andrew has come alive for me in a way that it might not have, had I only listened to his words in a less engaged way. It is this type of relationship I would encourage both social workers and faith-based workers to engage in with those they are seeking to support.

5.7 Conclusion

Chapter 5 has developed each cross-participant theme in relation to academic theory and theology. In Chapter 5 I have shown how the experience of my participants – such as the need to be seen, the need to be approached, the need to embed their lives with humour and joy – can be discussed and understood in relation to theoretical constructs. Building understanding based on theory will now lead into Chapter 6 and a full discussion of the ways given professions – social work, social work educators, and faith-based positions – can use my findings and relevant theory to better support those with dementia.

Chapter 6

Implications for Professional Practice and Conclusion

6.1 Introduction

The Professional Doctorate seeks to develop professional practice. In exploring the Impact of holding Faith when diagnosed with dementia, my goal has been to understand my participants and their stories, to help them feel heard and valued, to contribute to the knowledge base surrounding the areas of faith and dementia and, ultimately, to develop social work and faith-based practice.

The impact of holding a strong Christian faith on the dementia journey has been shown by my participants to be one of comfort, support, and love, coming through God's constant presence and coming through the self-sacrificial love and support of others. How this transcends into professional practice will now be discussed. Recommendations will relate to the findings, showing how taking the themes that emerged seriously can help professionals understand the role of faith in the lives of those they serve and encouraging them to be open to the use of faith in professional practice. I will address the faith-based professionals and Churches first, and then look at the social work education field.

6.2 Churches and Faith-based Workers: Recommendations

6.2.1 *Embrace embodiment*

The theme of "see me – I am not lost" emerged prominently for all of my participants. There are Biblical stories that can be embraced by the faith community when working with those diagnosed with dementia who hold the Christian faith that speak to this theme. The Bible offers a plethora of stories that locate faith and worship "in" the body and it is suggested that all in the faith community can be taught to make more use of these stories in their understanding of what it means to be a person.

During His time of ministry, Mary of Bethany sat at Jesus's feet and anointed them with oils and perfume (Matthew 26:6-13). Mary (mother of Jesus), Mary Magdalene and John the Evangelist "came to" Jesus on the Cross, such as my participants speak of people "coming to them" – they "saw" Jesus. Thomas, an apostle, put his fingers in Jesus's wounds after his resurrection (John 20:20-31). These are well known stories for people of faith and need to be revived to help our understanding of how to see the person with dementia. If these stories can be harnessed, it might give our faith communities the space to truly embrace and connect with people with dementia.

In "An Embodied Faith" Meg Braukmann (2011) makes an impassioned plea for our churches to embrace embodiment. Braukmann rightfully points to the Biblical stories that stress the role of the body in worship. She notes that at the beginning of the gospel of John, it is stated "And the Word became flesh and made his dwelling among us" (John 1:14) and that at the root of Christian theology is the incarnation of God into physical human form. She references the story of Thomas when Jesus tells him to touch the wounds in his hands and side so that he will believe that Jesus rose from the dead (John 20:27). She writes that "Jesus is a physical body, scarred by his vulnerability and love . . . We are not called the spirit of Christ, but the body" (para. 2). This statement distinguishing between the spirit and the body of Christ is key to our growing understanding of embodiment, as many Christians mistakenly see the body as less worthy than the spirit. Braukmann also notes the role of the body in understanding the vulnerability of the human being. The vulnerability of the body is part of our human nature, but also mirrors the vulnerability of Jesus on the Cross, a powerful notion for those who are declining due to dementia. As Braukmann states (2011, para. 4-5):

The body is not pretty all the time, the body ages, the body bleeds, the body wrinkles and weathers. The body carries wounds that do not heal without scars. To be present to ourselves as bodies is to locate our own fragility, it is a posture of radical vulnerability and humility. It is a call to move past shame, a call to openness, a call to learning what it means to be a body

and embracing this. Tragically, the history of the Church is one of nurturing a dysfunctional relationship with our bodies.

Faith communities need an enhanced understanding of the body and personhood. Christianity is an embodied faith yet, we do not always move beyond the spirit in teaching and approach to consider the body. When there is a mismatch between the Christian understanding of the body as an integral part of our being – and what people are hearing in Church – this might impact how others are seen and treated when they are diagnosed with dementia.

Churches and other faith communities need to consider language used. Statements such as “she is no longer the same person” are tossed around casually, and while these words express a real anguish on the part of family, it also shows a need for a developed understanding of what it might mean to “be the same person”. The language used by our faith communities needs to be reviewed, challenged and improved. While my participants stated that their faith in God and involvement in faith communities are factors that offer comfort and support, this comfort and support is most evident when their bodies, in time and space with embedded memories, are taken seriously.

6.2.2 Integrate humour

My participants demonstrated how using humour assisted them with coping, maintaining a sense of joy, and bolstering their well-being. In the context of faith, there is a rich heritage of joy, laughter and comedy in many Biblical stories to draw on. Providing dementia friendly services is a growing area in worship, and I propose that the use of humour can be integrated in Dementia Friendly Churches in a conscious and explicit manner.

There are different understandings of what constitutes a Dementia Friendly Church. Some churches try to make their regular services more welcoming and supportive of those with dementia. Other churches hold extra services, designed specifically for those with dementia. I had the privilege of attending such a service and observed how it was geared towards those

who were at different stages of dementia, trying to help people as their dementia progressed. It was full of song, short Bible stories, activity such as crafts, and each person with dementia sat next to a carer or a supporter. Conversation during the service was not just expected but welcomed, and the participation and comfort of those in the church service took precedence over any scheduling. We had activities such as “speak with the person next to you about a funny story from the past” and then we would discuss how God featured in the story (or did not). The role of laughter was considered paramount, and there was never a time when laughter was not welcome.

I propose that it would be useful to explore how humour can be consciously included in Dementia Friendly Church services. While exploring the available literature on Dementia Friendly Churches, I found recommendations for building such services. For example, Livability (p.7, no date) states:

.Being a dementia-friendly church is about more than welcoming people with dementia. It also involves making adjustments and adaptations to the places and practices of worship in order to allow people with dementia to continue to participate in the life of the church, however they choose to.

Much of the advice about building Dementia Friendly Churches relates to types of furniture that are helpful, encouraging patience and compassion in other church goers, and supporting caregivers. There is nothing explicitly mentioned about the role of laughter in the literature, though I did find an advertised Dementia Friendly Church Service where the topic was “laughter.” I would propose we can further support those of faith by finding ways to actively integrate humour in services, drawing on the role of humour in the Bible and in the faith-based stories that sustain people. This is an area that needs greater study.

6.3 Social Work Practice and Education: Recommendations

6.3.1 Overcoming Empowerment, Embracing Kenosis – a challenge for Social Work

The Christian faith is one that celebrates the story of Jesus releasing control on the Cross, for the higher purpose of serving all of creation. One theme that emerged with all participants was that of “releasing control” and becoming more dependent on others. It seems self-evident that as one’s body and mind changes and declines, as memory fades, and the ability to perform tasks decrease, there will be an inevitable release of control. Yet, we live in a culture infatuated with individual power and agency (Lamia, 2010; Spencer and Doull, 2015).

The social work profession needs to consider the concept of “letting go” and how to use this concept in an encouraging way with those with dementia. For those in faith-based social work positions this can be a part of the overall message for those with dementia. Issues of control, letting go, and - paradoxically – the control inherent in letting go, can be used in discussion, sermons, and Bible study. Stories of Jesus and his letting go on the Cross can be shared in an explicit way by those in faith-based social work. For those in the secular social work profession and social work education, this likely poses a bigger challenge.

”Letting go” as a value can be framed around the concept of “kenosis”. Kenosis has been a theme discussed at various points in this dissertation, and I propose that by claiming kenosis as a social work value, we can help deconstruct the value of empowerment, and truly offer loving support to those diagnosed with dementia.

Kenosis means “emptying” in Greek and within the context of Christian theology is defined as ‘self-emptying’ (Evans, 2006; Polkinghorne and Welker, 2001). It is the term used theologically to refer to Jesus’s emptying of knowledge, power, and control. What is sometimes forgotten by the secular world (and indeed the non-secular world) is that the Christian story is based on a God who did not use any power to redeem the world, but simply loved the world to point of salvation by self-emptying. This is such a strong concept and one that needs to be explored and restored when working with Christians. If and how we can use this within the secular social work world, however, is contentious.

Brandi Klingerman (2018, para. 1) discusses the Notre Dame Study on the concept of kenosis exploring "...how the concept of kenosis might create a common ground for personal growth, mutual understanding, civil discourse, and productive policy making in today's diverse and polarized society." Yet, despite the attention given by researchers such as Klingerman, this concept is completely absent from social work education, and it is difficult to envision how it can be included in social work education. I believe we need to re-envision our social work value base to make room for kenosis - we need to ask "empowerment" to step aside, and embrace, instead, the "letting go of power."

Dr. Daniel Hinshaw is a leader in the call to embrace the concept of kenosis in the fields of ageing, death, dying and dementia. Hinshaw notes that for the first time in history ageing is the primary source of morbidity, and this comes with a whole host of challenges not seen in previous generations (Hinshaw, 2023). He goes on to discuss the voluntary embracing of kenosis necessary in the current environment where extreme ageing is becoming more common, as well as the involuntary kenosis involved in the ageing process itself. As Hinshaw notes, kenosis has always been a part of all life – but that at this time and place in history, when people live longer than ever, there are barriers to truly embracing the "giving up" embedded into our very natures (Hinshaw, 2023).

Herve Juvin (2010), in his study 'The Coming of The Body' discusses in detail the many alternatives for altering and sanitizing our bodies, trying to deny the ageing process and offering all of us an opportunity to delay the inevitable. Juvin discusses the fact that our bodies remember they are finite, even if our minds do not. My participant Richard seemed to have a grasp of the contradictions between valuing youth and strength and having a mortal body with physical limits. He noted the fact that we are living in a world where physical strength is valued and can be obtained - while also trying to accept the inevitable decline of

the body. As stated by Richard, in discussing how Jesus understood loss as compared to how humans do:

I think this about Jesus - and how He reacts - that was part of His life and the future he was to lead. And there was that acceptance right from the beginning. He knew His purpose (in decline)...we don't...we don't discover that as humans....you think you're gonna be fit and healthy at 99 years of age...and I think that's the big difference...all my life from a very very early age, sports at quite a high level...that's helped to realize you cant be as agile as you used to be, and you can't be mentally.

Richard showed a real sense of the ambiguity involved in thinking we can be “fit and healthy forever” vs realizing we cannot be. His very way of phrasing - going back and forth in his speech, with a lack of clarity - might represent the tension for old older people in our youth obsessed society as they try to embrace a new reality.

The ‘body remembering it is finite’ links very closely to some of the theories of embodiment explored in this dissertation – that our bodies hold much of our memory, and that no matter how much we protest, our bodies will inevitably decline (Juvin, 2010). We must consider how we can help our service users, our parishioners, and each other embrace their limits and mortality in a world so focused on denying it. This thesis argues that the social work profession is doing our ageing population a disservice by over focusing on empowerment, instead of focusing on the (in many cases inevitable) need to let go. If faith is a source of comfort through the inevitable letting go in the ageing process – the social work profession needs to find a way to speak about the letting go in a way that resonates with people of faith and this might entail letting go of the concept of empowerment.

In Hinshaw’s (2023, p.2) book, ‘Thriving In the Face of Mortality – Kenosis and the Mystery of Life’ he states “...mortality is intimately woven into the fabric of our earthly existence from its beginning to its end and that its presence is reflected in a continuous *process* of change unto death – i.e., dying.” If we accept that we are, always in the process of dying and

that the dementia process (for some) is part of this process, we must have the language to support each other through it. We do not currently have the necessary language in the social work profession. We are over invested in the value of empowerment, while not adequately deconstructing the value. We need to acknowledging areas where it is a term that is unhelpful at best and detrimental at worst – and one of these areas is dementia.

Empowerment is a valued and key concept within the field of social work and for many clients is incredibly important, however, this does not necessarily hold true for those diagnosed with dementia (Adams, 2003; Kam, 2020). McLaughlin (2016) states empowerment is now considered a “self-evident good”, [emphasis added] (p.53). While exploring the empowerment literature of social work, I came across two consistent themes. The first involves theories and techniques to help social workers empower others. The second is a critique of empowerment from a political perspective, stating that until the system is changed, we cannot truly empower people (McLaughlin, 2016). No critiques were found challenging the assumption that “gaining power” might not be a value to always be enhanced. It is this idea of empowerment being a “self-evident good” that I am challenging for our service users with a diagnosis of dementia. I am calling for the profession to acknowledge that in certain situations the concept of empowerment might not only not be a self-evident good, but could indeed be harmful, and that an over-focus on empowerment might be preventing an embracing of kenosis. The term empowerment has “become a key objective in the training of professionals of all kinds, particularly the caring professions,” (Humphries, 1996, p.1). This needs to be challenged and considered from various perspectives.

It can be argued that there is something discriminatory in promoting empowerment for people who are mentally and physically declining and will be until an inevitable death. Certainly, the 4 participants I interviewed in care homes are in a process of complete letting go, physically and mentally, and this letting go does not allow for autonomy as their primary

value and purpose in life. If we add the reality of their strong faith in a self-giving, Kenotic God, it seems that relational care and learning to let go might be more helpful values for social workers to embrace.

It has been useful for my critique to consider how those in the social work profession actually define empowerment. It is a term that has multiple definitions but one common element of the definitions explored is the inclusion of “power”, which is at the roots of the word (Adams, 2008; Mclaughlin, 2016; Parsloe, 1996). By focusing the definition on the word power, there is an implication that power is something both desirable and achievable. I would argue that with people diagnosed with dementia, and especially those who hold a faith where voluntary kenosis is celebrated in its founder, this over- focus on empowerment can deny the reality of their lives and their values.

Pinderhughes (1983) has addressed empowerment and defined it within the context of human behaviour as a method to gain power or control over one’s own life. She posits that empowerment is the treatment goal of service users which will provide them with “...the ability and capacity to cope constructively with the forces that undermine and hinder coping, the achievement of some reasonable control over their destiny,” (p.334). This type of definition is common, but it leaves unresolved the problem of what happens when someone *cannot* “gain control over their destiny.”

The value of empowerment has broadened beyond the UK and other western countries and is now held internationally. The International Federation of Social Workers (IFSW) and the International Association of Schools of Social Work (IASSW) approved upon a global definition of social work which states that “Social work is a practice-based profession and an academic discipline that promotes social change and development, social cohesion, and the empowerment and liberation of people,” (IFSW, 2014, para. 2). Kam (2021, p. 330) comments on the “longstanding and wide endorsement” of empowerment in the social work

profession.. Furthermore, the concept of empowerment has become a goal in work with older adults, by default impacting those who have dementia (Thompson and Thompson, 2001; Kam, 2003).

Kam's reflections are relevant in that social work is growing as a global profession and having the IFSW and IASSW endorse the concept of empowerment holds great weight. A concept that is being embraced globally is one that is difficult to dispute, making my reflections that much more controversial. I speculate that the values of relational care and self-giving as opposed to the value of empowerment might be less controversial in parts of the world where autonomy is not considered a self-evident good. The profession would benefit from further research in this area.

Tew's (2006) discussion of professional power and its perhaps unintended consequences feeds into this discussion. According to Tew (p.47), "It can be all too easy to slip from a position of caring 'about' a person who is vulnerable to one of caring 'for' them - which may implicitly construct them as inadequate and needing others to take over the running of their lives." This concern of Tew's, while well-meant, shows clearly that there is almost an inherent dismissiveness of those who have to be "cared for". It is concerning that "caring for" is presented as a concept to be feared. In the field of dementia, being cared for is a natural need as the body and mind declines, and one we need to embrace in the social work field. We should not embrace the ethic that caring for someone implies they are inadequate in any fashion.

While the definitions of empowerment have nuances around their focus – one thing is clear – empowerment has something to do with "power" and "control" and little to do with an out-pouring of care for an individual. There is much critique surrounding whether power and control can be shared, given, or increased, and how poverty and disadvantage in a capitalist society (not to mention a social work profession tied to the state) makes empowerment

challenging and potentially not possible; However nowhere have I seen a critique that perhaps, in certain situations, empowerment is not even desirable. I am arguing that we need to teach students how to work with service users who are in the process of letting go and for those of the Christian faith, to invoke the concept of kenosis by using the stories of kenosis included in the Bible, letting these stories ease their path towards letting go.

It should be acknowledged that my research participants spoke to multiple needs including the need to be empowered and the need to let go. Phenomenology does not require one clear “way of being” even within one human being and to have seemingly contradictory themes emerge is an opportunity to gain a holistic understanding of someone’s lived experience. For most of my participants, their current lived experience is calling out for empowerment, to an extent, but calling far more for help in accepting their decline and depending on others.

Peter is an example of a participant who spoke to this dual-need. He expressed a need for “stability and organisation” to use as a coping technique; the ability to stay organised helps to empower him. He also spoke of his contributions throughout his dementia diagnosis, and I noted “contributions matter” as one of his individual themes. Empowerment still matters, to an extent, but Peter also spoke of the letting go that was necessary in order to live with his dementia. He now has to share the running of his church with his wife. He must accept that in the evenings, he cannot do much more than watch light-hearted gardening shows on television. It has been necessary for community members to take over some tasks as he becomes unable to do so. Being cared for is something that is not necessarily a negative, as Tews implies, but a way of living a meaningful life, too.

Balanced with a need to stay in control, my participants expressed a need for help in letting go. Andrew spoke to the frustration he feels when he gets or feels lost and his frustration at even having dementia. He stated “It frustrates me that I have ‘what’s its called’ and it’s frustrating – I used to know how to get home.” When presented with these types of

statements there is a choice a social worker might have to make about taking an “empowerment approach” or a “kenotic approach.” What a kenotic approach looks like, embedded into the social work curriculum and used by social workers, needs development. I think a full exploration of a model is beyond the scope of this thesis but literature from the hospice movement could be helpful.

Jay McDaniel (2021), an American philosopher and theologian, offers thoughts in relation to Process Theology and the hospice movement. Some of his thoughts might be relevant for helping social workers embrace a kenotic worldview. McDaniel focuses on the primary role of listening to others and living their feelings, without “changing” anything and the creative transformations that can occur when a worker takes this as the primary goal offers points for reflection. If those in social work education, when teaching the context of dementia, started with “relationship and feeling” before starting with “empowerment” it might then lead us on a path to helping ourselves and our clients understand and embrace the value of kenosis. Process Theology is beyond the scope of this thesis - however, given the theme of God’s Innocence and potential for future research, I would encourage readers to explore and consider this topic (Oord, 2015; Whitehead, 1978).

6.3.2 Embodiment and Social Work

In considering how the theme of “see me – I am not lost” can inform our practice, I call for a far greater focus on embodiment in the social work curriculum. The social work curriculum involves a strong base of psychology, sociology, social policy and politics, drawing on borrowed theories (Trevithick, 2008). Social work modules themselves involve communication skills, assessment skills, and understanding need and risk (Trevithick, 2008). Modules are taught which focus on the needs of certain populations, and all social work programmes, at this point, should have some attention to the dementia process and the needs of those diagnosed with dementia (Keating, 2017). What is unclear is if social work students

have sufficient or any education on the themes of embodiment, and how an understanding of embodiment can lead them to better see their service users in the ways they need to be seen. Current academic literature shows an increasing attention to embodiment in social work, but far more attention is needed. According to Tangenberg and Kemp (2002, p.9), “Although social work practice typically is concerned with physical conditions and experiences such as poverty, addiction, and violence, relatively little attention has been given to the body in professional literature. The ‘care and control’ of client bodies, particularly disenfranchised bodies, lies at the heart of social works disciplinary activities”. One can immediately connect this statement to the role of community care social workers in accessing care homes for those with dementia, and the impact of someone having to physically move to a new, unfamiliar location, without embedded body memories.

Social workers could better support such a service user if they had an understanding of the role of body, memories and place. Saleebey (1992, p.112) states that “The social work profession has become, in both theory and practice, disembodied.” He attributes this avoidance of the physical body to social work’s reluctance to be identified with the medical model. Anyone who has been a student in any social work curriculum in the western world has likely learned within the first few months of the problems inherent in the medical model, but it might be argued this has led to an aversion to a focus on the body that has been detrimental.

James Mensch (2009) offers some interesting perspective on how we can speak to students about “bodily memory” and the importance of actually seeing the body. Draper et al (2005) describes Mensch as building upon the phenomenology of Heidegger, Husserl, Merleau-Ponty and Levinas and noting that a significant part of our shared world involves the in-common experience of embodiment. Our bodies, in essence, are a significant part of our shared experience (Mensch, 2009). We discuss person-centered care a great deal in social

work education, but we rarely discuss our connected and shared way of being, and the communal experiences of the body. When we teach students to (rightfully) respect the individual, we might be leaving a whole area of unexplored ways of understanding the real nature of people and relationships, by ignoring the subject of their physical bodies.

Mensch notes that this may seem to be an odd notion to many of our students. Many of our students come from a cultural tradition in which the body is a source of separation - not shared experience (Mensch, 2009). He offers a few examples of embodiment that may help students appreciate a more nuanced understanding of our shared being-in-the-world. He suggests that sharing a graphically vivid story can bring about an empathetic response which then creates a shared moment for the students in the room (Mensch, 2009). There are ways of re-framing our teaching within social work education to help students understand the need for an empathic response and shared moments. Mensch's example of sharing a graphically vivid story can be explored and expanded upon encouraging students to then think about the bodily experiences of those in the ageing process or with physical disabilities. Students can be encouraged to think about their own bodies as well, as they age and change.

6.3.3 Re-thinking the role of faith in social work education

Many of the recommendations discussed have involved a call for the social work profession to include more about faith within its curriculum. As a social work educator of 16 years, and a person of faith, it has not escaped my notice how little attention the area of faith is given in the social work curriculum in Scotland. Faith and dementia are both neglected fields (Frank Keating, 2017). Marty (1980, p.465) has said "the literature of the profession genially and serenely ignores religion." If we are to educate social workers who will be working with our rapidly ageing population, we need to incorporate teaching about dementia and the role of faith in our curriculums. This will require a cultural change and will not be without considerable complexity. The suggestion is not only for a curriculum change that includes

content about various faiths (though that is needed as well) but a whole new openness to the deep impact of faith on human beings, and a commitment to dwell in the world of faith.

The lack of confidence in discussing or downright hostility to faith has been noted in various studies. Some comments by social workers to the role of faith in social work have been downright disheartening. One respondent in a UK study argued that “there is no room for religion or spirituality or cooking tips in social work” (Furman et al., 2004, p.780). Others have reported similar sentiments being widespread (Furness and Gilligan 2010; Whiting, 2008).

The comparing of religion and spirituality to cooking tips might be seen as mocking and call into question whether the respondent can practice the profession in an anti-discriminatory fashion at all. Hodge (2018), however, says that it is becoming more common for social workers to consider religion and belief as integral to the human condition. There is a tension and ambiguity in the current milieu that leaves an opening for curriculum change and practice change.

It is likely that the lack of faith-based education in social work leads to the ambiguous place it has in practice. Panagiotis Pentaris (2023) completed a study titled ‘Integrating Religion and Belief in Social Work Practice: An Exploratory Study.’ First he reviewed existing research and then conducted his own. He explored how social work practitioners integrate service users’ religion, beliefs and spiritual identities. Pentaris used thematic analysis and showed that practitioners employ either “avoidant” or “utilitarian” approaches when it comes to considering faith. According to Pentaris, some practitioners avoid the discussion of faith because they are afraid they will be seen as imposing their views on others.

The avoidant approach is dangerous because of the damage, even unintended, caused by avoiding considerations of faith. The social work profession prides itself on a holistic approach to service users (Campbellsville University, 2019), but if we are not invested as a

profession in attending to people's belief in God, we can hardly claim to be a "holistic profession" and we risk damaging service users. This is especially important with an ageing population as studies have found that belief in God typically increases with age, especially for those older than 68 which remains true across countries (Smith, 2012).

Social work students cannot be expected to understand the lived experience of those with faith if they are not explicitly taught to consider faith, as they are taught to consider race, in social work education. Dementia increases this need. As stated by Sister Karen Kielb (quoted in Elder Care Alliance, 2017, para. 4) "Dementia may seem to mask the need for spirituality, but the reality is that, from my experience, cognitive impairment does not eclipse out innate need as human beings for inner peace, comfort, prayer, and rituals." This need for spirituality, which is "genially ignored", can cause levels of damage we might not perceive.

Similar to the dangers of the avoidant approach are the dangers of the utilitarian approach. Pentaris suggests that the utilitarian response is related to professionals who see religious preference as just another category on an assessment form that should only be addressed when practical issues arise (such as an "older client having dietary needs or restrictions due to their faith"). Ninety-four percent of the participants in the Pentaris study "shared that a way of engaging with religion, belief and spiritual identities of service users is by filling out the right sections on the forms, especially during the initial assessment" (Pentaris, 2023, p.38). According to one participant "well, the secular part of the society says that you can ask it, but it does not really matter, and you tick the box on something and then you think it is addressed," (p.38).

These comments are problematic if they are indicative of social work practice as a whole. When considering the lived experience of my own research participants it could very well be that people of faith have that faith so embedded, they do not actively express to their visiting social workers how important it is. Compounded with the diagnosis of dementia, this very

implicit, accepted, life-ingrained faith might actually have to be drawn out – the comparison I make is we do not talk about breathing, we just breathe. As Charlotte said, “He is with us, whether we like it or not.” Pentaris’s study implies that the “just is” is often not understood by social workers, which can impact their practice with ageing populations and make it difficult for them to discuss it with service users.

Studies since the 1990s have explored how religion and spirituality fit into the social work curriculum but also how students respond to such initiatives. Dudley and Helfgott (1990) were early in the movement to explore the place of religion and spirituality in social work education. In their work with social work faculty members, they found that despite assertions from social work scholars that there is a rightful place for religion in the curriculum, the process of including it is still in its infancy. Sheridan et al. (1994) completed a similar study and found social work faculty members felt ill-equipped to teach content in their courses related to religion and spirituality. Despite the ongoing conversations about the importance of including faith and religion, these topics remain missing from most social work curriculum (Russel, 1998; Sheridan and Hemert, 1999; Furman et al., 2004; Kvarfodt and Herba 2018: Kvaforde, Sheridan and Taylor, 2018).

Furness and Gilligan (2014) have examined the presence or absence of religion and spirituality in conversations in social work practice. They suggest that there is a tendency to avoid discussions about this subject, which is why they encourage agencies to become more pro-active about training their staff to engage appropriately with religion and belief. The need for developing methods of spiritual assessment has been explored by Furness and Gilligan (2010) as well. The authors proposed the Furness/Gilligan Framework for Spiritual Assessment, which they piloted with social work students, and is addressed above.

Many authors have expressed a need for and attempted to separate religion and spirituality. Acknowledging the role of spirituality in social work may seem like a step forward, but it

comes with complexities as well. The recommendations are both positive and challenging. Crisp (2008) and Seinfeld (2012) recommend focusing on spirituality only and using it as an inclusive term, instead of religion. While this approach seems to move the conversation forward, there is worry that it is a way to further marginalize organized religion. Many who define themselves as spiritual have actively left organized religion and hold negative connotations regarding religion (Kitchener, 2018). If social work education opens the door to spirituality, but not religion, it is another way of disregarding the needs of those who define themselves as religious.

6.3.4 Using wonder In social work education: A way forward to understanding faith

There seems to be an ambiguity about the role of faith in social work. A resistance to embracing the role of faith and a slowly growing acknowledgement of its importance seem to exist simultaneously (Crisp, 2017; Dinham, 2018; Holloway and Moss, 2010). This ambiguity opens the door a crack and can be seen as an opportunity. I propose we can recapture a sense of “wonder” in the social work education field that could help in establishing the role of religion. It is possible that social work students, even from a secular perspective, would embrace the concept of wonder, even if they find the idea of organized religion controversial.

Mark Kramer (2020) speaks of the need to reclaim wonder when trying to understand the natural world around us. He states, “A lack of wonder may seem, at first glance, to be an unlikely culprit, but I believe that lack pervades much of our ability to dismiss and disregard the natural world, and much of our yearning to fill some void of meaning that causes us to plow over our (now mostly invisible) surroundings,” (p.1-2). That “lack of wonder” can be seen in the rationalistic, evidence-based social work education embraced in the west, and gives us the ability to dismiss and disregard the world of faith and religion.

Instead of insisting students back up every piece of writing with evidence we might allow them to speculate as to what life might feel like to the other. Kramer (2020, p.iii) defines wonder as “full engagement with something that bewilders you.” The role of religion seems to have become a source of bewilderment for many social work students and social workers, and instead of fighting that bewilderment, I wonder if there is a way to work with students to embrace it.

Students can learn to embrace wonder by being encouraged to engage with ways of being that seem (but are not necessarily) the antithesis of social work. This will involve a level of humility. Friere (1998) emphasises the need for humility. Humility requires courage and respect for others and one’s self. Friere asserts that no one knows everything, but no one is completely ignorant either. If social work students were taught to explore wonder, in the spirit of humility, challenging their very assumptions and “living in the world of the other” - it might eventually lead to an openness to religion and faith which is currently absent.

6.4 Models of Practice moving forwards: Local Authorities, Health and Government

As noted in my introduction, the Government is starting to take an increased interest in the need for faith embedded approaches, and this can impact the field of social work. Hardeep Singh (2023) has addressed the intersection between faith and social care. He discusses the Nishkam Healthcare Trust, a Sikh faith-based organisation in England and explores the ‘Faith New Deal Pilot Fund’ which aims to promote engagement between faith groups, local and national government.

Singh discusses the development of the Faith Compact and the Faith Covenant in the UK. According to Singh a “faith compact” is a set of principles for local and national government to work in partnership with faith groups and communities and is under development. He explains that a “faith covenant” for partnering faith communities with local government exists already but acknowledges that only a small number of local governments have signed

up for this (Singh, 2023). Twenty-four local governments have now signed up for the covenant as of May 2022.

The Faith Covenant is an interesting concept with implications for local government social workers. Developed by the All-Party Parliamentary Group (APPG) for Faith and Society, it is designed to promote partnership and understanding between faith communities and local government authorities, and it encourages working together (Singh, 2023).

The Faith Covenant is built on the principles of respect for faith shown by public services, public consultation with faith communities, freedom of involvement in public debates, and diversifying sources of funding. These principles can be considered somewhat revolutionary in a setting not always seen to be noted for its encouragement of partnership with faith communities. There is resistance to this type of partnership. For example, an independent review conducted by Bloom (2023) titled ‘Does Government do God?’ has stressed the importance of local councils participation with ‘Faith Partnership Charters’ and recommends more high level engagement between religious leaders and government officials. This, however, has faced criticism from Humanists UK (2023, para. 1), with some elements of the report being described as “...out of step with modern Britain, affording religion and religious groups unwarranted special treatment.” With this nuance clearly emerging – both the progression towards the need for more attention to faith – and the push back from prominent and influential groups – we can notice a clear tension that must be engaged with while considering my recommendations.

The openness of the academic setting to discussions of faith will impact how initiatives like the above are embraced (or not) by the new wave of social workers. Having a Faith Covenant involving local authorities will only be effective if those who work in the local authority understand why such a Covenant is needed and invest themselves in the principles. It is encouraging to see these types of developments but it is still incumbent upon those in the

social work academic field to bring these types of initiatives to the forefront of our teaching. It is the people on the ground in local authorities, such as the social workers, who will show whether such developments bear fruit.

6.5 Concluding Thoughts: Phenomenology of Love

If I had to sum up this thesis in terms of approach, learning, and recommendations for both faith-based work and the social work profession I would sum it up as work espousing a Phenomenology of Love.

Jean-Luc Marion (2007) argued that love is the privileged theme of phenomenology.

Heidegger himself believed that love permeates all phenomenological understanding (Heidegger, 1938). The Catholic and personalist theologian Von Hildebrand (1983) believed that one's awareness of his personal existence only comes into being through love. The lives of my participants are intricately intertwined with the love that is brought to them from family, friends, priests, ministers, social workers, nurses and care staff. The faith journeys of my participants are shown to be intricately bound with the way others come to them in "given-ness" and this "given-ness" impacts their well-being on a day to day level. Even in all their diversity, life experiences, and different expressions of faith, all of my participants were clear about how loving relationships are the key to their well-being.

Love, like faith, is not a theme that is discussed often in academic literature and is the "missing word" from much of the academic writing on dementia. Yet included in many of the statements from my participants was a searching for love and connection, a need for loving self-sacrifice on the parts of others, and a need for love to be expressed in bodily ways, by individuals coming to them, saying their names, giving them beauty, and helping them love God through vocal and physical prayer. Embracing of the concept of love by social work educators is a way forward for social work curriculums which can lead to an openness and

understanding that faith and love are inseparable. Within our faith communities, the topic of self-sacrificial love needs to be included in how we talk about and experience our faith. If my participants overwhelmingly expressed the importance of faith on their dementia journey – and a faith expressed through the way others treat them, through their dependence on others, and through stories of love and sacrifice – we need to be able to claim this in the way we work with those diagnosed with dementia.

The embedding of topics of faith and love in the social work curriculum will likely take a lot of “selling”. My hope is that this thesis takes us all one step further in showing why there is a need to re-embrace the basic human need for love and connection, and that these concepts can be taught, discussed, deconstructed and become a core part of social work education in the future. We owe it to our service users, our family members, our friends, and our communities to embrace each other, even in the course of dementia.

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Appendix 1: Information Sheets

a) Information Sheet

Outline of study: I am attempting to study the impact of holding the Christian theologies of hope and suffering, when one is first diagnosed with dementia. I am a doctorate student with the University West of Scotland and have full ethical approval for this study. I am in the process of recruiting participants who have been newly diagnosed with dementia (the past 6 months or so), hold their faith closely, and would feel empowered by the opportunity to discuss how they feel about their diagnosis and their faith.

I can hold interviews by zoom or do them “face to face”. Participants can have a family member or carer with them or choose to be interviewed alone. Because of the sensitive nature of the study, I am aware that interviews might need to be stopped, and the participant’s feelings and wishes during the interview will be at the forefront and respected.

Please see the below information sheet that will be provided to each participant. There is also a “simplified” information sheet, making use of visuals.

I can be contacted on [REDACTED]

Thank you for any assistance.

Tamara Horsburgh

Personal details withheld.

Information Sheet:

Title:

The impact of holding the Christian theologies of hope and suffering when first diagnosed with dementia/an IPA study.

Invitation:

Before you decide to take part in this study, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. I can be contacted if you have any questions or if anything is unclear to you. You do not have to take part in this study. If you do choose to take part in this study, it is important you understand why this study is taking place.

Purpose of the Study:

The purpose of the study is to explore how your faith has impacted your experience of being diagnosed with dementia. This is a sensitive topic, as being diagnosed with any illness can cause many complex feelings. I am interested in finding out if and how the holding of Christian theologies has impacted your experience. I am particularly interested in how you

understand the Christian theologies of hope, suffering, and how these theologies have or have not impacted you upon your diagnosis. My study takes a phenomenological approach, which means I am interested in your “lived experience”.

Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen because you have been recently diagnosed with dementia and you hold Christian theologies of hope, suffering, and the embodiment of Christ.

Do I Have to Take Part?

You do not have to take part. This research project is entirely voluntary. If you do decide to take part, you can withdraw at any time, up to the publication of the study.

What Will Happen to If I Take Part

If you take part, I will interview you for around 1 hour. I will interview you in your own home, or at an agreed, safe location, such as an office at the university. There is a possibility I can interview you as well through use of a video, as many people feel comfortable talking to others through videos, especially during the Corona Virus epidemic. You will have the option to have a friend, family member, or supporter with you. I will ask you to answer questions about your faith journey and your understanding of Christian theology. I will ask you questions about how you have experienced your diagnosis of dementia. I will have less than 10 questions to ask you. The questions will be open-ended and conversational in nature and sound something like: “Tell me about your reaction when diagnosed with dementia.” There are no right or wrong answers to any of my questions.

I will audio tape your answers. The reason I will audio tape your answers is that I will need to replay them, to form a deep understanding of your answers. The audio tapes will only be heard by me and my supervisory team. The tapes will be destroyed at the end of the research study.

Are there any possible disadvantages to taking part in this study?

This study involves sensitive issues. I will be asking you to explore your diagnosis. It is possible you might feel emotional during the interview. If at any time you feel upset and don’t want to answer questions, you have the right to say so, and the right to stop the interview. If at any time I begin to assess that you are getting upset, I might decide to stop the interview. If the interview is stopped, and you want to proceed at a later time, that is possible.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

By taking part in this study, you will get to express your thoughts, feelings, and experiences of your faith and your diagnosis. This can be empowering. You will also get an opportunity to contribute to wider society’s understanding of the role of faith in our life journeys. In my work with older people and with Christian ministers I have the responsibility to help people use their belief systems in positive ways through life transitions. It is possible that by taking part in this study you will have the chance to help me and others in my role do this to a greater degree.

How can I ensure confidentiality?

All information will be identified only by a code, with personal details kept in a locked file, or secure computer, with access only by myself and Yonah Matamba, the Post Graduate Research Coordinator. The only exception to confidentiality is if, through the course of the interviews, I have any reason to believe you are being emotionally, physically, or financially abused. I would then have a responsibility to report this to appropriate authorities.

What will happen to the results of the research project?

I will be basing my doctorate report on the results of my research. I will therefore be writing about the answers you have given me in my final written thesis. It is possible I will also use the research to inform journal articles or presentations at conferences. Your name will never be identified, in my final thesis, in journal articles, or at conferences.

Ethical Review:

This project has been reviewed and approved by the University West of Scotland Ethics Committee

Contact Information: The following contact information can be used by you to reach myself, Tamara (the main researcher), Yonah Motemba (Post Graduate Research Coordinator), or the University Data Protection Officer (for issues concerning the privacy of your data). Please feel free to contact any of us with any questions.

Tamara Horsburgh, Main Researcher

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

–

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

Personal details withheld.

The University Data Protection Officer

dataprotection@uws.ac.uk

b) Simplified Information Sheet

My name is Tamara, and I am hoping to ask you questions.

I am a doctorate researcher at the University of West of Scotland

There will be two different interviews on two different days. Each interview will take about 1 hour. You will be given time and not rushed.

I will ask you questions about how you feel about your diagnosis and about how your faith relates to and impacts your feelings.

You can stop the interview at any time. You can choose to now answer the questions.

If you want to contact
me, you can at:

If you are unhappy you
can contact:
Yonah Motemba

Personal details withheld.

Appendix 2: Preliminary Interview Questions

1. Talk to me about your life. Tell me a bit about your family. Tell me about activities you enjoy.
2. Share with me your thoughts about dementia.
3. Please let me know about the days and weeks after your diagnosis and what your feelings were.
4. Tell me a little bit about your faith.
5. Have you thought about your faith since your diagnosis? What kind of thoughts and feelings have you had?
6. Do you have any favourite Bible stories that help you to understand your diagnosis? Tell me about that.
7. Let's talk about hope. Often in our churches, Ministers and Priests talk about Christian Hope. Do you have any thoughts about hope in relation to your diagnosis?
8. Let's talk about suffering. Our church ministers and priest often talk about suffering. We are asked to "carry our cross" as Christians. Let's discuss how suffering relates to your diagnosis.
9. Is there anything your minister or priest (or others in your church) should understand about your feelings when he or she is trying to support you?

Appendix 3: Adult Support and Protection Protocol

The Adult Support and Protection Protocol is designed to help me keep focused on the well-being of the participant and to guide me if I suspect any abuse or neglect. As all Protocols, a written document cannot take the place of good assessment skills, continuously used during the interview – however, having a Protocol helps to prompt and remind the interviewer (whether as social worker or researcher) how to proceed. The below Protocol is based on the Adult Support and Protection Act (2007) and social work guides that have been consulted.

Signs of physical abuse: black eyes, bruises, welts, scratches.	Ask questions as to the nature of bruises, etc. Enquire as to cause, asking for private time with participants to question alone.	If participant and or carer are unable to answer questions adequately, or indicate that participant has been hurt, report to Adult Social Work team.
Participant expresses that he/she has been sexually abused, using either those words, or expressing they do not like how someone has been touching them.	Offer emotional support by listening to the participant, acknowledging what they are saying, and validate their feelings.	Report to Adult Social Work team.
Participant expresses that someone has been mean to them, yelling at them, making them feel uncomfortable, or noticing a carer/friend/family member yelling at, harassing, or taunting the service user.	Offer emotional support. Listening to the participant, acknowledging what they are saying, and validating their feelings.	Report to Adult Social Work team. If participant reports that he or she is scared to be left at that very moment, report to Emergency Social Work team, and to police.
Participant expresses that they are concerned about their finances and worried someone is taking their money, or reports that they give all of their money away and no longer has money for food or accommodation.	Offer emotional support, listening to the participant, acknowledging what they are saying, and validate their feelings. Question participant further, and also carer if indicated.	If not satisfied with answers, and worried remain about financial abuse, report to Adult Social Work team.

<p>Notice signs of neglect – malnutrition. Participant expresses that he/she feels left alone, doesn't know how they are getting food or cared for.</p>	<p>Offer emotional support, listening to the participant, acknowledging what they are saying, and validate their feelings.</p>	<p>Report to Adult Social Work team and GP.</p>
<p>Participant indicates that he/she has been harming themselves. Participant shows signs of possible self-harm for example, cut marks or severe malnutrition.</p>	<p>Ask questions (guided by social work assessment tools). Offer emotional support, listening to the participant, acknowledging what they are saying, and validate their feelings. Ask questions of care, if appropriate.</p>	<p>Report to Adult Social Work team and GP.</p>
<p>Participant expresses that he/she has been sexually abused, using either those words, or expresses they do not like how someone has been touching them.</p>	<p>Offer emotional support, listening to the participant, acknowledging what they are saying and validating their feelings.</p>	<p>Report to Adult Social Work team, and if there is immediate risk, emergency Social work team.</p>

Appendix 4: Committee's Questions and My Responses

a) Adult Protection and Distress Protocol

(I have put 3 of the Committees comments together, that deal with protection of vulnerable participants.)

Title: Please provide details below and how you propose to deal with such issues.

Committee's comments: These are fine principles, but what is lacking here is a discussion of specifics. For example, is there an Adult protection protocol in place for the project? Is there a need for the researcher to undertake Disclosure Scotland checks? How will instances of distress be managed during and after the interviews? More specific information is needed here in order to ascertain ethical soundness.

Title: Please outline how you will mitigate the risks involved with including participants from this group.

Committees Comments: There is no reference in this section to the UWS Code of Ethics and the Framework for ethical conduct in research and scholarship – is there a reason for this? It needs to be more explicit, how the research will be conducted in accordance with UWS's own framework for ethical conduct, either physical or psychological (see UWS Guidelines for Ethical practice in Research and Scholarship?)

Title: Is the study likely to cause any discomfort or distress, either physical or psychological (see UWS Guidelines for Ethical practice in Research and Scholarship)?

Committees Response: Talking about diagnosis within 3 months of receiving it clearly has the potential to cause discomfort and distress. How will this be managed? (see comment above regarding adherence to the Guidelines for Ethical practice in research and Scholarship).

Ensuring research participants not distressed/what to do if distressed:

The ethics committee has asked about what I will do if someone becomes distressed or upset in an interview. This is a vital question, as ethics must be the backbone of all research projects, and as a social worker, protection and empowerment are key values that I hold. I addressed these upon my first submission, but the ethics committee asked for further clarification.

I used the committee's question as an opportunity to further develop what is called in the literature "a distress protocol". Distress protocols are recommended when one is conducting "sensitive research". According to Burke, et al (2009) a feature of sensitive research might research that exacerbates emotional distress. In conducting the distress protocols, Burke et al (2009) were guided by findings and principles: they were guided by the research findings that:

- (a) most participants tolerate research on sensitive subjects well;
- (b) most participants find benefit in participating in research on sensitive topics;

- (c) a small group of participants will experience marked or unexpected distress
- (d) responses that indicate distress do not necessarily imply harm
- (e) although it is rare, there are some participants, especially those who are distressed before participation, who report negative effects from participation.

In creating my protocol 3 broad principles informed it, as suggested by the research and UWS Ethical Guidance – autonomy, beneficence, and justice. These 3 principles are the backbone of ethical practice. The UWS ethical guidelines discuss respect and care as guiding principles for good practice and notes that participants should be protected from physical, psychological, and cultural harm”. In the interests of preventing harm. I have devised the below distress protocol to help guide me in my protection of participants.

It is important to note, that a protocol acts as a guide to help the researcher best deal with situations that arise – it is not meant to be a prescriptive assessment tool. In the field of social work, we note that assessment is ongoing throughout our interviews and very much based on our experience as practitioners. However, the protocol is an important part of our “tool box” in keeping participant safe, and helping inform our next steps.

See the below protocol on the next page, followed by a discussion of Adult Support and protection and an Adult Support and Protection protocol.

Distress Protocol		
<p>The researcher will stay aware throughout all interactions of the well-being of the participant. The researcher will use observation skills and skills related to assessing body language and speech to determine if the participant is showing signs of distress. The following will simply be a guide for the researcher, but not used in a prescriptive fashion as “nothing takes the place of second by second assessment, and response, skills.”</p>		
<p>This interview will be terminated if:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The participant decides to terminate the interview. - The participant decides to participate in the interview at another time or place. 	
<p>The researcher will intervene if the participant is:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Experiencing anxiety or distress during the interview. (The participant should be asked if they would like to take a break and if they wish for the audio recorder to be switched off.) - Continuing to show signs of upset. (The participant will be asked if they would like the interview to end and if they would like the researcher to call someone to spend time 	<p>Follow up questions to be used in these situations: stop the interview, offer support and allow the participant time to regroup, assess mental state The interviewer will ask questions such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -“tell me what thoughts you are having”, -“tell me what you are feeling right now”,

	with them, such as a family member or friend.	- “do you feel you are able to go on about your day”, - “do you feel safe?”
Indications of undo or more extreme distress during interview: Participant indicates they are experiencing a high level of stress or emotional distress, or exhibit behaviours suggestive that the interview is too stressful such as uncontrolled crying, incoherent speech, indications of flashbacks, etc.	- The researcher will remain with the participant until they are calm and composed. The researcher will offer to contact family, friends, or GP. The researcher will not leave the participant alone in a state of extreme distress.	
In the event of assessing the participant has experienced distress, the researcher will, with the participants consent:	- Refer to others if they request. - Gain permission to call them later in the day and/or the following day to ensure they are no longer distressed. Alternatively, the researcher may ask if they would like a family member or other someone from the local community to call them to offer support. - Contact details of useful numbers and support groups will be offered to the participant if they require them.	If the participant refuses support of any kind, and the researcher assesses that the participant is at risk of harm, the researcher will use the Adult Support and Protection protocol to ensure the safety of the participant.

b) Adult Support and Protection Protocol

As a student researcher concerned with the ethics surrounding keeping a participant safe, and as a registered social worker, it is crucial that I appropriately report any suspicion that a vulnerable adult is being harmed. The Adult Support and Protection Act (2007) is “designed to protect those adults who are unable to safeguard their own interests and are at risk of harm because they are affected by:

- Disability
- Mental disorder

- Illness
- Physical or mental infirmity.

I will have a protocol in place to ensure protection if I suspect someone has or is suffering from:

- Physical harm
- Sexual harm
- Psychological harm
- Financial harm
- Neglect
- Discriminatory harm
- Information harm
- Human rights harm
- Institutional harm
- Self- harm

As stated above, this protocol is meant to guide my thinking and actions but cannot substitute for social work skills developed over 25 years of practice.

Please see below protocol followed by a short discussion regarding my disclosure checks.

Signs of physical abuse: black eyes, bruises, welts, scratches.	Ask questions as to the nature of bruises, etc. Enquire as to cause, asking for private time with participants to question alone.	If participant and or carer are unable to answer questions adequately, or indicate that participant has been hurt, report to Adult Social Work team.
Participant expresses that he/she has been sexually abused, using either those words, or expressing they do not like how someone has been touching them.	Offer emotional support by listening to the participant, acknowledging what they are saying, and validate their feelings.	Report to Adult Social Work team.

<p>Participant expresses that someone has been mean to them, yelling at them, making them feel uncomfortable, or noticing a carer/friend/family member yelling at, harassing, or taunting the service user.</p>	<p>Offer emotional support. Listening to the participant, acknowledging what they are saying, and validating their feelings.</p>	<p>Report to Adult Social Work team. If participant reports that he or she is scared to be left at that very moment, report to Emergency Social Work team, and to police.</p>
<p>Participant expresses that they are concerned about their finances and worried someone is taking their money, or reports that they give all of their money away and no longer has money for food or accommodation.</p>	<p>Offer emotional support, listening to the participant, acknowledging what they are saying, and validate their feelings. Question participant further, and also carer if indicated.</p>	<p>If not satisfied with answers, and worried remain about financial abuse, report to Adult Social Work team.</p>
<p>Notice signs of neglect – malnutrition. Participant expresses that he/she feels left alone, doesn't know how they are getting food or cared for.</p>	<p>Offer emotional support, listening to the participant, acknowledging what they are saying, and validate their feelings.</p>	<p>Report to Adult Social Work team and GP.</p>
<p>Participant indicates that he/she has been harming themselves. Participant shows signs of possible self-harm for example, cut marks or severe malnutrition.</p>	<p>Ask questions (guided by social work assessment tools). Offer emotional support, listening to the participant, acknowledging what they are saying, and validate their feelings. Ask questions of care, if appropriate.</p>	<p>Report to Adult Social Work team and GP.</p>
<p>Participant expresses that he/she has been sexually abused, using either those words, or expresses they do not like how someone has been touching them.</p>	<p>Offer emotional support, listening to the participant, acknowledging what they are saying and validating their feelings.</p>	<p>Report to Adult Social Work team, and if there is immediate risk, emergency Social work team.</p>

Disclosure Scotland Checks: The committee asked if there is a need for this. I am the lead researcher and will be interviewing the participants. I have been disclosure checked multiple times and hold my current disclosure for working with vulnerable adults, as per my job as Older Peoples Regional Specialist with the Salvation Army.

c) Assessing Capacity

Title: Please provide details of how you will recruit participants to your study.

Committees Comment: How does the research team propose to assess capacity to consent?

Title: Please provide details of how you will obtain consent and the information you will provide to potential participants to allow them to make an informed choice about whether or not to participate in your research.

Committees Comment: How will you ensure that these materials are presented to participants in cognitively accessible ways? (for example, at particular times of the day when capacity is relatively strong, or in the presence of someone who the person knows and trusts?)

Title: Please provide details of how you will recruit participants to the study.

Committees Comments: The initial months following diagnosis is often a distressing, disorienting, and disruptive time. Why must participants be recruited within this time window (I can't see why that criteria is essential in order to meet the stated aims of the project). If that is to be the case, care is needed in how participants are approached and invited to talk about their experiences.

Assessing Capacity:

The ethics committee asked me to clarify my approach to informed consent, rightly pointing out I seem to be using multiple models, and questioning the need for medical input into capacity. After speaking with my research supervisors, and doing more reading on the subject, I have decided to not seek to get GP input.

I have been guided by the Nuttfield Council on Bioethics (2009), and its statement that a "person's autonomy is found in how they express their sense of self, in their relationships with those important to them, and in their values and preferences". As per all of my research, including the Adults With Incapacity Act (2000) and Guidance, I have started with the principle that the default position is that someone has capacity. The Adults with Incapacity Act (2000) is clear that capacity is task specific, and one is not assumed to not have capacity simply because of a diagnosis of dementia. It can also be noted that 20 western European countries have laws that "assume capacity." However, although there is an assumption of capacity, this must be born out in a basic assessment, confirming that research participants understand material, and can, as the Nuttfield Council said, express their sense of self. (Nuttfield Council, 2009).

I have decided to use a protocol designed particularly for ensuring those with dementia have capacity to understand the nature of study and consent. However, I still plan on using a relational/process consent model "during" the interview to ensure that the participant is protected, safe, and wants the interview to continue. Process consent is not contrary to informed consent but can enhance it.

The protocol I am using was devised by Stirling University, but altered to suit my particular study. I also incorporate concepts from the University of California Brief Assessment of Capacity to Consent Protocol. I have 2 information sheets for potential participants (both attached in appropriate location), one with more detail and one presented in a simpler

manner, and in a visually easy to understand way. Both will be used when using the below protocol.

The ethics committee referred to times of day when research participants newly diagnosed with dementia might be best placed to understand information and indeed answer interview questions. The Scottish Code of Professional Practice for Medical Practitioners emphasises that if a decision can be deferred until a time when a person is going to have sufficient capacity to take it, then it should be. It is noted that people with dementia often have times of day that suit them better for discussion. I will ask both the person being interviewed and their chosen helper/family member if there is a time for me to come and I will adjust my timing based on that.

It is also important to note that the “way” a person is approached and spoken to may in itself affect their capacity or apparent capacity to make a decision. It is increasingly recognised how the use of an infantilizing manner or language – elder speak – actively disempowers older people from involvement in their own care. As a social worker, I am well practiced in conversations with people at various stages of dementia, and am aware of talking simply, while avoiding infantilizing, is key to meaningful communication.

Mental capacity protocol - this is an example of the protocol I will use to assess capacity, when going over the information sheet with the potential participant. This is meant to guide my assessment of the ability of the participant to give informed consent. I devised this with the input of the Stirling University Mental Capacity Protocol, and the University of California Brief Assessment of Capacity to Consent Protocol.

Introductions: (The researcher will be guided by the following, during introductions)

- Is the POTENTIAL PARTICIPANT orientated in time, place and person? In the beginning of the conversation, introducing myself, and having the potential participant introduce him/herself, I will be able to look for signs of orientation to time, place, and person.
- Is the potential participant able to tell their name, where they live, and the month?
- (The researcher should use their discretion here. Even in the early stages of dementia it is possible people may get dates and years wrong, this should not be a ‘test’. The point is to ensure the person is orientated to the here and now, can tell us who they are and more or less the time of year.)

Moving on from Introductions: Give person information about the study, what it is about and what it will involve.

“Do you have any questions you’d like to ask me - anything about being a participant?” ↓

The researcher will go through each part of the information sheet with the potential participant. From the discussion, the researcher will assess:

- Has the person understood the information?
- Is the person able to retain the information?

- Has the person understood the information relevant to their decision whether to participate? Has the person used the information given in deciding whether to take part? Has the person communicated their decision to you on whether or not to take part?
- I will use both information sheets – both the more complex sheet and go through the simpler version. Both versions will be sent to the potential participant ahead of time, as well, to give them the time and space to read, think and understand, as in line with current advice regarding research and those with dementia.

Evidence of the above five points

From the University of California Protocol – the researcher can use the below to questions to guide his/her assessment of capacity and informed consent – the following are examples of the kind of questions that can be asked:

- What is the purpose of the study that was just described to you
- What makes you want to consider participating in this study
- Do you have to be in this study if you do not want to participate
- Please describe any uncomfortableness you might feel with this study
- Please describe some of the benefits of this study

If the person is able to communicate that they want to participate and why, ask them to sign consent form.

Although I will be working with participants who have the ability to understand my questions and engage in discussion, I believe consent is an ongoing process. This is where the concept of process consent comes into it. Although many researchers have wrote about process consent as it relates to those without capacity, I think there are elements which speak to interviews with those WITH capacity. Therefore I will, during the course of the interview, seek to watch their body language, note any distress, note lack of eye contact, change in demeanor, signs of disengagement, and then offer the participant a chance to stop the interview. (see distress protocol). While I will use the above protocol to gain consent at the outset, the entire interview will be conducted in a way so as to ensure the participants wishes are respected.

Why 3 months post diagnosis?

The ethics committee asked why I will seek to interview people 3 months of diagnosis. There are various reasons for this decision. My research goal is to help people express their experience of diagnosis and how their faith has and is impacting the diagnosis. People within 3 months of diagnosis are in the ongoing experience of integrating the news of their diagnoses and relying on their coping and resilience skills. Certainly, as the committee points out, it can be a disruptive and disorienting time. However, we know in times of trauma, many people of faith turn to that faith, and I am trying to explore how that faith has (or hasn't) had an impact on the disruptive nature of the diagnosis. I note the Hannah Aldridge's research which looked at the shame felt upon diagnosis – she successfully interviewed those diagnosed within a month of the diagnosis, focusing on felt shame, which in itself a very emotive topic - .but she, like I ,feel the voices of those newly diagnosed important to capture.

d) General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

Title: Who will have access to the data collected during the study and how will you keep it confidential?

Committee Comment: Data will need to be held in accordance with the GDPR and this needs to be fully considered. Will, for example, participants be able to see transcripts of their interviews? If so, how will they be informed how to access them and what the timeframe will be? How and when will sensitive (un-anonymised) data be destroyed?

In my original submission of the ethics application, I wrote the following:

There are multiple considerations regarding the confidentiality of personal data. I have researched this area and considered the implications of this being qualitative research, done through IPA, and with a small sample. It is acknowledged in the literature that the nature of this type of study is more difficult in terms of confidentiality than a purely quantitative study. (Raymond M Lee, 179) “Qualitative researchers gather textual data which, because it comprises words rather than numbers, cannot be mechanically transformed”.

I believe that confidentiality (along with informed consent) are the keys to an ethical research projects, and I plan to incorporate the following:

- Deletion of names and identifiers
- Restricting access to my data (to myself and the supervisory team)
- Ensuring all conversation about my research, within my community of practice uses codes as opposed to names
- Encryption of all material
- A locked box to hold any hard copy paper-work, with the consent forms in a separate locked box from any other papers.
- Ensuring that participants are clear about the constraints on confidentiality, for example, reporting duties under the Adult Support and Protection Act.

The committee asked that GDPR be further addressed, particularly in my information sheet, which is appropriate. This led me to go back and review the GDPR and Data Protection Act of 2018, as well as the UK Policy Framework for Health and Social Care Research, and GDPR and Research – an Overview for Researchers. The reading I did was thorough, and I explored areas such as the lawful basis for processing data, transparency, and the data-subjects’ rights under GDPR. Much of the literature focused on the lawful right for holding personal data full stop, and certainly the most likely lawful basis for processing personal data for researchers in institutes of higher education is that it’s a “task in the public interest.

GDPR for Researchers offers a useful guide/checklist for ensuring that requirements are met – that your sheet include:

- The name and content of our organisation

- The name and contact details of our rep
- The contact details of our data protection officer
- The purposes of processing
- The lawful basis for the processing
- Retention periods
- Rights available
- The right to lodge a complaint
- All information provided in a way that is: concise, transparent, intelligible, easily accessible, using clear and plain language.

In light of the reading I've been doing, I am adding to my information sheet, using the template suggested by University West of Scotland. In addition, I will simplify the GDPR information for my second, simpler, Information Sheet.

My new Information Sheet will be attached to the ethics application – however it now includes the UWS suggested format, altered to reflect my research project:

Data Protection Privacy Notice (please see this as attachment as well, that will be given with the Information Sheet):

- The data controller for this project will be the University of the West of Scotland. (UWS) The UWS Data Protection Office provides oversight of UWS activities involving the processing of personal data and can be contacted at
- UWS's Data Protection Officer is Emma Cockrow and can be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk.
- If you have any concern about how the private information about you is being used, you can contact Emma Cockrow.

Your personal data will be processed (which in this case means kept, stored, or used) so long as it is required for the research project. This means that your name and information such as your diagnosis, GP, and date of birth will be kept, but only for as long as necessary. The only people with access to this information will be myself, my research team, and the organisation that referred you to me. I will keep this information locked up. This information will be destroyed within 6 months of my thesis being complete.

I will anonymise and/or pseudonymise the personal data you provide in my written work. I am writing a thesis regarding the answers to the questions I have asked you, and your name and personal information will not be in this thesis. All information in my final report and in my work towards my thesis will be anonymised. Nobody will know your name except for myself, the people who referred you to me, and my research team. All other places your name will be anonymised.

If you are concerned about how your personal data is being processed, please contact UWS in the first instance at

- dataprotection@uws.ac.uk.

If you remain unsatisfied, you may wish to contact the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO). Contact details, and details of data subject rights, are available on the ICO website at: <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/data-protection-reform/overview-of-the-gdpr/individuals-rights/>

What will happen to the results of the research study?

The results of the study will be presented as a thesis. If it is successful, I will try and publish information about the study in appropriate journals. Your personal details will not be revealed in any publication.

Who has reviewed the study?

The study has been reviewed by the UWS Ethics Committee, to ensure it will be conducted in an ethical fashion that protects your information.

Contact for Further Information:

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Appendix 5: Debrief

Title: Please provide details of when this debriefing will take place, who will do it and how it will be done.

Committee's Comment: But what if they have concerns with how the researcher has facilitated the interview? Are they likely to tell the person that during this conversation? There needs to be access to a neutral third party who participants can call if they have concern about the research.

As noted throughout this application, the well being of research participants needs to remain paramount. As someone who has worked with people who have various diagnoses and vulnerabilities, I am well aware that interviews and questions can bring up feelings that might need expressing. After my interviews take place, I plan to phone the participants interviewed (or their carer, if the participant prefers) within a week of the interview, to follow up on how they are feeling, if they have any questions for me, and if I can offer any resources. I will have left the phone the number to Alzheimer's Scotland with all of my participants and/or their carer, but I do think a follow up phone call, to remind them of possible resources (if needed) and a chance to ask questions is important. I will also offer the research participant and/or their carer a chance for a follow up call after one month. (See above discussion, under dissemination section, regarding dissemination of research results and contact).

The Ethics Committee has asked about the information given to participants about who to phone if they have concerns with how the interviews have taken place, and if they do not want to consult the researcher. This is a very important point. I am giving the phone numbers and email addresses of other members of my research team, as well as the Data Protection Officer of UWS to the participants. This will be on both information sheets - the detailed one, and the simplified version. They will be reminded by me after the interview that they can

contact any of these sources of support at any time, and do not have to inform me that they are doing so.

Appendix 6: Interview Transcripts

a) Mark

1 INTERVIEWER: Talk to me about your life. Tell me a bit about your family. Tell me about
2 activities you enjoy.

3 [Attachment: About my Life]

4 MARK: I was born in Asheville, NC during WWII. The family moved back to Dunn's Rock
5 Community in Transylvania County to a farm which had been in our family's hands since
6 1900. My father was a part-time farmer as well as a cabinet maker. He practiced
7 "sustainable" agriculture before that word became well-known. Mother grew a two-year crop
8 of vegetables each year in case there was a crop failure. It was a depression lesson to be
9 resilient. We always had chickens, a milk cow or two, in addition to the garden. I went to NC
10 State University where I majored in Agriculture/Animal Science and received a Masters in
11 Adult Education. There I met my wife, [redacted], and we birthed two girls,
12 [redacted] and [redacted]. I worked in Kentucky for nine years in community development
13 until we returned home to Transylvania and worked the farm for several years until the school
14 system asked me to take a teaching position at Brevard High School. My life has been
15 influenced by my family, the four of us and the larger extended family. We have had a home
16 full of laughter and we love living on the land I grew up on. We continue to live life with love
17 and purpose, faith and hope. Even as we face hardship in later life, our girls and loved ones
18 around us offer so much to our lives. We live in gratitude.

19 INTERVIEWER: Share with me your thoughts about dementia.

20 MARK: It is a series of black and white events. When I cannot come up with words or
21 express myself or think things through...that is a time of "black". "White" is the time men
22 and women come and share with us in love. It is a time of family in love and support.

23 INTERVIEWER: Please let me know about the days and weeks after your diagnosis and what
24 your feelings were.

25 MARK: I was angry...I had lost my freedom. I thought of dementia as a "Living Death" - a
26 long hanging on the cross for me.

27 INTERVIEWER: Tell me a little bit about your faith.

28 MARK: I try to focus on love and sacrifice as demonstrated by Jesus, both his life and on the
29 cross. I try to keep my faith simple...Faith and Love in Action, not just words. Both of my
30 siblings went into the ministry. I sometimes wondered why I did not. But then I was reminded
31 that I AM IN MINISTRY. We have a lot of contact with people and do a lot of listening.
32 Listening is my ministry. I ask the right questions and respect them in the lives they have
33 chosen. I do not force anyone into my faith. These guys who help me every week...they help
34 me...love me...share with me...a true ministry. The story of Jesus brings realization that
35 sacrifice and love is the job he took on. That is basically what I go by...in my spiritual life.

36 INTERVIEWER: Have you thought about your faith since your diagnosis? What kind of
37 thoughts and feelings have you had?

38 MARK: We are part of a wonderful faith community. I am bonding with more people that
39 have expressed their love for us. I love the way Mel Bringle's hymn expresses the experience
40 of dementia. The hymn's words "When memory fades and recognition falters..." shares what
41 is happening to me. But the last verse expresses my hope: "Within your spirit, goodness lives
42 unfading. The past and future mingle into one. All joys remain, un-shadowed light pervading.
43 No valued deed will ever be undone. Your mind enfolds all finite acts and offerings. Held in
44 your heart, our deathless life is won." Sometimes I think this might be read as "our deathless
45 life is one" - for winning in our faith journey is NOT a competition...It is a community
46 entering a LOVE HOME, even after death. I am also influenced by Lani Leary's book No
47 One Has To Die Alone. For her, the end of life experience is a soul experience before and
48 after death.

49 INTERVIEWER: Do you have any favourite Bible stories that help you to understand your
50 diagnosis? Tell me about that.

51 MARK: The three stories that have influenced me are the Good Samaritan, the Prodigal Son
52 and God in the Garden with Adam and Eve. The Good Samaritan tells me that we have
53 compassion on all people whether they are like us or not. The Prodigal Son speaks to our
54 welcoming home even those who have gone astray as a Father welcomes his children with
55 unconditional love. In the Garden, God asks Adam and Eve...and ALL OF US...to take care
56 of creation, ALL of it...plants and air and water and animals and people alike. All of the
57 stories of Jesus speak to my faith. Faith without action is not true faith. What good is it?
58 Jesus' willingness to be crucified. It's a deeper message there...the message that love entails
59 service AND sacrifice.

60 INTERVIEWER: Let's talk about hope. Often in our churches, Ministers talk about Christian
61 Hope. Do you have any thoughts about hope in relation to your diagnosis?

62 MARK: Hope is in our second reunion, our new life ... Reunion of others who have gone
63 before us and spirits of those we may have never even seen. I'm greatly affected by my view
64 of hope for a meaningful death, as well as life. Again, Lani Leary, our friend and author, has
65 renewed my hope for reunion. I had a glimpse of this when I have been with relatives who
66 have been near death. I also had an experience of my father, many years after his death. I will
67 attach my recollection of that experience called "It's OK."

68 INTERVIEWER: Let's talk about suffering. Our church ministers often talk about suffering.
69 We are asked to "carry our cross" as Christians. Let's discuss how suffering relates to your
70 diagnosis.

71 MARK: Sometimes we create our own suffering. I have a choice of loving myself and others
72 or suffering. I choose to show love and joy and getting by the best we can.

73 INTERVIEWER: Is there anything your minister (or others in your church) should
74 understand about your feelings when he or she is trying to support you?

75 MARK: For people with dementia, you sometimes cannot process information. I have trouble
76 hearing and interpreting conversations at times. I sometimes do not recognize people, even
77 loved ones I've known for many years. And so, when you have dementia, like I do,
78 sometimes people do not "recognize" you and leave you out. I'm talking about recognition as
79 a person who wants to belong but cannot always get the words or thoughts out to share.

80 Many, though, show respect, talk slowly and directly to me. Sometimes they hear me hesitate
 81 and they say, just like my Dad: “That’s OK. It’s OK”. After my father’s death in 1971, I
 82 grieved for years, maybe decades, over the fact that I could not recall a time where I told him
 83 “I love you Dad for all you are and have done for me”. I was so self-centered on starting my
 84 own career and family, I paid little attention to the very ones who made my life possible and
 85 happy. The guilt of my failure as a son hung over me daily as a black cloud. At times, it was
 86 emotionally disabling. As my beloved Momma was dying, I asked her to tell my Dad that I
 87 loved him. Sometime later, after carrying this guilt-laden grief, I was awakened one night
 88 about 2:00 a.m. and saw a faint blue glow at the foot of the bed which I immediately
 89 identified as my Dad’s presence because there was a brief inaudible but simple message that
 90 personified my father, “It’s OK.” There was another presence that emerged immediately from
 91 the core of my soul. It was like a rush of warm wind that flooded me with the language of the
 92 Spirit: healing, forgiveness, reconciliation, affirmation and comfort. I think of it as my own
 93 Pentecost experience which washed me with a new life. It wasn’t a forgettable dream but a
 94 powerful experience of Eternal Love. “It’s OK.” I’m OK. “What Wondrous Love is This”
 95 [redacted], Son of [redacted]

96 INTERVIEWER: Do you find a role for humour in the dementia process?

97 MARK: There is a role. We all have and need to have some humour. Probably every time I
 98 have attended a funeral, it has a little or a lot of humour. My sister Pat’s was full of
 99 humour...exactly what she would want. She was a trickster and everyone she played a joke
 100 on spoke at her service. They were told that they could openly tell about their experience. So
 101 many people got up and told tales. We were all laughing at the memories. It was a recognition
 102 of what Pat was like. Before the service the historic Freedom Bell from Berea College was
 103 tolled, one time for each year of Pat’s life. Pat wanted the bell to “ring her home”. My
 104 daughter and I rang the bell and at the end I cried like a baby. There was a message in each
 105 ring...a message of purpose, of joy, of a life well lived. Pat had been the Baptist Campus
 106 minister for the college. In her papers which were shared with me after her death, she had
 107 files and files of documents marked “HUMOR”. The picture she had on her office wall was
 108 of a laughing Christ. Humour has always been a part of my life. My family tends to be story
 109 tellers and laughing around the supper table or, in old timey days, around the wood stove was
 110 just a part of life each day. Specific to dementia, humour helps us see the bright side of life,
 111 not just the dull side. Most of my memories involve humour...funny things happening and
 112 sharing the stories from old times to present day.

113 [NOTE: Mark then started telling stories about his family and funny memories he has,
 114 including:]

115 MARK: [redacted] with his son-in-law [redacted] talking about the neighbor’s dog and the
 116 possum [you’ll

117 have to ask him to tell you this one]

118 MARK: Aunt Zepha in the nursing home in Sylva playing hide and seek and trying on
 119 different residents’ teeth; and

120 MARK: The preacher at Pat’s church who wore his microphone to the bathroom just before
 121 the church service. The congregation could hear everything as Pat went running down the
 122 hall to tell him his mike was sharing his “activity” with the whole congregation!

b) Richard and Marcy

1 INTERVIEWER: I'll just start Richard - if you want to tell me a little about yourself and
2 background, your spiritual background.

3 RICHARD: I was bought up in church of England. Believe it or not a choir boy in youth with
4 a wrap around my neck, but then you get to an age and go into senior school and there are
5 other interests pursued. When I met Marcy it was an introduction back into church life. Not
6 just being an attendee but it required a response.

7 INTERVIEWER: Yes it requires us to give our heart to God.

8 INTERVIEWER: Tell me a little bit about how you think about dementia and a little about
9 your feelings about getting a diagnosis of dementia. How you see that. No right or wrong.

10 RICHARD: Nothing really spectacular, all my life I've been very fit, I always played
11 different sports, mentally I always pursued things, college, sally army college, continued
12 approach to study. So my mind has been quite active. From an academic point of view and a
13 mental point of view.

14 MARCY: you understand so well that dementia is no respecter of a persons intellect. People
15 we have known personally, so many have it, and people of all types of life.

16 RICHARD: Yea and I think probably you don't realize you got the encroaching issue of
17 dementia – it comes without you realizing it. Its only when you start to be repetitive in asking
18 what you've already asked for.

19 I know there's this old thing about husband not listening to wife [he started laughing
20 here]...there's been a gradual awareness...its no surprise...it doesn't give me any concern.

21 MARCY: I personally from my angle I felt that there was almost a sense of relief – I don't
22 know whether relief is the right word...but when it was confirmed...now we know where we
23 are at....

24 INTERVIEWER: something to work with Marcy – that's right.

25 INTERVIEWER: Talk to me a little bit about how you see your faith in God along with this
26 diagnosis.

27 RICHARD: Its not affected my faith at all. That's still strong. I've realized and accepted that
28 if you have a faith it doesn't exonerate you from all the ills that come with old age at
29 all. You just live with that. It's a totally separate thing for my faith, it doesn't impede my
30 practice of faith.

31 INTERVIEWER: Tell me about your understanding Hope as a Christian and how you feel
32 about having dementia:

33 RICHARD: there's no negative response to that at all. One has to be realistic that as you get
34 older things are not the same. Physically its not the same and mentally its not the same and
35 emotionally, it is something that is all part and parcel. Its not something that has effected me
36 adversely in those areas.

37 MARCY: both of us right from the onset said we have to be positive in this situation. The
38 positivity, which I feel our faith and hope is so much connected with that – we don't know

39 what's down the road, and I'm not interested in hearing about other peoples experiences in
40 that sense. All I know is we live day to day with a positive spirit.

41 RICHARD: you really quickly dispensed with a phrase you started to use "you worry me".
42 It's also an acceptance by those who are close to you, not just your own acceptance. You
43 have to embrace it – if you embrace it you are still in control.

44 INTERVIEWER: When we think about as Christians, Jesus and his suffering and obviously
45 how he suffers for us, have you thought about that at all, its ok if the answers no, but I'm
46 curious.

47 RICHARD: No if I were to give some clear consideration – my faith is totally separate from
48 an accroaching dementia It hasn't diminished it hasn't challenged my faith, in fact it helps me
49 to embrace it, I think what helps is, if you've got a partner who is thinking about the same
50 lines and not saying "oh you worry me"...well laughter, she still says that sometimes. (Marcy
51 - But "I'm getting a lot better") – its one of those things who for the majority of people is
52 much better...you can't stay at 19 all your life.

53 MARCY: in regards to the Lords suffering – if he suffered...should we not be prepared to
54 have our ups and downs and out difficulties and sufferings...if he was prepared to suffer on
55 our behalf, we have to understand that's the going to be inevitable...we never blame God

56 RICHARD: I think this about Jesus and how He reacts that was part of His life and the future
57 he was to lead and there was that acceptance right from the beginning. He knew His
58 purpose...we don't...we don't discover that as humans...you think you're gonna be fit and
59 healthy at 99 years of age...and I think that's the big difference...all my life from a very very
60 early age, sports at quite a high level...that's helped to realize you can't be as agile as you
61 used to be, and you can't be mentally...the difference between those two and emotions are
62 totally different...emotions are influenced by who you live with and those around you...its a
63 strength.

64 MARCY: perhaps it would be right to say we are very fortunate two of our children live
65 nearby they have a strong faith and they are very supportive as out their partners too...so I
66 think spiritually they support us as well....

67 So having that whole group of people, its who you have around you...

68 MARCY: and our Church, our Church family as well, the Salvation Army that we belong to
69 they are all understanding and helpful, lovely people, one of the guys knows I volunteer at the
70 charity shop and he comes and takes Richard for a walk or coffee.....and its good to be with
71 other people....

72 INTERVIEWER: Just a couple more questions...would you say that there are any Bible story
73 that maybe you would use to help comfort yourself, or use to help understand the diagnosis or
74 just impacts you in particular

75 RICHARD: pause.....general response to that is that even the in the early days they were
76 subjected to opposition, to abuse to danger, and they had those human feeling responses to a
77 lot of those things which makes them feel totally genuine in their faith walk as it started and
78 as it grew....I think being a Christian, having a firm belief does not remove you from having
79 doubtful thoughts, it helps you through them...I don't think you become super human as a

80 Christian, that's totally unrealistic in having a Christian faith and Christ taught that...we
 81 don't step out into another plane of living...living out your faith around other people makes it
 82 more realistic and genuine...[GENUINE.....HELPS YOU THROUGH.....REALISTIC]

83 MARCY: prayer mountain, we've been reading this book, and its taking the journey of Elijah
 84 and the rough road he had to thread, and you look at a prophet like Elijah and the times he
 85 had nervous breakdowns hiding in caves etc, here's a man of God used in a dramatic way but
 86 God, and the natural human instincts are there....

87 RICHARD: and I think this was one of the lessons of Christ I think. There is the son of God
 88 and he's subjected to such cruelty and hardships. I think there's a lesson there for all
 89 Christians. The person who thinks they should be beyond all that is missing the true reality of
 90 what it is to live a life of faith. What's the point if you are going to be exonerated of all the
 91 ills, the physical, mental, abuse, misunderstanding. It's a spurious way to look at how you
 92 should be living as Christian. The person who feels the consequences of these things and still
 93 has a faith...that's the genuine faith. [STILL HAS THE FAITH]

94 INTERVIEWER: The Church – Our ministers our officers our priests, the Church
 95 community – Is there anything you'd like to see THEM doing.....

96 RICHARD: you can put us in that bracket! Even though you're retired you still thread that
 97 part. We should demonstrate you're not excluded from the ills of life. They are there for you
 98 to experience. Its one of the principles of Christ's life. Every individual Christian will
 99 approach it differently but the faith is still there. [NOT EXCLUDED FROM ILLS OF LIFE]

100 MARCY: one thing both would say, we really appreciated going to Alis Alzheimer's
 101 training. We've never forgotten the illustration of the book case. Its things like that help you
 102 to understand how people are coping or not coping with memory loss. Some people are a bit
 103 afraid, because they are not sure how they are going react. Lovely people who are struck
 104 down, But we are blessed with our own leaders here at the Corps.

105 RICHARD: following in that analogy of Alis bookcase, if you accept the fact that you don't
 106 want to be put back on the top shelf...accept quite happily coming down a few levels...I
 107 have no problem...I'm quite happy sitting on the bottom shelf...(ACCEPTANCE)

108 MARCY: I don't tell Richard whats happening the next day – its too much information all at
 109 once...those top books don't matter anymore

110 RICHARD: a real helpful positive lesson is not to say "you worry me" -the spouse has to
 111 accept it and embrace it as well. Where there is a repetitive response its so negative and
 112 unhelpful. As if theres something wrong with you that you have been the cause of.

113 [Richard – multiple times – stop saying "you worry me"]

114 MARCY: the person living with it -the spouse, - you are not given any help or understanding,
 115 otherwise you just have to seek it...our only help was Ali...you're reacting cuz the person
 116 you love and have been with all these year suddenly is showing signs of not being the same
 117 person.

118 [Marcy and Tamara discussing need for churches to do more re understanding]

119 RICHARD: we found there are some practical things helpful. I write a lot of things down in
120 my diary, on a daily basis look at my diary and see what is there. There are some practical
121 steps which can be taking which alleviate the concerns. I'm not at the point of waking up and
122 saying who are you – mind you that might be quite exciting...joke re beautiful woman...his
123 wife....discovering her anew. (lots of laughter here).

124 RICHARD: I accept it and I mean folk who got far more severe dementia I'm just starting on
125 that road and its not a problem it's a nice road, an acceptable walk.

126 Also, don't beat yourself about the head, when you're not as capable as you used to be and
127 learned to accept it. It can be quite an enjoyment accepting there are things you don't have to
128 remember. [(get back to this). (ENJOYMENT – NOT HAVING TO REMEMBER)]

129 [SECOND INTERVIEW]

130 RICHARD: My relationship with God doesn't change...its firm...its unaltered in all ways I
131 think we all deserve the right to sit back...to let go. There's nothing Church can do to better
132 support me better. That's my constant, the Church, they are wonderful...an officer, he and his
133 wife are always very communicative....we see each other each week at church or if I am
134 working round the Church, they talk to me, they make an effort to talk to me, they come to
135 me. I love the New Testament. Its about relationships...contact...The Bible doesn't restrict
136 you....it provides you with more open thinking.....some people think faith is restricting but
137 its wide open.....faith is a personal and individual thing....there can be 2 rights....things in
138 life are not always right or wrong. We can live with multiple "rights".

c) Adela

1 INTERVIEWER: Tell me a bit about your life and about your faith – tell me a little bit about
2 you.

3 ADELA: Faith is everything. If I didn't have hope and trust I'd be absolutely desolate. Belief
4 in God helps me – I say “Infinite mercy help me”. I say that all the time. I repeat it. “Infinite
5 mercy - help me.” I say that and I say it. I was a head teacher in a catholic school. I believed
6 in helping all the children. Whatever their ability, if they were good students or struggles. I
7 worked with them all. I'd go into the classroom and work with them, sit at the desk with
8 them. I sat right down. Nobody is beyond help. Nobody.

9 [Adela – at this point – asking if she can say more about her life – I answered of course]

10 ADELA: I had 1 daughter, my son died - If I hadn't had my faith I don't know where I'd
11 be...it was the only thing that could help me. It's the only thing that can help me. He was in
12 an accident. It was so sad. It was so long ago. But my faith keeps me.

13 [Adela started to look very sad and tear up – in line with my protocol and ethical social work
14 practice, I gave her time to express herself and compose herself, and also asked about
15 stopping the interview – she said she wanted to continue. I also asked if she needed me to get
16 the nurses. Adela explained that she always teared up when speaking of her son. She said “I
17 am fine. I am ok. I talk about my son. I'm ok”. She made it very clear she expected to be
18 able to talk about her son, that it was important. I thanked Adela for sharing this with me and
19 acknowledged what a challenging life she has had. She reached for my hand at this point and
20 held my hand. She said she was fine to keep going. We moved on to more questions]

21 INTERVIEWER: How do you feel about your diagnosis? And your relationship with God
22 now? Let's talk about your diagnosis and your feelings about faith.

23 ADELA: I Never feel angry at God I only just ask God to help me...I don't feel angry. He is
24 there and He helps me. It doesn't matter -my diagnosis.

25 INTERVIEWER: Tell me about the Christian virtue of Hope? How do you consider Hope?

26 ADELA: I have a conviction about hope – “absolutely” – I hope – and if the whole world
27 were like that what a happy world we would have. One thing to say - “God I love you, Jesus
28 take me into your kingdom, never abandon me. You're the source of my hope in life”. Keep
29 saying that. I go to Mass every day – It helps me spiritually...I feel close to God...they take
30 me down to Mass. Saint Jude is my favourite saint...the forgotten saint because of his
31 name...they mix up the Judes! I love the Jude mix up. But he's my saint [Adela laughs
32 joyously when she talked about the “mix up”].

33 INTERVIEWER: Tell me what our Priests and Ministers and others do to help with your
34 dementia journey.

35 ADELA: it gives me a great deal of consolation to have a Priest here. And the sisters. It is
36 Helpful to have Priests near to us, talk to us...to come to us, I'm sitting here and they come to
37 me.... I get closer to God as I get older... I'm sorry for those who don't believe...they don't
38 know what they are missing.

d) Elizabeth

1 INTERVIEWER: Tell me a little bit about your faith journey.

2 ELIZABETH: I've always been Catholic. Always.

3 INTERVIEWER: And tell me about your feelings about dementia and your faith. Tell me
4 about your journey. All the different feelings you've had, when you were diagnosed.

5 ELIZABETH: Well, I'm not mad, I'm not angry. Why should I be mad? I've never been mad
6 at God. I love the Magnificat. A ladies Daughter gave me a version of it. I'll tell you what I
7 want – a prayer group. I wish we had a prayer group. A lady of Guadalupe group. This is
8 what would be good for me. This is what I think about, when I think about dementia.

9 INTERVIEWER: I love our Lady of Guadalupe too. Are there other Saints who help you?
10 Saints that you love?

11 ELIZABETH: Oh yes. Saint Theresa. Saint Elizabeth, my name! The saints are comforting.

12 INTERVIEWER: And have you thought about comfort or suffering in relation to your faith
13 and dementia journey?

14 ELIZABETH: Suffering: Oh yes, I don't think we can really avoid it. People should take it.
15 We see a lot of suffering in here. The girls are wonderful. Some of the residents can be not
16 very pleasant. There's a lot of suffering. But the girls who help are so good.

17 INTERVIEWER: Do you think its part of the Cross?

18 ELIZABETH: I haven't thought of it that way.

19 INTERVIEWER: And have you thought about hope in relation to your faith?

20 ELIZABETH: Hope – I think a lot of people don't feel it; don't see it; so many people don't
21 think about anything. They don't see it at all. It would be nice to have a prayer group.

22 INTERVIEWER: What other things are important in terms of people supporting you through
23 the dementia journey?

24 ELIZABETH: Our nurses have a good understanding, they are not all sappy, we don't need
25 sappy we need comedy. We don't need long faces. Come to me, we need funny. Our nuns
26 and priests do a great deal for us with dementia – they give us daffodils. They come to us and
27 give us daffodils. My mother had Alzheimer's and was an alcoholic. She caused a lot of
28 anguish. What I didn't realize is how much it impacted her relationship with my dad. When
29 she died I was glad. She was in a care home. I didn't cry. But you know what my mom came
30 to me. She said she was in a lovely place. She came to me after she died

e) Brother James

1 INTERVIEWER: Tell me a little bit about yourself, about your faith. Tell me about your life
2 and faith.

3 BROTHER JAMES: I was brought up in a Catholic family. Very religious, father very
4 traditional. Didn't talk about it, everything according to the book. Mother thought more
5 deeply. It was just the way it was. From an early age I wanted to be a Marist priest/7 years of
6 age. My father was a good man.

7 INTERVIEWER: I'm interested in "its just the way it was". Have you ever doubted?

8 BROTHER JAMES: Every other day...what kind of question is that? Doubt is there. Faith
9 and doubt.

10 INTERVIEWER: How do you see your faith and God along with your diagnosis? Are you
11 relying on God? Are you Angry at God?

12 BROTHER JAMES: The answer is no. No, I'd be angry with myself rather than God. Its vast
13 or meaningless. I don't know - it is for me what it is.

14 INTERVIEWER: Tell me how your faith helped you or impacted you. – in life or through
15 the dementia journey.

16 BROTHER JAMES: You don't know that it does help, it might actually cause more
17 problems... [jokes, jokes – he said jokes, and starts laughing] ...I don't see faith in that way,
18 as helping me...that's not what faith is.

19 INTERVIEWER: Tell me about faith and suffering.

20 BROTHER JAMES: Suffering is simply "there" – not so sure what Jesus's suffering was. I
21 don't believe half the stuff people think Catholics are about....

22 INTERVIEWER: What about Hope? How do you see Christian hope in relation to your
23 dementia?

24 BROTHER JAMES - Hope – I don't like the word. The word is too structured. For me, in
25 reality - it means there could be NOT hope...if you even use the word.... Hope suggests it
26 might NOT be the case...

27 INTERVIEWER: Let's discuss how the Church can support those with dementia.

28 BROTHER JAMES: The Church should shut its mouth and learn to listen not talk. I object
29 strongly to suffering being a religious thing... Heaven is now – people who are kind and
30 generous...

31 INTERVIEWER: Do you have any Saints that you follow?

32 BROTHER JAMES: Saints...don't know if I believe in saints...|

33 BROTHER JAMES: I can tell you about folks I admire. The persons I admire most wouldn't
34 know what a university is. They are not those types.

35 INTERVIEWER: You have a sense of humour, Tell me about the use of humour on your life
36 or spirituality.

37 BROTHER JAMES: A sense of humour is one way of disregarding questions, not
38 answering.....I have an excellent sense of humour or else I couldn't live.....

39 [SECOND INTERVIEW]

40 [I went to meet BROTHER JAMES again, I reviewed who I was, the purpose of my
41 interview, and discussed consent. This was more of a discussion than an official interview.
42 BROTHER JAMES repeated much of what he told me in the first interview and talked a
43 great deal about his family. I asked him to talk to me about his faith and dementia journey
44 and he said the following]

45 BROTHER JAMES: My dad was a very set Catholic. My mother was more thoughtful. They
46 were pious people. It was a way of being. They were of their world. It wasn't discussed or
47 talked about. My father was a good man. But I was always different. I question. I question. I
48 knew I wanted to be a Marist Brother by age 7. But I've always been more questioning. I am
49 a questioning person. I don't know who God is. I change my mind every day.

50 INTERVIEWER: We talked about hope and suffering and whether you feel angry at God
51 because of dementia.

52 BROTHER JAMES: Angry at God? What's God? What's anger?

53 INTERVIEWER: I like the way you answer a question with a question, lol!

54 BROTHER JAMES: [Laughed and laughed] I like this interview.

f) Peter

1 INTERVIEWER: Tell me a bit about yourself

2 PETER: I graduated in 71 and most of my friends were from the east coast that came out this
3 way, so I have a very close housemate who lives in Poughkeepsie New York.

4 INTERVIEWER: My dad worked in Poughkeepsie my dad worked for IBM, and he was
5 down in your parts.

6 [Peter was interested in my dad's work with IBM and asked a few questions about it.]

7 PETER: let's turn the conversation back to me – I know that's what you need to hear!

8 PETER: For my 70th birthday, I sent out basketball tickets to my five other college
9 housemates and said that we're going to have a basketball reunion back at the place so that
10 was kind of fun.

11 INTERVIEWER: Excellent when was that.

12 PETER: Right before the pandemic.

13 [We had a chat here about the pandemic, in general]

14 PETER: my birthday is March 14 and the following year 2020 I planned a big family party,
15 since I did this reunion - one I wanted to have a family gathering and I have a daughter in law
16 that's at a works at a event Center that's kind of a Bowling alley and an event Center so I
17 planned this big party, and it was on Saturday.

18 PETER: March 13 the day that our governor said no events, no, no.

19 PETER: It was the very first day but we went ahead and did it because it was pre-paid and we
20 had our own private location, and that was really the last time that all of us got together.

21 [Discussion about camera issues – then Peter asked about me and how I was getting on with
22 Lent, and a bit about my faith and its relation to this project. He asked me my motivation for
23 doing a project on faith and dementia. I told him of my background as a social worker, and a
24 Christian, and my interest in how Churches empower (or don't empower) people with
25 dementia.) We then moved on to discussing his life]

26 INTERVIEWER: I understand you're a retired minister.

27 PETER: I am. Well no. I'm not retired. They won't let me retire! (laughter)

28 INTERVIEWER: So you're still a minister.

29 PETER: Yes, part time.

30 INTERVIEWER: Why don't you tell me a little bit about your faith.

31 PETER: I'll give you my quick background.

32 PETER: I was raised as well, Roman Catholic and that's what led me to the University of
33 Dayton - a good Catholic university and all of those kinds of good things - and I've been
34 married twice.

35 PETER: My wife had no desire whatsoever to convert to Catholicism and I felt that it was
36 very important to go to church with my family and I decided to do that - and so I got very
37 active in the United Methodist church.

38 PETER: that's what she was a member of.

39 PETER: And we started attending.

40 PETER: I was a Sunday school teacher for children, I was on the board, I was involved in
41 very many activities - telling people I did most of it out of a sense of guilt for leaving the
42 Catholic Church. [laughs]

43 PETER: Right - so - and when I was about 40 I began struggling, I was in sales and
44 marketing that's where my degree was in and I even lived in Irvington New Jersey, for a
45 couple of years - I was selling computer software that for hospitals that ran on IBM
46 equipment, so I was doing a lot of team selling with IBM.

47 PETER: So I did that, but I felt that there was something more to life than that and to make a
48 long story short, I felt the essence of a call to ministry and went back and began attending
49 seminary as a student pastor in the United Methodist church.

50 PETER: So that's what I did - went through all the process to become ordained elder.

51 PETER: It became difficult – it's very difficult when you take a family who is used to one
52 way of living coming through sales and marketing and those kinds of things to a lower level
53 of income as a student pastor and that was very difficult and It worked for a while, but I knew
54 that this wasn't quite it for me and I needed to take a leave of absence. Are you familiar with
55 Mark Nouwen and I'm sure you are. yeah.

56 [short discussion about Nouwen's work]

57 PETER: So I took a leave of absence from Ministry for about four years and I began working
58 for people with disabilities, I was a home manager and worked for a company that had group
59 homes and all of that, before I began to feel a sense of call to go back into ministry – and then
60 I went through a divorce .Then I felt a sense of need to go back and the United Methodist
61 church - they wanted me to come back. But I wasn't itinerant - you know the Methodist say
62 you're at the discretion of the Bishop you move as you move.

63 PETER: And I just didn't feel that part of it in my heart, so I began to search - a friend
64 introduced me to the United Church of Christ.

65 PETER: And I began to see a call with the United Church of Christ - I found some
66 commonality with them and connected with them and Lo and behold, after going through that
67 long process in 2001 – I became a part of them.

68 PETER: I became the pastor of the United Church South Vienna Ohio and surprisingly - and
69 it is a small community - that was struggling – and struggling churches merged as a
70 federation in 1971.

71 PETER: The United Methodist and United Church of Christ blended together to form that
72 Church - It was a good blending lol. It fit. (laughs here)

73 PETER: I could handle that - yeah and I have been there for 21 years now.

74 PETER: My current wife, she became ordained, and so we are co pastors - and so when I
75 received my diagnosis - and I can talk a little bit about that a little bit later - but I knew at
76 that point, I could not do administrative work, but I still could preach and teach and do that
77 but I needed to step away from a lot of the administrative tasks of the church and so.

78 PETER: Lo and behold, but as a pastor you know - income is tough so from 2007 to 2015 - I
79 supplemented.

80 PETER: For about 10 or 11 years I taught at Urbana University teaching philosophy and
81 religious studies so I'm very ecumenical I've taught world religions and I've done all you
82 know, so I am I consider myself progressive.

83 PETER: I'm pretty progressive when it comes to the religious side of things and the essence
84 of spirituality - I think - I think you and I would get on really well because we seem alike.

85 INTERVIEWER: I'm quite progressive in the sense that I start with the basis that God is
86 abundant in his love and I take it from there, so I might not be as rule oriented as others. I try
87 to understand other people's perspectives, I come from a very multicultural family my mother
88 was from a Muslim family so.

89 INTERVIEWER: yeah I have influences from all over the place - I can really relate to that
90 and the philosophy - I love that you taught philosophy brilliant.

91 PETER: Well, you know it was so funny because my whole background was marketing. And
92 then I'm teaching philosophy.

93 PETER: I taught at a very simple course in the spring, I think it was religion and American
94 history of religion that I taught and the Dean, asked me, she said.

95 PETER: She said "Our philosophy, Professor doesn't like to teach in the summer - Would
96 you mind teaching the summer school Program?"

97 PETER: And I said, well, what is it, and she says "well it's every student has to take it to
98 graduate it's called seminar in personal philosophy."

99 PETER: And, and the book that I had to use was philosophical questions, east and west and it
100 had all of the ancient writings - Confucius at the end -everything was in it.

101 PETER: And I thought oh my God and at the same time, my daughter, who was going to
102 Urbana said dad I gotta graduate next fall and I need to take that seminar and now its
103 personal.

104 PETER: So she said, I need to do philosophy this summer have they asked you, by any
105 chance to teach it.

106 PETER: And I said yeah as a matter of fact, they did, but I don't think I'm qualified to do it
107 and she said oh sign up for it and the students will help you get through it.

108 PETER: All right, I'll do that, so I asked the Dean, I said, what do I have to really do this
109 class and she said I'll tell you do whatever you feel you need to do, but you have to use this
110 book.

111 PETER: So I said Okay, so I thought about it and I sit down with these students are getting
112 ready to graduate I know what I'm going to do.

113 PETER: So I started off the first class and I said I've read this book I've studied it - it's awful
114 so here's what we're going to do, each of you are going to take a chapter in the book and teach
115 it. You're going to do the work.

116 PETER: And you're going to have handouts and you'll have everything that you need and I'm
117 going to honor everything and how that reflects to you because it is philosophy it's how you
118 think.

119 PETER: yeah and I've added - I added a lot of other different things to the course but from
120 that period on I taught that course every semester.

121 INTERVIEWER: I wish I was in that course.

122 PETER: It was great.

123 PETER (changing topics): And one of the things that I came across was a documentary called
124 the ONE. I don't know if you've ever heard of it, it came out right after 911.

125 PETER: And it was an answer to the oneness in the world, and it was interviews by all the
126 different spiritual paths - recognized spiritual leaders of the major and minor religions of the
127 world and it just really opens us up to the understanding that there's just one.

128 PETER: Whatever we call it, its one.

129 INTERVIEWER: I love it oh I'm gonna look that up - I am.

130 PETER: And it ends with Father Keating.

131 PETER: Talking about not the one - but it's really the other and we're all connected.

132 PETER: So that's how I ended up my class with that one

133 INTERVIEWER: love it love it love it love it and Father Keating. I've certainly have friends
134 who followed him quite closely - did he passed away.

135 PETER: Just not too long ago

136 INTERVIEWER: Okay, so interesting so tell me a little bit about your diagnosis, then, and
137 what led up to that and.

138 PETER: I'm going to tell the story.

139 PETER: Back in 2018 the summer of 2018 I was out in the back-yard and I was just doing
140 What I thought was going to be a normal project.

141 PETER: Just something very simple and I couldn't do it, it just - it frustrated me - my blood
142 pressure, went up - my stress level went up everything and I just yelled out "I think I'm
143 losing it and you know - I think I'm losing it."

144 PETER: yeah and My wife came and got me and brought me in and sat me down and calmed
145 me down and said why don't we just let it go for a while and so the next day she approached

146 me and she said “I'd like to have a conversation with you - some people at church friends
147 have noticed some things going on with you.”

148 PETER: You see, prior to this. I had difficulty with words -misplacing and losing things - and
149 so my wife said, “now you've had that frustration with this project, why don't we go talk to
150 your doctor. “

151 PETER: And I have to tell you, I have a wonderful doctor when I first came to Urbana I
152 needed the doctor and that was Back in 1997 and Urbana family practice was welcoming to
153 new doctors.

154 PETER: Dr Richard had just come out of his residency at Toledo Hospital and they were
155 having an open house, so I went to this open house even met him and I said “Would you mind
156 being my doctor” and he said” that's what we're doing this for, and I said “okay fine, so I
157 started going to Dr Davis.”

158 PETER: And, three years after that he said “I'm leaving this practice and I'm opening a new
159 one in new Carlisle Ohio” and I thought “gosh that's 30 miles from where I live. But I'm
160 going.”

161 PETER: I'm just gonna go.”

162 PETER: I'm gonna go and I've been with him, ever since and we went in we had a
163 conversation and he's a very progressive doctor.

164 PETER: And he said “I'll tell you what I've started doing - what is called memory mapping -
165 it's a memory test and I'd like to give you one because maybe there are some things going
166 on.”

167 PETER: So he gave me that memory mapping test and Karen and I went back in 10 days
168 later, to get the results.

169 PETER: And even though it was done as a matter of checking me, I had an appointment
170 scheduled for one o'clock that day, so it made sense.

171 PETER: We went back in and the test was done in his office but it's evaluated by a
172 neurologist - all sent to them, and it came back with the diagnosis, showing me where I had
173 strengths and weaknesses and problems in certain segments of my brain.

174 PETER: And on that piece of paper and it said ‘dementia Alzheimer's stage one’ and I thought
175 “oh you gotta be kidding.”

176 PETER: He said “here's where your issues are and what happens - it gets raised because of
177 the stress level in your life. He discussed stress with me and how it builds on itself.

178 PETER: And he said “that really is a problem - we have to get that managed - and talk about
179 living in the present moment and then I'm going to put you on medication” and then I think it
180 was about a month later, I went in for my quarterly checkup and I said, “are you sure”?

181 PETER: You know. And he said.

182 PETER: “Listen this, this is the way it is and I know you want me to be honest. “|

183 PETER: He said “We're going to work with you and you're the type of person that is open and
184 willing to do whatever is best for your health and not be in denial” and I said “yep that's
185 about it.”

186 PETER: So I didn't know much about Alzheimer's other than the fact that I had members of
187 my congregation dealing with it

188 PETER: And I had their caregivers even dealing with it. And not knowing what to do. There
189 was so much to learn.”

190 PETER: So the first thing I did was Google Alzheimer’s and it came upon the Miami Valley
191 Dayton Area Alzheimer's Association, so I got connected with them and I started attending
192 their workshops, you know, learning all about the warning signs.

193 PETER: Understanding dementia and Alzheimer’s effective communications – I learned all
194 of that.

195 I took a couple of my kids with me to listen to them and Lo and behold, I am now
196 Community Educator for them.

197 INTERVIEWER: Oh, I love that.

198 PETER: I’ve been doing workshops via zoom most of the time.

199 PETER: For all of this because it's easy for me to share my story.

200 INTERVIEWER: yes very, very inspiring as well as you were able to use your skills, you had
201 the skills already from teaching and business. You had your faith and your knowledge and
202 you were able to take it, and now use it in this new forum.

203 PETER: So then. Part of that was to be transparent about it, and one of the first things we did
204 was tell all of the family members, everybody, and it was really interesting to listen to their
205 responses.

206 PETER: Their denials and everything that they all had to say, regarding that and asking
207 questions.

208 INTERVIEWER: We all have human reactions, don’t we.

209 PETER: And then I preached from the pulpit one Sunday.

210 PETER: And I just told the story, here it is, and I talked to our Association Minister for our
211 denomination and he came in and sat down with the congregation and told them, you have a
212 real opportunity here

213 PETER: You know you have a real opportunity to not have this individual hide it, but how
214 can we work through it and it's amazing how our church people have responded in a way that
215 they are doing more than they had before.

216 INTERVIEWER: And all they have to take some responsibility.

217 PETER: All which is interesting, but I’ll tell you it wasn't easy for me, I mean I went through
218 all of the stages of grief and still go through grief in many ways - you're meeting me in the
219 morning.

220 PETER: yeah I'm very good in the morning -and I'm very good in front of people my wife,
221 will give you a totally different story.

222 PETER: There are high stress levels and how I digress throughout the rest of the day, and by
223 nighttime all I'm good for is maybe watching a hallmark movies.

224 INTERVIEWER: And you know something I think you're saying something very important.

225 INTERVIEWER: It's so interesting and it's not easy - and tell me how you feel about God in
226 this.

227 PETER: I sent you a document.

228 PETER: Okay Just today I responded to the email for the zoom and One of the things - I'll
229 tell you one thing – that is in my story.

230 PETER: At the exact same time that I got this diagnosis something happened.

231 PETER: I am not an animal lover.

232 PETER: Right - we've all had dogs in our family, the kids you know, and I not paid much
233 attention to them, but we were sitting with a neighbor just about the same time, as I was
234 having this wondering what's going on before the memory testing.

235 PETER: And then a friend of ours said.

236 PETER: Our children have to get rid of their dog it's getting to be too much for their three
237 children, and I said, well, what is it and they said and she's right here with me it's a black
238 Labrador.

239 PETER: A labradoodle! It's a black labradoodle.

240 PETER: And Ill tell you what I said we'll try it out for a week and, if they can't live without
241 the dog will give it back, and if we can't deal with it. will just give it back no questions asked

242 PETER: So this thought came to us.

243 PETER: In August, I was diagnosed in September came the dog - trained - and my wife said
244 "I'm not dealing with this."

245 PETER: Right - I agreed – she's not dealing with this. So she came and I think probably after
246 the third day we were pretty well attached to the hip so

247 PETER: She gets me up 630 every morning I probably get 10,000 to 12,000 steps a day.

248 INTERVIEWER:: what's her name the doggy.

249 PETER: Oh that's gonna be hard. Listen to this - Her name is DRIGGS. Okay. And the only
250 reason she's named that is Karen and I went to the grand tetons mountains in Wyoming and
251 Idaho and we stayed in a town called Driggs Idaho that we loved and we said, if we
252 laughingly, what are we going to name the dog - as well as much as we love Driggs Idaho -
253 we named him Driggs.

254 PETER: So that that's a God thing.

255 PETER: I really thought that God put that in my path.

256 PETER: I also took a sabbatical

257 PETER: One of the things I wanted to do and just focus on different aspects of my spiritual
258 life and I did, one of the things I did, and I sent you the document was this thing on a book
259 that came to me or didn't come to me I've had it on my shelf for years.

260 PETER: But I pulled it out and decided to do it the "hunger of the heart, a call to spiritual
261 growth, a workbook"

262 PETER: And so I did it and I kind of wrote about it and that's what I sent to you.

263 PETER: it opens up with these words "he who has the why can endure the how"he who
264 knows the why can endure the how.....

265 INTERVIEWER: And so okay.

266 PETER: He who has the why can endure the how.

267 INTERVIEWER: The how I'm writing that down that's a lot.

268 PETER: I sent it to you, so you if you got that word document you should have it there, so.

269 PETER: It had in this workbook these different steps for spiritual growth.

270 PETER: And I realized that I could apply that on how I would deal with this diagnosis and
271 basically God didn't give it to me, I mean I'm a physical human.

272 PETER: With frailties and imperfections.

273 PETER: So God really didn't have anything to do with this in terms of that it's how I choose
274 to deal with this and I came to the conclusion that I am healed I am healed from the disease of
275 having Alzheimer's I am healed. I have it but I am healed.

276 PETER: Yes, but it doesn't need to be the focus of my life. (I AM HEALED).

277 INTERVIEWER: So that is so powerful - healed of the disease of the Alzheimer's - that is
278 really powerful.

279 PETER: And I preach that.

280 PETER: And announced it and, and I see that in many of the miracle teachings of Jesus, you
281 know your faith has healed you now that person may still have whatever it is that they have,
282 but you know it's the choice that we, we can make, and I still work on that constantly.

283 PETER: I work on this.

284 PETER: You know, for my wife in one aspect of it, she said, you know, doing the workshops,
285 with the Alzheimer's association and I get involved with the walks and I'm very busy. She
286 said - for her it's just too much sometimes.

287 INTERVIEWER: Too much.

288 PETER: I don't want to deal with all of that.

289 PETER: And there are moments when I get done that I'm so wiped out, I go now why Why
290 am I doing it - but I do it in the sense that my ministry continues

291 PETER: Yes, no matter what and you know, and I talked about how I cope with it, you know.

292 PETER: I think God has led me throughout my life to prepare me for this

293 PETER: Everyone talks about one of my greatest gifts is being so organized.

294 PETER: Well, I have to be.

295 PETER: Every day, to deal with this.

296 PETER: You know I start off with my lists.

297 PETER: Yes, and if it's what's on my list, I am going to do if it's not on my list it doesn't ever
298 happen or get done.

299 PETER: That's what I do, that's just the way it is.

300 PETER: I need help, remembering - you know what was it that we were watching yesterday
301 or what were we talking about those kinds of things.

302 PETER: But I can tell you great stories from the past.

303 PETER: And that's just and that's just the way it is and yeah

304 INTERVIEWER: Just the way it is and yeah I'm hearing that from a lot of people that within
305 their faith and you know within all the different kinds of Christian faith of people I've talked
306 to a common theme seems to be. "I don't blame God, this is just part of my life as a physical
307 human being and one of the things I'm asking people is, if you see any part of Christ's cross
308 in this - , do you think "I'm suffering Christian suffering" do you think we are called to
309 suffering anyway.

310 PETER: There's this aspect of Christianity - all the joy, you know. And you know - I've
311 thought about that yesterday, when we had the saying. When I sang "the wonder is the cross"
312 and in the blog and you know. I used to sit up there, as the pastor and go - wow - why do we
313 have to sing these songs about death - rock of ages.

314 PETER: And it wouldn't be so bad if they didn't play it so slow. But why the slow, why the
315 suffering?

316 INTERVIEWER: Yes, dismal, dismal.

317 INTERVIEWER: So you're definitely more on the joy and the hopeful side of Christianity,
318 the Christianity of hope, as opposed to the Christianity of suffering.

319 PETER: But you know Peter Peck said, life is difficult.

320 INTERVIEWER: Yes, he did.

321 PETER: there's no doubt about it, and you know it's difficult. I gotta tell you - it's the way it
322 is. Difficult.

323 PETER: There are a number of things over this whole period of time that connected me to
324 assist me through this.

325 PETER: And to be open up, and so my mornings begin with my spiritual practices and I tell
326 people I can't do anything before 930 or 10 o'clock period that's the way it is.

327 PETER: And part of my spiritual practice begins with making coffee and walking the dog -
328 that is all part of it and doing that time but Mark Nouwen has been a great source through his
329 work.

330 PETER: He references Brother Richard out of Australia there's a gratitude network of you
331 familiar with that

332 INTERVIEWER: I'll have to look that up.

333 PETER: yeah and so.

334 PETER: I've got connected with this idea of living in gratitude each day and moving in in
335 that direction.

336 PETER: So, and then there's another group out of Wisconsin called the Living Compass.

337 INTERVIEWER: Oh, I like that I like that name.

338 PETER: And Living Compass their whole focus is on heart mind, soul, and strength.

339 PETER: I mean that that that's it and they put out two wonderful devotionals for Advent and
340 Lent.

341 PETER: The lenten one they just began yesterday that they're doing.

342 PETER: It all ties in with. Change - oh dealing with change. And I know that's part of my
343 most difficult aspect of all of all of this.

344 PETER: The church changing -aging in the congregation - my aging

345 PETER: Constant constant change.

346 PETER: funny enough at the exact same time - I get a devotion from a church in Washington
347 DC -called Church of the savior.

348 PETER: and They send out a quote every Day on my cell phone and it connected and one
349 quote really inspired me to look into the author and the author's name was Jan Linn.,

350 PETER: And wrote back, and I said I might read one of her books, so I got one about a month
351 ago, two months ago, and I was sharing this on Ash Wednesday.

352 PETER: Two months ago I said well you know, every day, every night before I go to bed I lay
353 there and I can recite by memory, the entire serenity prayer.

354 PETER: The whole one.

355 PETER: The whole one, and this person wrote a book on the serenity prayer and so all of a
356 sudden I'm telling folks the serenity prayer book that I'm reading.

357 PETER: Dealing with the living compass advent study that we're doing.

358 PETER: it's all about change, choice, expectations - I guess that's my next step that I need to
359 be be working on.

360 INTERVIEWER: So wow

361 PETER: So, though, that spiritual practices is what gets me through the rest of the day.

362 PETER: It really does.

363 INTERVIEWER: Do you know it's and it's that serenity prayer I discovered the whole thing
364 relatively recently.

365 INTERVIEWER: And I've screenshot it and I have it on my phone because I love it and I
366 think the world has been done a disservice.

367 INTERVIEWER: I only know, in the first few lines.

368 PETER: Well, this is.

369 the book that I'm studying. Living Inside Out – by Jan....hmmm.....last name...Jan Linn.

370 PETER: I think it was written in 1994.

371 PETER: I got used, but you know it's so simple that serenity is the ultimate meaning of life,
372 we should all be striving for that.

373 PETER: And the bottom line is it's a choice

374 PETER: it's our attitude and our actions and that's really the biggest thing that I know that I
375 asked God's help on is I just.

376 PETER: it's it's these frustrating moments that I have you know when I can't find things.

377 PETER: Where the hell, did I leave my cell phone, because if I don't put things exactly the
378 way they should be they will never be found it just increases my stress level.

379 INTERVIEWER: that's the story of my life because I'm not an organized person by nature.

380 INTERVIEWER: I'm not, but it does lead to frustration when you think Okay, this is the 40th
381 pen I'm using today, because every time I put one down I can't find it again.

382 PETER: And for me with this that frustration raises my stress level and it just makes things
383 even worse for me and for my wife so be being organized I have to have everything a certain
384 way with my list to get me through it.

385 INTERVIEWER: So tell me what you think the churches can do to help.

386 PETER: Well it's interesting.

387 PETER: Because I am now on our Conference level From the association to the conference
388 we're working towards becoming. what's called a “differently abled congregation.”

389 INTERVIEWER: Okay, I like that.

390 PETER: And there's a process being welcoming inclusive supportive and engaging with
391 people because that's what I found most difficult for me as a pastor knowing people in my
392 congregations with disabilities.

393 PETER: I might as well just get everything out wait a minute.

394 PETER: So I attended the Miami Valley Association - they had a one day workshop with a
395 guest speaker and it was a chaplain of a nursing home and or Assisted Living facility memory
396 clinic in Richmond.

- 397 PETER: Richmond Virginia and she wrote a book called When Words Fail.
- 398 INTERVIEWER: Right Okay, yes.
- 399 PETER: And, and she also gave me the DVD so I can do workshops for congregations and
400 I've gone to I've gone to a number of our congregations - my cluster group of churches -
401 and just talked about my story, and what we can do as churches to be welcoming to
402 individuals who are differently abled and we are.
- 403 INTERVIEWER: So it's about welcoming it's about being able to open your mind to it, seeing
404 other people.
- 405 PETER: Creating safe places when disruptions occur.
- 406 INTERVIEWER: Yes.
- 407 PETER: You know and doing that, I mean. 15 years ago yeah.
- 408 PETER: A doctor started attending our small church, because he had been in Springfield at a
409 bigger church where his wife and she was beginning to experience dementia. And being
410 disruptive in worship and he needed a safe place.
- 411 PETER: I mean, she used to get up I'd be up there preaching and she do this. She would get
412 up and put her coat on - And I go. - I wouldn't say anything but. finishing up and none of us
413 ever said anything or did anything we just welcomed.
- 414 PETER: and accepted them.
- 415 PETER: And that's what we are to be about - so we're working towards that - being different
416 -really able to really be okay.
- 417 INTERVIEWER: I have one final question for you odd one. And this has come up only
418 because I'm I pick this up and a lot of the people I'm talking to which is wonderful. Tell me
419 about your sense of humour and if you have found your sense of humour to be important.
- 420 INTERVIEWER: A support for you in this process.
- 421 PETER: it's interesting that you ask that question because. When I first went into the
422 ministry. I took what was called clinical pastoral education CP working at a hospital.
- 423 PETER: Being in group dialogue with other.
- 424 PETER: Individuals focusing on yourself for getting ministry and all of that, and one of the
425 things that we had to talk about was some of our dislikes about ourselves, and there were two
426 things that I really didn't care about, that I don't like. One was my humour. And one was my
427 self esteem -low self esteem - and I used humour to mask my feelings, you know haha make
428 everything funny. You know. And then you don't have to deal with. With your issues and so
429 on. We shouldn't mask them. I've worked on that and I've always felt that humour is very
430 important, I mean I always, I think that, at a funeral you need to have that moment of laughter
431 as well.
- 432 PETER: If it's done not at the expense of anybody. You know if it's done in in the right way.
433 So I can joke about this, my wife doesn't like for me to do that too much, but you know but
434 I've had to catch myself, and I think about it in the way that. I sometimes have difficulty

435 with. The words I'm using... Not to downplay it or make fun of it. But to go. Something
436 might happen, and then it can be funny you know. Just the funny situation - Yes, okay, so its
437 funny!.

438 INTERVIEWER: Interesting I might send you, if I find a good article on it.

439 INTERVIEWER: So I read this article about the use of humour what like you said when used
440 appropriately, not to put someone on someone down or or to mask feelings, but sometimes it,
441 it also implies a high sense of maturity and acceptance. When you can almost step back and
442 see the light side. You know okay I didn't choose this whatever it might be that has come on
443 me but there's a way I'm living in it that I can see the light side of it and it takes me to a
444 different plane. And a few people have written about that concept, maybe not so much, even
445 with dementia, but with other illnesses and other things as well, so um yeah it's really
446 fascinating.

447 PETER: You know I can step back and I can laugh about certain situations and go well "you
448 know, I do have memory issues." And the only thing that really bothers me the most is when I
449 talked about this and effective communications workshop is you know, a person, no matter
450 what stage they are in of this dementia. They still have adulthood self respect - we need to
451 maintain that.

452 INTERVIEWER: mm hmm.

453 PETER: don't force things on them like "oh you can remember if you try".

454 INTERVIEWER: yeah.

455 PETER: Well, you can't.

456 INTERVIEWER: Yeah and you're not five years old and you're not in kindergarten and you
457 don't need. To open to like that you're an adult with a lifetime of experiences my own
458 mother had Alzheimer's before she passed away. She passed away about six years ago of
459 unrelated to the Alzheimer's of a brain mannerism. But she was very different she was a very
460 different person from I'd say you you're very open and you face things head on your face
461 things around. My mother was more of the denial type and she would phone me and say Oh,
462 what is this nonsense your father and your siblings are talking about you don't think I have
463 this dimension, do you putting me on the spot, obviously. And it's. You know, do you go the
464 honest truth you try and redirect and with my mother, it was a very sensitive thing, but for me
465 it shows how. People are different people live lives and there was something in her that
466 needed that protection you obviously you're strong you're courageous you're smart not my
467 mother was strong and courageous in other areas of life, but just not not. And yeah it's I
468 suppose it's about that individuality, as well.

469 PETER: yeah yeah that's what I find when I go out and give the workshops and that's why I
470 stress.

471

472 PETER: Early early early diagnosis, if there is an issue just talk to your doctor
473 your doctor is your best source of information in all of this, nobody else talk to your doctor
474 yeah get that get that opinion and I I'm grateful for that doctor.

475 PETER: Can I tell you a couple of the things that really helped me.]

476 PETER: Absolutely also, at the same time, this all happened through one of our UCC
477 seminaries I took.

478 PETER: yeah - It was just a year ago, and when a year ago winter an eight week course
479 called "next steps" via zoom and it was for people who are in the later stages of life, looking
480 at retirement.

481 PETER: or being retired.

482 PETER: Or what are your next steps, going to be and making a plan for those next steps and
483 looking at how you want to live those moments.

484 PETER: And put that plan together and that's kind of what we all had to do as a group and
485 presented to the class and do all that, and that was very special because it was.

486 PETER: How do you look at what you're doing, and maybe do other things that you might
487 not have thought of or do something different, or are doing that, so I pretty much at this point,
488 as I mentioned.

489 PETER: My wife and I because we're co pastors we preach every other Sunday.

490 PETER: So that's easy enough to take two weeks to prepare.

491 PETER: I can prepare - that's great, and I can do all of the worship preparation each Sunday,
492 I enjoy sitting at the computer and preparing the worship service but I'm not going to be the
493 one that's going to print it.

494 PETER: Or get it ready and set up the altar and forget it, I can't do any of that.

495 PETER: yeah so I pretty much have developed a weekly routine for myself.

496 PETER: I'm good for about four hours of activity, a day that's that's about it and involvement
497 and I have a stepdaughter that works with people with disabilities, she

498 PETER: She is kind of a path navigator.

499 PETER: helping them to go out in the workplace, and they have a Job Center where people
500 are learning different skills in the workplace.

501 PETER: And I told her you know back in the 90s, I was working at a group home, maybe
502 there's something I could do with this group of people so on Mondays and Tuesdays I work at
503 the Job Center for four hours and on Mondays I work with six clients and we prepared lunch
504 for the staff.

505 PETER: And the clients and.

506 PETER: Just enough I'm done about one or 230. I'm home done, and then the next day we do
507 baking skills and kitchen skills and that's my Monday and Tuesday and then on Wednesdays,
508 I have a lunch group that comes to the church and we do a Bible study.

509 PETER: that's a great thing.

510 PETER: I leave Thursday's open usually for lunch your medical appointments or whatever, I
511 want to do, and then on Fridays, I have a mixture of like a discussion group with people.

512 PETER: I enjoy community.

513 PETER: and talk if, like, I can, and if we can study and right now it's a group from it's out of
514 our date and peace museum. We were discussing foreign policy.

515 PETER: All every other week.

516 PETER: And.

517 INTERVIEWER: it's a very tense time with policy.

518 INTERVIEWER: policy.

519 PETER: it's just good conversation.

520 PETER: And everybody's respected and it's not it's not faith based so I like that I don't have
521 to.

522 PETER: You know I can say whatever I.

523 PETER: I would like to say I'm not worried about offending anybody in the congregation.

524 INTERVIEWER: Yes, yes.

525 PETER: What we do.

526 PETER: And so, and then you know weekends Saturdays with family and so that kind of a
527 routine is very helpful.

528 PETER: And I think God is just in the midst of all of that really is it's that presence and faith
529 is for me the realization that no matter what happens God is presence, no matter what

530 INTERVIEWER: Do you all, do I needed to hear that today I needed to hear that today so
531 that's beautiful for me.

532 INTERVIEWER: That is, for me, because yeah that sometimes it's so easy to rant and rave
533 and where is God in this and I don't feel him and all that kind of stuff and you know
534 something know, sometimes we feel him, sometimes we don't but he's there.

535 PETER: he's there.

536 PETER: that's right.

537 INTERVIEWER: And if we keep that awareness, then we're able to anything we need to do
538 in that particular situation we know he's there in the backdrop and that's really beautiful.

539 PETER: So what is the Rainbow of hope.

540 INTERVIEWER: So when I started working at the University on that and, in the middle of
541 lockdown I I'm working right now in my attic now we're back on the campus a bit.

542 INTERVIEWER: But at this moment I'm in my attic and a lot of my colleagues were putting
543 different backdrops up, so I just saw that photo and I loved it and I thought, because we're in
544 the middle of covert our students are struggling a lot is going on and I felt like it was.

545 PETER: like that.

546 INTERVIEWER: yeah so that's why that's up there, but if iyou saw the real background to
547 me, you would just see my sloping attic walls.

548 PETER: I'm in my basement.

549 PETER: it's interesting there's a TV show here. That comes out of the BBC. Called escape to
550 the country.

551 INTERVIEWER: Ah yeah.

552 INTERVIEWER: Cross that.

553 PETER: People it's gorgeous by the big mansions crumbling down matches out in the country
554 and its. Beauty Scotland, Wales, I just love that show it's on from four o'clock to seven
555 o'clock.

556 PETER: on weekdays here and, if I can catch one of those those is just so relaxing and you
557 learn so much about that part of the world, and I think it's awesome.

558 INTERVIEWER: I feel very blessed. To feel like I have two homes, sometimes it's a bit
559 disconcerting sometimes it's a little bit where do I belong, who you know who do I belong
560 with, but then I look at the blessing side of it, I love, my home country, I love my family there
561 I love this Country of my husband's family I'm one of these blessed people who has in laws
562 that I adore.

563 INTERVIEWER: My father in law is. He's been telling my kids about his memories of World
564 War Two.

565 PETER: When he was about absolutely.

566 INTERVIEWER: Well 13 watching the bombs, the one part of Scotland, that was bombed
567 tina's family stood on the roof watching Clydebank burn and you know just it feels like
568 history, but for him it's still within his lifetime, and it was embedded and he said something
569 that I think was very important for my children to hear.

570 INTERVIEWER: He said, you know when I was a 12 13 year old boy in the middle of World
571 War Two I hated the Germans, he said I hated them, he said, but then I grew up and I realized
572 that every country in the world has done bad things.

573 INTERVIEWER: I thought all what a good lesson for my children to hear that from their
574 granddad's.

575 PETER: that's wonderful that's that's awesome.

576 PETER: Growing.

577 INTERVIEWER: And I think imagine we all just left instead of judging and condemning and
578 all these young people, I thought, what what a lovely response and that's what he tends to do,
579 he sees a world that's changing rapidly around him.

580 INTERVIEWER: It is yes, no he doesn't quite get it he's not somebody who's on the computer
581 or the Internet or anything he learned he and my mother in law, learn to use to Skype during
582 lockdown and it was like they.

583 INTERVIEWER: They felt so clever my brother in law had written out the instructions for
584 them and stuff but they're people have another time and era, but within that they just handle it
585 so gently. Yes, and that's.

586 PETER: that's what I find in our congregation.

587 PETER: anytime sure.

588 PETER: Wonderful and I can help

589 INTERVIEWER: What I'd like once my finished project is written up I'd like to send it to
590 you.

591 INTERVIEWER: Okay um I may ask your permission, but you can say no I'm going to ask
592 folks who are willing to have their names used I'd like to thank them in my little Thank you
593 section.

594 PETER: I have no problem with that.

595 INTERVIEWER: Okay, some folks might rather remain anonymous and of course that's
596 everyone's choice um and I'm really hoping that once this is done.

597 INTERVIEWER: It can just add that little bit that little bit more knowledge about the ideas
598 what people really think and feel themselves what getting the voice out of people themselves,
599 I think that's important.

600 PETER: I do.

601 INTERVIEWER: yes and you're very articulate and obviously have this you know, an
602 academic backgrounds and all that kind of stuff I'm interviewing people have a wide variety
603 of backgrounds.

604 INTERVIEWER: Skills your pace, so the other day I interviewed a Catholic woman who's
605 probably been praying her Rosary from the day she was born kind of thing yeah.

606 INTERVIEWER: And you know her throwing herself into the saints, you know that's her
607 approach she throws himself into the saints.

608 INTERVIEWER: But it wasn't the same kinds of academic discussion that you and I could
609 have it was it was different but still valuable everybody's approach is valuable that's what I'm
610 getting from this and our churches, need to be able to work with people whatever angle
611 they're coming from.

612 PETER: that's what we're hoping.

613 PETER: To do that as well with our group and how can we congregations can be so open.

614 PETER: and welcoming to these people. And it takes some education, it takes teaching and
615 showing them so.

616 INTERVIEWER: Yes, and a sense of openness that it's Okay, if someone gets up in the
617 middle of a sermon.

618 PETER: Yes.

619 INTERVIEWER: You know it's it's Okay, if someone puts on their coats and walks out or you
620 know starts to laugh or whatever it might be, this is just another expression of humans, the
621 way we are yeah and it's all getting to be okay with that yeah.

622 INTERVIEWER: Thank you, thank you, thank you.

623 PETER: Thank you, I appreciate you contacting me and if there's anything else, I can do
624 please just don't hesitate.

g) Andrew

- 1 INTERVIEWER: Tell me a little bit about yourself – anything you feel like sharing, your life,
2 your family. I have been calling you “Otto” is that ok.
- 3 ANDREW: I’m usually called Andrew -SHE only has 1 name (laughs, points to wife) and I
4 have 2. I can’t tell you why...but there you go.
- 5 INTERVIEWER: Both are good names
- 6 ANDREW: oh yes, yes. Despite having two names, they STILL let me go in to teach
7 people/
- 8 INTERVIEWER: So you were a teacher –
- 9 ANDREW: Of sorts yes
- 10 INTERVIEWER: What did you teach
- 11 ANDREW: Now I won’t give you the cheeky answer. I taught mathematics and what else –
12 WIFE: astronomy
- 13 INTERVIEWER: So clearly very clever
- 14 Andrew – I don’t know about that [laughs]
- 15 INTERVIEWER: telling about my maths experience
- 16 INTERVIEWER: And you’ve been a life long church goer? What church is that?
- 17 ANDREW: takes a minute – Church of Scotland
- 18 INTERVIEWER: My husband’s parents are lifelong c of s...but I love them all, all the
19 Churches.
- 20 ANDREW: that’s a good way of going about things.
- 21 INTERVIEWER: So I was hoping you might be able to tell me a little bit about how you feel
22 about having a diagnosis, Alzheimer’s. Share with me your thoughts on dementia.]
- 23 ANDREW: ughhhhh that’s the answer! [contextual]
- 24 WIFE: [Explains that he handles it very well but gets quite annoyed in car when he can’t find
25 his way home]
- 26 ANDREW: yes that’s putting it best. I don’t always remember things I used to know about in
27 the past. And that’s frustrating – its frustrating, I used to know how to get home. Considering
28 some of the things I used to do in the past...hill walking...and not getting lost. It frustrates
29 me that I have whatever its called.
- 30 INTERVIEWER: I don’t do Munros...I look at them...my husband does them. I like to look
31 and have a cup of hot chocolate.
- 32 ANDREW: that’s an interesting way of doing it. Ill come along and keep the hot chocolate
33 for you.

34 INTERVIEWER: So tell me a little bit, have you considered how you feel in terms of your
35 faith or God, and spirituality then getting this illness.

36 ANDREW: I have no problems

37 INTERVIEWER: You Don't feel angry?

38 ANDREW: nope.

39 INTERVIEWER: Do you have any favourite Bible stories that you can remember?

40 ANDREW: Off hand, no I used to have but at the present moment I can't tell you off hand.

41 INTERVIEWER: there are so many sometimes its hard to sit down and choose

42 INTERVIEWER: Have you ever thought about suffering from a Christian sense. Whether we
43 as believers in God, that part of our path is to suffer.

44 ANDREW: I just accept that as a possibility.

45 INTERVIEWER: Its sounds like you have a positive attitude

46 ANDREW: I don't know that's its positive but its there. Its all simply there.

47 INTERVIEWER: what about Christian hope – have you thought much of hope.

48 ANDREW: Hope - that's that the position.

49 INTERVIEWER: Does going to church help you?

50 ANDREW: Yes I enjoy going to church. I'm quite happy to go to church.

51 INTERVIEWER: How would you describe to me why you love God or being a Christian –
52 how being a Christian impacts you?

53 ANDREW: now that is an interesting question. How do you answer that? I have been brought
54 up and I've stuck with it.

55 INTERVIEWER: Is it a source of comfort

56 ANDREW: I think so! I know so!

57 INTERVIEWER: What I'm hearing from you is a great deal of conviction – it's a part of your
58 life, brought up with it, stuck with it. And you are not angry with God?

59 ANDREW: no no – I'm not angry. It is.

60 INTERVIEWER: You accept

61 ANDREW: Yes.

62 INTERVIEWER: What other types of things can you tell me about your journey with
63 dementia.

64 ANDREW: [jokes with his wife – points to her]

65 ANDREW: My wife and family have come first – have taken care of me. Its super to have
66 them like that. They look after me and hopefully I can look after them. I can look after them
67 too.

68 INTERVIEWER: that is fantastic.

69 ANDREW: [joking about his family then says] “and music.”

70 INTERVIEWER: Do you like music?

71 ANDREW: Oh yes

72 WIFE: He plays the piano

73 ANDREW: Yes I have not recently played, I used to play banjo, I play the piano most days,
74 and...

75 WIFE: and trombone!

76 INTERVIEWER: [laughs] and slide trombone, and banjo.

77 INTERVIEWER: I’m struck at how much you have in common with my husband.

78 ANDREW: [joking about picking out tunes and playing by ear.]

79 ANDREW: Play by ear – well you should see my ears!

80 INTERVIEWER: You have a sense of humour which is fantastic

81 ANDREW: It helps. Oh very definitely

82 INTERVIEWER: Do you have any thoughts about what the church can do to help you or
83 Carol

84 ANDREW: Some folks don’t have a good attitude. that’s their loss (those who don’t have
85 same attitude) – if they can be persuaded gently to have a better attitude towards their illness.
86 I’m not judging but want people to have a better attitude.

87 ANDREW: The fact that you can go along to the church and maybe some afternoon during
88 the week, have a coffee, theres a “come and sing”

89 CAROL: [explains the dementia friendly services]

90 ANDREW: well I’m just demented! [says this when wife refers to dementia friendly services]

91 ANDREW: I have a peculiar sense of humour.

92 INTERVIEWER: When people at church come to you or talk to you, is there any way that
93 you feel like they should approach you or listen to you.

94 ANDREW: not really – I’m quite happy to go and chat with people, after the service, go for a
95 chat, some are people who I know are not members of the church but just go along, and I chat
96 to them, I would chat to the members of the church session.

97 CAROL: so many people said Hello Andrew. And that made him feel good.

98 ANDREW: oh yes. Most of the names I'm really Otto - but I'm called Andrew. Anyone who
 99 knows me knows I'm Andrew (amongst other things...!) They come to me and say "hi
 100 Andrew" and I know they know me. They come to me.

101 INTERVIEWER: Is there anything you'd like to tell me, anything you'd like to share about
 102 your faith or your dementia...

103 ANDREW: if there was any way of being able to counter this dementia problem I would be
 104 interested in studying it at least. Id have least have a look at it. Because that's a very
 105 important part if I can get rid of the dementia that would be good.

106 ANDREW: if you come this way you are not a stranger.

107 [Closing conversation and chatting].

108 [SECOND INTERVIEW]

109 INTERVIEWER: So we talked about different things, but a few things you told me about
 110 yourself Andrew was that you are very musical man you've played many instruments and that
 111 you were very musical. And that that was always been important to you, I also have in my
 112 notes that you were quite a keen, and probably still are, a very keen walker. And you told me
 113 some interesting things about your church and about how you even though covid had come
 114 and sometimes you couldn't go when you could go how much it meant to you when people
 115 came up to you and spoke to you and used your name. And you liked when people
 116 remembered who you are, and that was quite you know quite a comforting thing to you, and
 117 then we talked a little bit about your belief in God and the fact that you had been a lifelong
 118 churchgoer. So I'm not going to keep you all long, but I just had a few follow up questions
 119 because they encourage us to do the second interview some months down the line. And
 120 anything you're comfortable answering you don't have to answer anything you can turn off
 121 your resume whenever you want there's absolutely no rules just whatever you feel like
 122 saying.

123 ANDREW: Well, as you realize, I have been involved in doing things for other people and
 124 the past. To help them with say, you know, various different things, maybe, people who have
 125 been. I've always liked to help people. I've forgotten, what was it I helped with at school?

126 WIFE: It was in maths.

127 ANDREW: Of course, of course – it was maths tuition.

128 INTERVIEWER: yes I remember that you'd been a math teacher.

129 WIFE: Yes, and you also did the Duke of Edinburgh to award scheme only took people out
 130 for walks .

131 INTERVIEWER: wonderful wonderful so you're somebody who likes to help people.

132 ANDREW: Yes, say I like to help people, but it's also very nice to be able to go in to do
 133 these things and get out. When I think of the places that I have actually walked.

134 ANDREW: This is not meant as boasting but weve been great places. |

- 135 ANDREW: What we have done because [redacted] and I have been to the far side of the
136 world and being for of very nice long walk. On gosh where was it...
- 137 WIFE: the Great Wall of China Great Wall of China.
- 138 ANDREW: Yes! The great wall of China! We've been there.
- 139 INTERVIEWER: I'm very jealous actually I would love to see that part of the world. The
140 Great Wall of China so you've had a lot of interesting experiences.
- 141 ANDREW: and, hopefully, it has not stopped.
- 142 INTERVIEWER: It hasn't stopped.
- 143 INTERVIEWER: Yes, and hopefully the world is opening up a bit more now that everyone's
144 had their vaccines and we are all a bit more comfortable going out. Have you been getting to
145 church recently.
- 146 ANDREW: Not So much. Well, we haven't been since before we went on holiday just
147 because, of course that's quite a while all must be about four or five weeks yeah.
- 148 WIFE: and then I had covid. So its been a good 4 or 5 weeks!
- 149 INTERVIEWER: Okay, so I'm going to ask you, the last time we talked I had asked you
150 about your feelings about God. When you get wet unwell or feelings about your dementia -
151 how God fits in. I had asked before if you ever got angry at God and you, you had said quite
152 clearly know that you did not feel anger towards God and that you came to a point in your
153 life, where you accepted what came to you, so I wondered I just wondered if you still feel that
154 way, if you have anything more you want to add to that.
- 155 ANDREW: As you said. No I think that's very straightforward. Its very straightforward. Its
156 as you said.
- 157 INTERVIEWER: So no blame. You don't blame God for when negative things happen - and
158 would you say that God is a source of comfort.
- 159 ANDREW: I would think, yes, because of problems that come up. The occasional problem
160 comes up and I pray about this. It helps to get me doing things. Considering I have problems.
161 Physical problems - probably mental as well. So I can pray. I think I can pray when there are
162 problems.
- 163 INTERVIEWER: Prayer can be a very calming thing and make us feel quite centered and
164 calm, I agree with you there prayer can be a wonderful thing to rely on. Another person I
165 interviewed said she had quite the sense of humour herself and she said. "I don't think I
166 would have gotten to age 98 without believing in God, because my belief in God has stopped
167 me from killing all the people I've gotten angry at.
- 168 ANDREW: laughs and laughs and says "my goodness"! Yes yes sense of humour. I've
169 always had it.
- 170 INTERVIEWER: About Oh, this is interesting, so the other thing I had asked you about and
171 again there's no right or wrong answers is, if you have any favourite Bible stories. |

172 ANDREW: I pray and read the Bible. I read the Bible at night. I can't think of stories right
173 now.

174 INTERVIEWER: Anything maybe through time or that you've particularly enjoyed hearing at
175 church or that you find particularly comforting.

176 ANDREW: We need to think about that for. There are some people who we occasionally
177 meet who are much worse state than I. So I accept. But I think we're getting on quite well.
178 And we are lucky. I don't want others getting on badly but I see they are and know I'm lucky.

179 ANDREW: I think that's that's important for all of us, whatever we're going through not that
180 we want bad luck for anybody else.

181 INTERVIEWER: But sometimes it helps to think Oh, "you know actually I'm lucky because
182 there were people who might not have as much as I do you know if there's a there are
183 different ways of looking at things." And yes there were always people that that need our
184 prayers and our help. So - final question for you is if your church or any of the groups, you go
185 to could be more supportive is there anything that you like that churches do or an or wish
186 they didn't do, or they could do better. In terms of helping people as they get older and things
187 change and they maybe have dementia, or maybe have physical illnesses that churches can do
188 better to help people.

189 ANDREW: I think our Church does very well. You know, when I was 12, I was asked by my
190 Church to ring the Church bell. It was a long day, but I went early, to ring the bell. It could
191 sometimes be quite tricky, keeping it going.

192 INTERVIEWER: You were heralding people to church, and that is beautiful.

193 ANDREW: I was 5, or 12. How old was I? I rang the bell for many years. Did you know,
194 when you ring the bell, your body moves with the bell? The rope moves, the bell moves, and
195 you move. One time I rang it too hard and broke it. It all went wonky. (laughs). And it was
196 loud so loud. But I was strong. I moved with it. And one time I threw the rope over the bell
197 and it didn't work. It was all my body, I had to do it right.

198 INTERVIEWER: Do you know I'm glad you said that about when you're ringing the bell it
199 kind of moves your body and you move along with it. And i'll tell you why because part of
200 what my project is doing, as well as a few other people who are working on similar ish
201 projects about about faith and Christianity is looking at the link between the use of our
202 bodies. And our belief system so for the, for example, for the Roman Catholics white
203 interviewed I interviewed some Catholics. You know, in the Roman Catholic Church it's a
204 very physical church you're on your knees crossing yourself. The spirituality is almost
205 expressed in a physical way and I thought of that when you were mentioning the bell and
206 how somebody ringing the bell is heralding the people in and using their body to do so and
207 contributing to the church and it's all quite a spiritual experience. So that's that's really, really
208 interesting and I know it was a long time ago, when you were a little boy so.

h) Charlotte

1 (Introductions and chit chat. CHARLOTTE was very enthusiastic and smiley. We discussed
2 the reason behind my research and reviewed all the consent material. CHARLOTTE's sense
3 of humour emerged even at the start of the interview. She asked ME about my life and joked
4 with ME about having teenagers. She said "imagine a little girl like you has two such big
5 boys". She proudly told ME she is 98 years old and has a visitor coming in the afternoon. She
6 asked the care staff for coffee and tea and said "please bring my little girl here Some coffee
7 and tea too". It took a while to get to the interview questions and she said "make them simple
8 now.....its not a quiz!"

9 INTERVIEWER: How do you feel about God? Tell ME about your faith and your
10 understanding of dementia.

11 CHARLOTTE: Omnipotent! That's what He is. He is omnipotent.

12 INTERVIEWER: What types of feelings did you have when you were diagnosed with
13 dementia?

14 CHARLOTTE: Well I just accepted it. I don't get angry at anyone. Not for a long time. I
15 don't get angry now, maybe when I was young. But I'm older now.

16 INTERVIEWER: Does your faith influence how you understand having dementia?

17 CHARLOTTE: Oh yes, I was very ill once, and I prayed, and God made ME better. God
18 helps ME. I'm sure He says something every day of our lives. Life would be harder if I didn't
19 believe and when I die, the last journey. God helps in these things. I never thought I had
20 dementia. You don't think of these things. You just kind of go on and call on God.

21 INTERVIEWER: How do you feel about suffering?

22 CHARLOTTE: God suffered on the Cross....it depends on the person, depends on the
23 suffering.....I don't blame God for suffering, why should I? I might as well blame YOU.
24 (and she laughs).

25 INTERVIEWER: You have a sense of humour don't you...

26 CHARLOTTE: It's a good point. You have to see the laughing side of things.....you don't
27 know I'm really 20 years old (burst out laughing, touches her hair)

28 We are happy where we are - but we don't go on forever. Of course, He's [God] always with
29 ME and you, too, whether we like it or not. Everyone's in heaven except ME - it has to
30 happen - it's a mixture...I like being here but I miss people in Heaven. But God is always
31 here for ME.

32 (At this point CHARLOTTE started asking ME more about my family, wanting to know the
33 names of my children, and my husband, and my life in America. She was happy and off the
34 subject of her diagnosis. Then she said she was getting tired, and I offered to call the care
35 staff for her, which she accepted. Even as she was being wheeled away she was smiling at
36 ME and said "now be good!"

Appendix 7: Transcript Coding Grid Example (Adela)

Transcript Snippets	Codes beginning to emerge/ Exploratory Notes/My reflective Diary Notes	Experiential Themes emerging/shining from experiential statements	Clustered Themes (for cross participant themes)	GEM	Empathy/Suspicion
<p>Beginning conversation. Review of consent and getting comfortable. Then on to interview.</p> <p>Me: Tell me a bit about your life and about your faith – tell me a little bit about you.</p> <p>Adela: Faith is everything. If I didn't have hope and trust I'd be absolutely desolate.</p>	<p>Adela presented as very friendly, very happy to have me chatting with her.</p> <p>Hope and trust and mercy come out strongly – “can't live without it.”</p> <p>From my reflective notes written after interview: “Adela is very clear in how she expresses herself and very clear in her convictions about faith. I note her use of words like “desolate”. There's a real juxtaposition/showing of opposites in how she expresses her thoughts – “everything” vs “desolate”.</p>	<p>“It is” and its total.</p>		<p>Further down I suggest that the word INFINTAE might be a GEM. There is something about the “totality” in how Adela expressed herself. This section where she says “faith is everything” might be part of that “totality”. She tends to use words of absolutes.</p>	<p>Its interesting, the use of the word desolate, juxtaposed to “everything”. Is there something in the way she uses “absolutes” that can be deconstructed? Desolate is a very strong word.</p>
<p>Adela continues: Belief in</p>	<p>Repetition of a specific prayer. There is</p>	<p>Ritual Matters</p>	<p>“Gods Innocence”.</p>	<p>Could Infinite be a GEM?</p>	

Transcript Snippets	Codes beginning to emerge/ Exploratory Notes/My reflective Diary Notes	Experiential Themes emerging/shining from experiential statements	Clustered Themes (for cross participant themes)	GEM	Empathy/Suspicion
<p>God helps me – I say “Infinite mercy help me”. I say that all the time. I repeat it. “Infinite mercy - help me.” I say that and I say it.</p>	<p>something about repetition that is important to Adela. I note as well how she calls God “Infinite Mercy”.</p> <p>Notes from my reflections, written after my interview: “I like how Adela “talks to” aspects of her faith. She “talks to” Infinite Mercy.</p>	<p>God’s infinite mercy.</p>	<p>Gods power is in Love. Process Theology. All of my participants discussed talking to God and asking Him to spread comfort. None asked Him to change their condition. This might be a part of what I’m calling</p>	<p>There is something about the totality of it. The repetition and the totality. Perhaps this understanding of the Infinite helps her through the “temporary” of her diagnosis? I note above other words that imply “total”.</p>	
<p>Adela (who kept talking): I was a head teacher in a catholic school. I believed in helping all</p>	<p>From my reflective notes – I jotted down how Adela struck me as “ahead of her time” in terms of teaching technique. She repeated a few</p>	<p>Nobody is beyond help. All humans matter. Even in struggles we matter. “WE MATTER”.</p>	<p>See Me/Radical Recognition.</p>	<p>Above I propose INFINITE</p>	

Transcript Snippets	Codes beginning to emerge/ Exploratory Notes/My reflective Diary Notes	Experiential Themes emerging/shining from experiential statements	Clustered Themes (for cross participant themes)	GEM	Empathy/Suspicion
<p>the children. Whatever their ability, if they were good students or struggles. I worked with them all. I'd go into the classroom and work with them, sit at the desk with them. I sat right down. Nobody is beyond help. Nobody".</p>	<p>times how "all students" needed attention. I also note how she went into the classroom, and "sat right down". The "bodily" is in much of the way she phrases material.</p>	<p>The Body Matters/SEE them/See me/Radical Recognition.</p>		<p>as a GEM. Although Adela doesn't actively expand on this word - there are ways throughout this interview that she shows she hold to the "infinite" in her thinking.</p> <p>There is something about her being there for all students – good and bad – that feels connected to how she sees God – as always there – for everyone. Could this relate to INIFINITE as a GEM? (see Gem column).</p>	

Transcript Snippets	Codes beginning to emerge/ Exploratory Notes/My reflective Diary Notes	Experiential Themes emerging/shining from experiential statements	Clustered Themes (for cross participant themes)	GEM	Empathy/Suspicion
<p>Adela – at this point – asking if she can say more about her life – I answered “of course”</p> <p>Adela: I had 1 daughter, my son died - If I hadn’t had my faith I don’t know where I’d be...it was the only thing that could help me. It’s the only thing that can help me. He was in an accident. It was so sad. It was so long ago. But my faith keeps me.”</p> <p>(Adela started to look very sad and tear</p>	<p>I notice the use of the PRESENT in how she expresses herself – it wasn’t just “then” that God helped. Its “now”.</p> <p>In my reflective notes I noted how sad Adela’s face became when she spoke of her son – and that she tilted her head back up and looked away, then looked at me, talking of her sadness. It also moved me – how long ago it was and how clearly it still impacts her. I also reflected on the decision to keep going with the interview – Adela didn’t want to stop, and theres something empowering about having people able</p>	<p>Faith alone – the bedrock. Life without faith – means lost. “Faith keeps me”.</p>			

Transcript Snippets	Codes beginning to emerge/ Exploratory Notes/My reflective Diary Notes	Experiential Themes emerging/shining from experiential statements	Clustered Themes (for cross participant themes)	GEM	Empathy/Suspicion
<p>up – in line with my protocol and ethical social work practice, I gave her time to express herself and compose herself, and also asked about stopping the interview – she said she wanted to continue. I also asked if she needed me to get the nurses. Adela explained that she always teared up when speaking of her son. She said “I am fine. I am ok. I talk about my son. I’m ok”. She made it very clear</p>	<p>and willing to listen to her sadness. The nurses confirmed for me that this is important for Adela – talking about her son – she wants and expected people to listen and be kind to her.</p>				

Transcript Snippets	Codes beginning to emerge/ Exploratory Notes/My reflective Diary Notes	Experiential Themes emerging/shining from experiential statements	Clustered Themes (for cross participant themes)	GEM	Empathy/Suspicion
she expected to be able to talk about her son, that it was important.					
<p>I thanked Adela for sharing this with me and acknowledged what a challenging life she has had. She reached for my hand at this point and held my hand. She said she was fine to keep going. We moved on to more questions:</p> <p>Me: How do you feel about your diagnosis? And your relationship with God now? Let's talk about your</p>	<p>No anger – this was said with conviction.</p> <p>I noted in my reflective notes how simply and clearly this was stated. I also noted in my reflective notes my own surprise – “I’m surprised – I did expect more anger. “Do people not have anger or not feel they can express it? I can’t make assumptions about this”.</p>	<p>No Blame.</p> <p>“God is God, and my diagnosis is my diagnosis.”</p> <p>Radical Acceptance</p> <p>“He Is” – linked to the GEM of “infinity”?</p>	<p>Gods Innocence</p> <p>This is a common theme throughout all the interviews.</p>		<p>“It doesn’t matter”. But also “I only just ask God to help me”. Both exist simultaneously – the acceptance “it doesn’t matter” AND the need to ask for help.</p>

Transcript Snippets	Codes beginning to emerge/ Exploratory Notes/My reflective Diary Notes	Experiential Themes emerging/shining from experiential statements	Clustered Themes (for cross participant themes)	GEM	Empathy/Suspicion
<p>diagnosis and your feelings about faith.</p> <p>Adela: I Never feel angry at God I only just ask God to help me...I don't feel angry. He is there and He helps me. It doesn't matter -my diagnosis.</p>					
	<p>I note how she says "I just ask for help" – there is a sense of the actual help being IN the asking.</p>				
<p>Me: Tell me about the Christian virtue of Hope? How do you consider Hope?</p> <p>Adela: "I have a conviction about hope</p>	<p>Conviction, hope, universal application – Adela's use of the word conviction was said with adamance.</p>	<p>Absolute – no doubts – it IS – linked to "Infinity".</p> <p>God "is", Hope "is".</p> <p>It just IS.</p>		<p>I think Adela's thoughts on "hope" might help us explore INFINITE as a GEM. Her conviction – The Whole World –</p>	

Transcript Snippets	Codes beginning to emerge/ Exploratory Notes/My reflective Diary Notes	Experiential Themes emerging/shining from experiential statements	Clustered Themes (for cross participant themes)	GEM	Empathy/Suspicion
– “absolutely” – I hope – and if the whole world were like that what a happy world we would have”.				Adela expresses her words in BIG fashion.	
Adela: One thing to say - “God I love you, Jesus take me into your kingdom, never abandon me. You’re the source of my hope in life”. Keep saying that.	This statement was said in conjunction with my question about “hope”. She seemed to relate repeating this prayer to her hope. I note how she has told me two phrases/prayers she regularly says. There is something about repetitive prayer that is important to her.	Rituals Matter.			
Adela: I go to Mass every day – It helps me spiritually ...I feel close to God...they take me	Ritual – the ritual of prayer and the ritual of Mass. She depends on people to take her down to Mass. Feeling “close to God” –	Help Me Worship Rituals Matter See Me	See Me/Radical Recognition		

Transcript Snippets	Codes beginning to emerge/ Exploratory Notes/My reflective Diary Notes	Experiential Themes emerging/shining from experiential statements	Clustered Themes (for cross participant themes)	GEM	Empathy/Suspicion
down to Mass.	relationship of her body to God				
Adela: Saint Jude is my favourite saint...the forgotten saint because of his name...they mix up the Judes! I love the Jude mix up. But he's my saint. (Adela laughs joyously when she talked about the "mix up")	Sense of humour – I jotted in my notes after the interview how many times Adela laughed in her conversation with me. She clearly liked to laugh.	Humour Heals	Humour/the double edged sword.		
Me: tell me what our Priests and Ministers and others do to help with your dementia journey.	Being close to us; bodies coming together. Using words such as "closer" to God. I wrote in my notes "Id like to link this to Merleau-Ponty".	Bodies matter; closeness matters. SEE ME/Radical Recognition.	SEE ME Radical Dependence.		

Transcript Snippets	Codes beginning to emerge/ Exploratory Notes/My reflective Diary Notes	Experiential Themes emerging/shining from experiential statements	Clustered Themes (for cross participant themes)	GEM	Empathy/Suspicion
<p>Adela: it gives me a great deal of consolation to have a Priest here. And the sisters. It is Helpful to have Priests near to us, talk to us...to come to us, I'm sitting here and they come to me.... I get closer to God as I get older... I'm sorry for those who don't believe...they don't know what they are missing.</p>		<p>Come to Me/Radical Dependence</p>			